

THE GOVERNANCE AND LOCAL INTEGRATION OF MIGRANTS AND EUROPE'S REFUGEES

Work Package 2: Deliverable 2.1

2018

Introduction	1
Sweden and Malmo	
1. Approaches to asylum and integration in Sweden	5
1.1 From 1945 to the 1970s	6
1.2 From the 1980s until 2010	10
1.3 From 2010 onwards	13
2. Immigration and asylum in Malmö	17
2.1 Integration, networks and governance in Malmö	22
3. An overview of the WP topics in Malmö	24
WP3: Regeneration and urban exclusion	24
WP4: Education and developing linguistic competences	26
WP5: Integration into the labour market and skills training	28
WP6: Gender dynamics of reception and integration	29
References	30
Italy and Calabria	
1. Approaches to asylum and integration in Italy	33
1.1 From constitutional republic of 1948 to 1990	33
1.2 From emergencies of 1990 to 2002	33
1.3 North African Emergency of 2011 (ENA) and its impact on the accommodation asylum system	34
1.4 The complexity of the Italian asylum accommodation system	36
1.5 The SPRAR system	38
1.6 Differences between first reception and the SPRAR system	40
2. Calabria, immigration and asylum	41
2.1 Integration, networks and governance in Calabria	43
3. Integration in Calabria	45
3.1 Regeneration and urban exclusion	45
3.2 Education and developing linguistic competences	47
3.3 Integration into the labour market and skills training	50
3.4 Gender dynamics of reception and integration	54
Appendix A: Abbreviations and Acronyms	57
References	58

The UK and Glasgow

1. Approaches to asylum and integration in the UK	60
1.1 1945 – late 1990s	61
1.2 Late 1990s-2010s	63
2. Scotland, immigration and asylum	68
2.1 Integration, networks and governance in Glasgow	74
3. Integration in Glasgow	76
3.1 Regeneration, accommodation and urban exclusion	76
3.2 Education and developing linguistic competences	78
3.3 Integration into the labour market and skills training	80
3.4 Gender dynamics of reception and integration	82
Appendix A: Abbreviations and Acronyms	84
Appendix B: Selected Relevant Legislation and Policy	85
Appendix C: UK Asylum and Refugee Pathways	86
References	87

Cyprus and Nicosia

1 Key events and demographic developments in migration	95
1.1 Development of a 'national integration policy'	99
2. Cyprus Immigration and Asylum	103
2.1 Regeneration and urban exclusion	103
2.2 Education and developing linguistic competences	107
2.3 Integration into the labour market and skills training	111
References	118

The Governance and the Local Integration of Migrants and Europe's Refugees (GLIMER)

Overview

Migration and integration, especially the reception of refugees and displaced peoples, are widely shared social and political challenges across Europe. The purpose of GLIMER is to understand how the governance and local integration of migrants and Europe's refugees is developing, and in ways that can be utilised through best practice sharing and reporting. Inspired by the success of 'welcoming cities' in southern Italy, we will work with civil society groups, local authorities, citizens and refugee groups in order to support sustainable the meaningful integration of diverse communities. We will focus on cities in both Southern and Northern Europe and a key aspect of the project will be dedicated to investigating how the local governance of new arrivals can secure successful integration across a range of indicators. This research will be carried out in close collaboration with practitioners with the aim of co-producing knowledge that can be beneficial for a range of stakeholders including civil society groups and NGOs as well as municipalities.

Project objectives and targets

Migration is embedded in the economies and societies of contemporary European countries. However, where regulated inward economic migration, while remaining open to dispute, has largely been accepted as a structural feature in most EU systems (Czaika and de Haas 2015), the reception and incorporation of displaced people in EU countries remains a contentious topic. This project investigates the local policy implications of the immediate and pressing crisis of refugee displacement and arrival. According to the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), over 1.6 million migrants and refugees entered Europe in 2015 alone (IOM 2015). This 'Refugee Crisis', recently characterised as the 'new normal' by the European Commission (2016), is felt both by frontline and final destination states. Despite the principle of sharing numbers of people according to relative economic strength and country size, as outlined in the EU Task Force for the Mediterranean and wider EU Strategic Guidelines, countries in both Southern and Northern Europe are being forced to find innovative solutions at local and city levels to manage the arrival, flow and settlement of people. One of the overlooked outcomes of this development is that new modes of governance are observable which are characterised by two striking features. The first is that local and city level articulations of migrant and refugee reception are sometimes significantly diverging from national level policy and rhetoric. Possibly an illustration of 'decoupling' across geographies of policy delivery (Pope and Meyer 2016: 290), this local variation is patterned by ground-level politics, local strategic incentives, and pre-existing economic resources in a manner that requires further scientific investigation through live cases. The second is that local and city level forms of reception of migrants and

refugees are leading to patterns of successful early integration. These include those cultivated by associations from the third sector which have assumed a key role in what Elia (2013: 36) has termed 'bottom up welfare'. In this respect, a number of towns in the southern Italian region of Calabria have led pioneering schemes to welcome migrants, incorporating them into the local labour market (Bruckner 2016), while further examples can also be found in Glasgow, Malmo and Nicosia. The methods and structure of GLIMER are informed by the following project goals:

- To combine qualitative research with action research, bringing academics together with end-users to provide innovative solutions to displaced migrant and refugee integration.
- To convey the research results in operational ways through the elaboration of site-specific strategies able to generate an immediate impact within the research project's development.
- To disseminate the results as widely as possible, in the EU and worldwide, devising strategies to involve relevant communities, stakeholders, practitioners, policy makers, housing and educational institutions.
- To involve local stakeholder and populations in the strategies of co-production to support the creation of inclusive and vibrant communities.
- To offer coherent and sustainable policy recommendations to urban governance institutions to support diversity and the development of vibrant urban communities.

Theoretically, GLIMER is informed by two established conceptual approaches that have not been sufficiently brought together to understand the current challenge. The first understands migration and refugee reception as reflecting the ways in which modern societies have grown so complex, dynamic and differentiated that no single system can exercise hierarchical and bureaucratic control over the movement and reception of people. What this means is that we need to understand migrant integration as an issue of governance which entails dispersed networks based on partnerships, and the blurring of boundaries between state and civil society (Elia and Fantozzi 2013). As such, GLIMER moves away from seeing the arrival of displaced migrants and refugees as purely a matter of central government which is more top-down, centralised, bureaucratic and state-centric. This is crucial where the governance of migration relies on a 'mixed economy' of welfare provision that involves working in partnership with '3rd sector' (voluntary, community sector) organisations and NGOs at various levels through service delivery, consultation and partnerships, and which are especially evident in the reception and integration of new arrivals (McDaniel, 2016). This broad tendency is accentuated in austere economic times, where the diffusion of state responsibility outwards to civil society may also be understood as the acceptable face of spending cuts. However, most previous research into the governance of migration

emphasises either bottom-up participation of grassroots citizens or top-down influence from the state. Both of these perspectives are limited because civil society is composed of mediating institutions that blur distinctions between top and bottom (O'Toole and Meer 2016). Indeed, some researchers recognise that migration governance produces hybrid categories like the 'expert citizen' (Bang 2005), and that it is important to bring together top-down and bottom-up perspectives into the study of migrant and refugee reception (Cornwall and Coelho 2006, Lowndes and Thorp 2010). As the initial findings from the Prospects for International Migration Governance (MIGPROSP) project (funded by the European Research Council) has shown, in national level migration policy 'not only is change seen as difficult to deliver, but change itself is viewed as problematic because of the possibility of unforeseen consequences in an unstable and highly politicised policy field' (Geddes 2016). Local innovation is therefore a profoundly important space and GLIMER will offer an analysis of the relationship between civil society and governance in our respective cases, and will be well-placed to observe forms of 'ethnic capital' (Modood 2004) and productive spaces of civil society both in support of migrants and refugees as well as by migrants and refugees themselves.

The second conceptual frame, integration, is as established as it is contested and has been described as 'a concept both dazzling and treacherous' (Saggar and Sommerville 2012: 6). While integration is often a primary policy objective, its relationship to governance is unclear. A theoretical concern with integration is as old as the earliest social scientific accounts of modernity, in so far as how social scientists have conceptualised the division of labour and the kinds of social relations that characterise modern societies. Latterly, and especially as it was translated through the work in US ethnic and racial studies (Meer, 2014), the concept has come to describe post-migration relations. Castles et al. (2002: 17-18) offer a useful delineation for what a concept of integration can resemble, especially at it relates to migration:

- Usage 1: The process through which migrants and refugees become part of the receiving society. Integration is often used in a normative way, to imply a one-way process of adaptation by newcomers to fit in with a dominant culture and way of life.
- Usage 2: A two-way adaptive process involving changes in values, norms and behaviour for both newcomers and members of the existing society. This includes recognition of the role of the ethnic community and the idea that broader social patterns and cultural values may change in response to immigration (ibid: 17–18).

The following key research questions - taken up across each thematically specific work-package – will guide the research:

1. To what extent are cities and local contexts adopting approaches to the governance of migration and refugees that diverge from national level policy positions?
2. How and in what ways are cities and localities cultivating innovative approaches in the reception and integration of migrants and refugees?
3. Which approaches are proving successful and how can we model this for other contexts to learn from?

These three core research questions will be empirically pursued across the substantive work-packages dedicated to data collection on:

- WP3: Accommodation and Regeneration
- WP4: Education and Developing Linguistic Competences
- WP5: Integration into the Labour Market and Skills Training
- WP6: Gender Dynamics across Reception and Integration

Work Package 2: Sweden and Malmö

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1. APPROACHES TO ASYLUM AND INTEGRATION IN SWEDEN

In a historical perspective, Sweden has transformed from being a country of emigration to one of immigration.¹ Top emigration rates were reached in the 1880s. Immigration has exceeded emigration since 1931, but it didn't really take off until after the Second World War (Nilsson 2004). The proportion of foreign born residents in Sweden in 1930 was less than one per cent; in 2016 it reached almost 18 per cent. Over this period of time, the approaches to asylum and integration have shifted.

In the early post-war period, in particularly from the early 1950s to the late 1960s, the national borders were 'open' and most immigration was categorised as labour immigration. It was dominated by immigration from European countries. After this, from the early 1970s and until the late 2000s, labour immigration was very limited. The 1980s is usually described as the decade when immigration to Sweden shifted to non-European and refugee immigration. This is also the decade when the Swedish government reformed the system for the integration of refugees. In Sweden, on both policy and operational levels, there is a distinct separation between the reception of asylum seekers and the integration of refugees and their families. While the reception of asylum seekers has always been the responsibility of the state, between 1985 and 2010 the reception of refugees was transferred from state to local authorities. The Swedish welfare model, as it developed after the Second World War, has meant that civil society organisations have played a marginal role in the reception and integration of asylum seekers and refugees. As the model have transformed, in particularly since the 1990s, the role of civil society organisations has changed. Below, we describe the shifting approaches to asylum and integration divided into three periods.

1. In a long-term historical perspective, the development of Sweden has, of course, depended on immigration (see e.g. Harrison 2016).

1.1 From 1945 to the 1970s

In Swedish immigration history, the period after the Second World War and up until the oil crisis in the early 1970s is typically depicted as a period of labour immigration. Although the relation between labour immigration and refugee immigration is contested, in Sweden the development of social rights and integration for refugees and their families must be understood in relation to how rights of labour migrants developed during this period. The early welfare state schemes were established to protect Swedes in Sweden, but after the Second World War foreign citizens, labour migrants and refugees alike, gained access to social rights and welfare services. Central to this development was the alliance between the ruling Social Democratic Party and the national confederation of Swedish trade unions (Landsorganisationen i Sverige, LO).

Many refugees left Sweden after the second world war, and very few new refugees arrived. At the same time, Sweden experienced economic growth, a booming industry and a labour power shortage. Already as the war was about to end, the Swedish government established an agreement with the Nordic countries about labour contracting of Nordic citizens. Building on this, in 1954, a common Nordic labour market was established. Nordic citizens could work and take up residence in other Nordic countries under the same conditions as national citizens. While the agreement was mutual, in practice it functioned to supply the Swedish labour market with workers, in principal from Finland (Byström and Frohnert 2017).

However, the Nordic immigration did not cover the labour shortage in Sweden. The Swedish government was cautious about opening up the borders for labour immigrations, not least on nationalist protectionist grounds (Johansson, J. 2008; Johansson, C. 2005; Byström 2012). Nevertheless, in 1946 the government appointed a group to prepare the recruitment of foreign labour (Beredningen för utländsk arbetskraft) and in 1948 a new authority, the Swedish Labour Market Board (Arbetsmarknadsstyrelsen, AMS) was established to manage labour market issues, including labour immigration as well as the reception of refugees and the selection of quota refugees (Byström 2012).

Swedish 'labour import' started slowly in 1947 (from e.g. Italy, Austria, Hungary), and from the early 1950s until 1967 the borders were in practice open for labour immigration. Over this period of time, 1950–1970, foreign born tripled from 200 000 to 538 000 in Sweden, Finnish born being the largest group (Nilsson 2004). In line with ideas central to the Swedish welfare state model – equality and universalism – it was established that foreign, also non-Nordic, residents should have the possibility to live on the same standards as natives. This was also in line with the ideals of the 1951 Refugee Convention. Another central aspect to this development was worries that immigrant labour would lead to dumped salaries and a worsening of work conditions. Against this background, the trade unions safeguarded that immigrant labourers were contracted under the same conditions and with the same salaries as national workers. In addition to this, trade union membership was made mandatory for migrant labourers (Johansson, C. 2005; Johansson, J. 2008). It should also be mentioned though, that foreigners gained access to different segments of Swedish social services and rights at very different pace (see e.g. Righard 2017).

From around the mid-1960s a discourse of immigration and immigrants as a societal problem grew strong; the adaptation of immigrants (invandrarnas anpassning) became a key topic. The discourses on the 'immigrant problem' (invandrarproblemet) had several grounds. One part of it had to do with a decline in the labour market, increase of immigration, and growing difficulties in finding job contracts. Additionally important was the severe housing shortage (e.g. Lundh 2010). Other factors that such as the change of immigrants' countries of origin (e.g. Yugoslavia and Turkey), in combination with discourses of national superiority and protectionism also played a role in this development (e.g. Johansson, C. 2005; see also Mulinari and Neergaard 2004). Starting in 1967, and through a number of sequential decisions by the government and the national confederation of the trade unions, non-Nordic labour immigration was definitely stopped in 1972 (Frank 2005). The bottom line argument for this shift set focus on the equality and universality of the Swedish welfare model. In order to maintain this model building on full employment in the population, labour immigration should be regulated and assessed against the structure of the Swedish labour market and labour force, including women (Frank 2005). The economic recession and the strained situation on the Swedish labour market that followed on the oil crisis and economic restructuring in the early 1970s, meant that immigration from the Nordic countries also slowed down and that return migration increased (Lundh 2010; Nilsson 2004). As labour immigration was stopped, the regulation of family reunification was liberated; family members were granted residence permit independently of labour market or supply conditions. Hence, obviously Sweden opted for another model than, for instance, the German guest worker model. At this time, the refugee immigration to come was not anticipated (Frank 2005; Byström and Frohnert 2017).

The debate on the adaptation of immigrants was influential in several ways. The government appointed the Immigrant Investigation (Invandrarutredningen, IU) which worked 1968–1974. This led to the establishment of a new field in Swedish politics, namely immigrant policy (invandrapolitik), what is usually referred to as integration policy. During the first period of debate on the immigrant issue, a political line of universalism was maintained. This meant that cultural, ethnic and religious activities and associations should stay outside the sphere of governmental intervention. However, following on the Immigrant Investigation and a governmental decision in 1975, Sweden took on a multiculturalist approach in integration politics. This has later been replaced by first a selective and then by a residual integration policy (Dahlström 2004). However, while on the rhetorical level, a number of distinct approaches to integration can be identified, in terms of implemented interventions, the Swedish approach to integration has remained rather constant. The table below, illustrate how politics have shifted over time, and that interventions started before politics was established, and once they were established most of them have remained even though politics changed.

	1964–1967	1968–1974	1975–1985	1986–1996	1997–
Rhetoric	No policy objective	Universal policy objectives (UO)	Multicultural policy objectives (MO)	Selective policy objectives (SO)	Universal policy objectives (UO)
Practice	1965 Information (SO) - Training in Swedish language (SO) 1966 Support for immigrant organizations (MO) 1967 Cultural support (MO) - Adult education (UO)	1968 Interpreters service (SO) 1970 Labour market programmes (SO) 1971 Training in mother tongue (MP) 1974 Support for religious organizations (IP)	1976 Support for troubled urban areas (SO) - Voting rights (UO) 1977 Support for newspapers and journals (MO)	1986 The support for newspapers and journals are cut off (MO)	

Figure 1. Immigrant policy objectives and programmes in Sweden, 1964–2000
Source: Källa: Dahlström 2004, p. 214.

In international comparisons of integration politics, Sweden is typically depicted as a country with an extensive integration policy (see e.g. the work by Will Kymlicka and Keith Banting). Indeed, in the latest updated version of the Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX), from 2015, Sweden scores number one out of 38 countries.² It should, however, also be recognised that Sweden scores low when labour market integration is compared (see also Brochmann and Hagelund 2011). For instance, when the difference in the employment rates between native and foreign born is compared, in Sweden huge differences are revealed. Unemployment rates are specifically higher among persons born in a non-European country and the newly arrived, but also among young persons in general (Bevelander and Pendakur 2009; Korpi and Tåhlin 2011; Dahlstedt 2017). Moreover, in a comparative European perspective, the gap is bigger for women than for men. For men, Sweden is third last after Denmark and Belgium, and for women Sweden is second last, after Denmark (OECD 2015, p. 69;).

After labour immigration stopped in the early 1970s, followed a period of relatively stable and limited net immigration, dominated by refugees and family members. Among the earlier refugee immigrations are Chileans (approx. 10 000) who came after the coup in 1973 and the so called boat refugees (approx. 6 000) from Vietnam who came after the war had ended in 1975. Large numbers of refugees have arrived from countries in the Middle East since 1975 and onwards. Since people are registered according to their nationality, important groups, such as the Kurds and Christian Assyrians are not registered in the statistics (Svanberg and Tydén 2005).

At this time, a more generous asylum policy developed. While it had emerged by way of praxis from the 1960s, in 1975 the government decided to extend the grounds for residence permit for asylum

2. MIPEX 2015, <http://www.mipex.eu/sweden>

seekers beyond the definition in the 1951 Geneva Convention. This regarded several groups, for instance, military service refusal (krigsvägran) now became a ground for residence permit, and persons who could not go back to their country of origin could now be granted residence permit as 'de facto refugees'. At this time, permanent residence permit was also introduced, as a measure to lessen the insecurity temporary permits implied. Of significance, not least in international comparison, is the introduction of voting rights in municipal elections for foreign residents (Byström and Frohnert 2017).

1.2 From the 1980s until 2010

From the mid-1980s, asylum applications and granted residence permit grew in numbers. Below are two graphs, the first showing the growing number of asylum seekers, and the second the relation between various forms of granted residence permit.

Figure 2. Asylum seekers per year, 1987–2015
Source: DELMI (our translation).

Figure 3. Type of residence permits, 1980–2016
Source: DELMI (our translation).

The increased number of asylum seekers and refugees led to political debate of the refugee reception. The Swedish Labour Market Board (Arbetsmarknadsstyrelsen, AMS) meant that the reception of asylum seekers and refugees was beyond their area of competence, and requested it to be transferred to the Swedish Immigration Agency (Statens invandrarverk, SIV). This happened in 1985 when the government implemented what has been named the Whole-of-Sweden Strategy (Hela Sverige strategin). This strategy meant that the Swedish Immigration Agency was made responsible for the reception of asylum seekers and asylum seeker facility accommodations where the asylum seekers were expected to stay for a limited period of time while their asylum application was managed. After residence permit had been granted, the responsibility was to be transferred to a municipality by way of a municipality placement (kommunplacering). The Whole-of-Sweden Strategy was meant as a way to support the integration of refugees, but also a way to disperse refugees in the country counteracting (ethnic) housing segregation in urban areas (Byström and Frohnert 2017).

However, the reception system did not live up to the demands and the Whole-of-Sweden Strategy was criticized from the beginning. One ground for critique was that the reception of refugees was transferred to local authorities' Social Service Departments. This meant that the reception of refugees was transformed from a labour market to a social issue; refugees who could not provide for themselves were associated with social problems. From 1992 the local authorities could pay a special Introduction Allowance (introduktionsersättning) to refugees in the Introduction Program (the first two years with residence permit)³. This was meant to make it more rights-based like, but many municipalities continued to pay out means tested social welfare (ekonomiskt bistånd) to refugees, also during the first two years of residence. Another criticism had its ground in the high and unforeseen numbers of refugees. In 1985 nine facility accommodations (flyktingförläggningar) hosted 1 500 asylum seekers. In 1993, and in spite of a more restrictive refugee immigration since December 1989 (Luciabeslutet), around 270 refugee facility accommodations hosted 90 000 asylum seekers (Lundh and Ohlsson 2004, ref. in Byström and Frohnert 2017, p. 73), the increase of refugees was partly due to the Balkan war. On top of this, some municipalities refused to contract municipality placements for refugees with the Swedish Immigration Agency (Statens invandrarverk). Hence, many refugees with residence permit were locked-in in facility accommodation with delayed integration as a consequence. The situation was unsustainable and, after ten years, the Whole-of-Sweden Strategy was abandoned (Byström and Frohnert 2017). In 1994 it was replaced by what is often referred to as Own Housing (Eget boende, EBO).

The Own Housing strategy, implemented in 1994, meant that asylum seekers can participate in daily activities and be eligible to day allowance (dagersättning) also when they reside outside of a Facility Housing (Anläggningsboende, ABO)⁴. Moreover, a housing allowance could be payed to persons in Own Housing. The reasons for implementing Own Housing was to avoid asylum seekers' passivity by emphasizing the responsibility the asylum seeker had for him/herself. The changed regulation resulted in increased concentrations of asylum seekers and refugees to certain neighbourhoods in urban areas such Stockholm, Gothenburg and Malmö (Boverket 2008). In Malmö, it was severely critiqued during the 2000's, as presented below.

The 1990s is a decade of growing inequalities in Sweden, foreign born being overrepresented at the lower end of the continuum. It is also a decade of fundamental restructuring of the Swedish model of welfare. This has led to far reached ethnic and socioeconomic housing segregation. Certain neighbourhoods reached unemployment rates of 95 per cent (Schierup 2010). Overall, housing and

3. Lag (1992:1068) om introduktionsersättning för flyktingar och vissa andra utlänningar.

4. Lag 1994:137 om mottagande av asylsökande

housing segregation is a field of growing political significance, also in relation to refugee immigration and reception.

The 1990s also implied a new, at least in the political discourse, relationship between the state and civil society. Sweden has a history of a strong civil society. Historically it is typically described in terms of 'people's movements' (folk rörelser) and refer as such, for instance, to the labour movement, the non-alcoholic movement, and faith based movements with roots in the nineteenth century. The concept of 'civil society' was introduced to Swedish politics in the 1990s as a critique of the relation between the labour movement and the Social Democratic Party (Amnå 2005). This same vein of debate, also problematized that civil society organisations in Sweden, as in the Nordic countries more generally, was comparatively weak in the production of social services. In 2009 the Swedish governmental policy on people's movement was replaced by a policy on civil society (Prop. 2009/10:55). This policy shift entails a growing emphasis on engaging civil society in the social service production and integration work through dialogues and agreements with relevant organisations. A first agreement with regard to social services was signed by the government, civil society organisations within the social field, and the Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions (Sveriges kommuner och landsting, SKL) in 2008⁵, and a second regarding integration work was signed by the government, civil society organisations in the integration field, and the Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions (Sveriges kommuner och landsting, SKL) in 2010⁶. This shift was of significance during and after the immigration of refugees and asylum seekers in 2015.

5. Överenskommelsen mellan regeringen, idéburna organisationer inom det sociala området och Sveriges Kommuner och Landsting (government decision id.nr. IJ2008/2110/UF).

6. Överenskommelsen mellan regeringen, idéburna organisationer inom integrationsområdet och Sveriges Kommuner och Landsting (government decision id.nr. IJ2010/2235/UF)

1.3 From 2010 Onwards

Following on the critique of the reception of refugees at the municipal level, the government reformed the system in 2010: The Establishment Program. Since then, the reception of refugees and their families is again the responsibility of a state agency, the Swedish Employment Service (Arbetsförmedlingen, former Arbetsmarknadsstyrelsen, AMS). The reception of asylum seekers has with some exceptions remained with the Swedish Migration Agency.

The number of asylum seekers arriving to Sweden has grown since 2012. As many other European countries, Sweden experienced the arrival of an unparalleled number of asylum seekers in 2015 when 162 877 people applied for asylum in Sweden.

Figure 4. Asylum seekers in Sweden, January 2010–December 2017
Source: Swedish Migration Agency (our translation).

Among the asylum seekers, the proportion of men in relation to women has slightly grown over this period of time. Most significantly, the number of unaccompanied minors have grown. In 2015 every second asylum seeking minor, arrived without a legal guardian.

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Total	29,648	43,887	54,259	81,301	162,877
Women	10,708	16,142	19,496	26,484	48,149
Men	18,940	27,745	34,763	54,817	114,728
Children	9,699	14,151	16,452	23,110	70,384
<i>of which unaccompanied minors</i>	<i>2,657</i>	<i>3,578</i>	<i>3,852</i>	<i>7,049</i>	<i>35,369</i>

Table 1. Asylum seekers in Sweden, 2011–2015
Source: Swedish Migration Agency, in Parusel 2016

In 2015 the largest group of asylum seekers came from Syria, followed by Afghanistan and Iraq. The increase of unaccompanied minors, is dominated by Afghanistan as country of origin. In 2015, 23 480 unaccompanied minors came from Afghanistan, 3 777 from Syria, and 2 058 from Somalia (Parusel 2016).

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2015 (%)
Syria	640	7,814	16,317	30,583	51,338	31.5%
Afghanistan	4,122	4,755	3,011	3,104	41,564	25.5%
Iraq	1,633	1,322	1,476	2,666	20,858	12.8%
Stateless	1,109	2,289	6,921	7,863	7,716	4.7%
Eritrea	1,647	2,356	4,844	11,499	7,233	4.4%
Somalia	3,981	5,644	3,901	4,831	5,465	3.3%
Iran	1,120	1,529	1,172	997	4,560	2.8%
Albania	263	1,490	1,156	1,699	2,615	1.6%
Kosovo	1,210	942	1,209	1,474	1,779	1.1%
Ethiopia	269	339	383	608	1,716	1.0%
Total	29.648	43.887	54.259	81.301	162.877	100%

Table 2. Main countries of origin among asylum seekers in Sweden, 2011–2015
Listed by order of share in 2015

Source: Swedish Migration Agency, in Parusel 2016

The comparatively high numbers of asylum seekers in the fall of 2015 caused massive pressure on the reception system for asylum seekers, for instance regarding registering and providing housing and material support. Arguing that society was facing a “collapse” in November 2015 the Social Democrat and Green coalition government presented measures intended to decrease the number of asylum seekers.⁷ These measures included the implementation of temporary identity controls at the border between Sweden and Denmark. This meant that you could not cross the border without a valid identity card and stands in stark contrast to the Nordic agreement of free mobility formalised in 1954 as well as to free mobility within the Schengen Area. In practice, the border was closed for asylum seekers, hence the drop of asylum seekers visible in the graph above. Later, in June 2016, new measures also included the introduction of temporary residence permits for refugees, except quota refugees. Several restrictions on family reunification was introduced in July 2016, including for persons with temporary residence permits and without means to economically support their family members. Additionally, in this context, the possibility of ‘changing track’, from asylum seeker to labour migrant that was made possible through the law on labour immigration introduced in 2008, implies a lowered threshold for asylum seekers in low-pay sectors such as service, domestic, and construction work, Politically this implies a big change in Sweden when the borders between labour immigration and refugee immigration becomes officially more blurred (Sager and Öberg 2017).

This political shift was very controversial for other reasons as well; permanent residence permits and family reunification had been central to the Swedish approach to refugee and migrant integration. It should be mentioned that while these measures are considered extreme and have caused aggressive debates in Sweden, they are not new. The government took on similar measures in the 1990s to diminish the number of asylum seekers from the Balkans.

The reformed system for reception of refugees, the Establishment Program (etableringsprogrammet), aimed at strengthening the emphasis on labour market integration. Persons between the age of 20 and 65 with a residence permit as a refugee, quota refugee or as a person in need of protection, and their family members, can be included in the program that lasts for 24 months. The Swedish Employment Service allot full time activities, for instance Swedish classes, and participants are eligible to an allowance.⁸

A political concern that has grown over time regards housing for asylum seekers and refugees. It is, in part, grounded in worries about the increasing socioeconomic and ethnic housing segregation, and it is linked with a long-standing critique of the Own Housing system for asylum seekers described above. But is also grounded in a concern about that many refugees remain in asylum seeker facility accommodations long after they have a residence permit. Some, but too few, municipalities have voluntary agreements about refugee reception with the Swedish Migration Agency. Hence, in March 2016 the government implemented a law on the allocation of refugees to municipalities.⁹ This law stipulates that municipalities must receive and find housing for allocated refugees, even though there is no voluntary agreement with the Swedish Migration Agency. It aims both at facilitating the integration of refugees and dispersing the burden of refugee reception among the municipalities.

7. "Regeringen föreslår åtgärder för att skapa andrum för svenskt flyktingmottande", see governmental webpage <http://www.regeringen.se/artiklar/2015/11/regeringen-foreslar-atgarder-for-att-skapa-andrum-for-svenskt-flyktingmottagande/>

8. For details, see: Lag 2010:197 om etableringsinsatser för vissa nyanlända invandrare.

9. Lag 2016:38 om mottagande av vissa nyanlända invandrare för bosättning, often referred to as the Settlement Act (Bosättningslagen).

Another major concern regards unaccompanied minors. This concern is on the one hand grounded in the special needs of this group since it regards children without legal guardian. On the other hand, there is a concern about large numbers of unaccompanied minors. In 2015, when Sweden received 35 000 unaccompanied minors, Germany received second largest numbers, 14 400 unaccompanied minors. The introduction of identification card controls on the border to Denmark in the fall of 2015, is probably the main reason why the numbers of unaccompanied minors have dropped. In order to safeguard the special protection needs in this group, asylum seeking unaccompanied minors is not the responsibility of the Swedish Migration Agency, but of the municipalities, often the Social Services Department or any other unit working with child protection, also after they have received a residence permit. All unaccompanied minors have the right to a legal guardian appointed by the municipality.

2 IMMIGRATION AND ASYLUM IN MALMÖ

Located in the south of Sweden, where the bridge since 2000 physically connects Sweden with the continent, Malmö is what we, at least by Nordic measurers, can call a gateway city. While it towards the end of the nineteenth century was a major port of emigrant departure, it is today a port of immigrant arrival. This was not least visible at the Malmö train station in the fall of 2015.

This is indeed noticeable among the people inhabiting the city. While the proportion of foreign born in Sweden on average reaches 18 per cent, in Malmö 34 per cent of the inhabitants are foreign born. In November 2017 the population in Malmö counted to 331 201 and it included 178 nationalities (Malmö stad 2017a). Out of the ten largest groups of foreign born in Malmö, are Iraq and Former Yugoslavia, together with neighbouring Denmark and Poland the biggest.

Figure 5. 10 largest groups of foreign born residing in Malmö, 2016
Source: City of Malmö (our translation)

It is also city with a population that over two last decades has been growing at a faster pace than at both the regional and national level (Region Skåne 2017). Looking at it from a longer historical perspective, the population grew from the late nineteenth century up until the oil crisis in the early 1970s when it started to decrease due to out-migration. Population has been growing again since 1984, and more significantly so since the 2000s. The graph below shows how net migration to Malmö among native and foreign born has shifted over time. While the population decline in the 1970s depended on out-migration of native born, the increase from the 2000s primarily depend on the immigration of foreign born to the city (Salonen 2012).

Figure 6. Net migration to Malmö from abroad and from other parts of Sweden, 1968–2011.
Source: Salonen 2012, p. 17 (our translation).

Even though Malmö has a gateway location, Stockholm and Gothenburg, the largest and second largest city in Sweden, have received larger absolute numbers of refugees. The graph below shows how the numbers of refugees are divided between the three major urban areas in relation to their population sizes. Obviously, when refugee reception is considered in relation to the population size of each city, Malmö has the largest reception of refugees, and has had so over time.

Figure 7. Number of persons in the refugee reception system, per 1 000 inhabitants in Stockholm, Göteborg and Malmö, 2005-2016
Source: City of Malmö (our translation).

When asylum seekers are residing in Own Housing (Eget boende, EBO), they will have their municipal placement (kommunplacering) in the municipality where they are already residing. Own Housing depend on the individual's ability to find accommodation and that in its turn relies on personal networks and know-how. The system is widely criticised for increasing housing segregation in urban areas. The graph below shows how the number of refugees from Own Housing varies in relation to the total number received in the municipal reception systems in the twenty largest municipalities in Sweden. The twenty biggest municipalities received in between three and eleven refugees per 1 000 inhabitants. Malmö received almost eight refugees per 1 000 inhabitants and almost five where already residing in Malmö at the time they received their residence permit. The following figure shows how the proportion of different categories of refugees received in Malmö has varied over time. Refugees from Own Housing has increased, as have the number of unaccompanied minors, in principal over the last few years. On February 1st, 2017, 2 794 persons waiting for a residence decision were in Own Housing in Malmö. Moreover, in 2017 Malmö was expected to receive 408 persons through the new Settlement Act (Bosättningslagen). This means that the City of Malmö is expected to provide these persons with housing (Malmö stad 2017a).

Moreover, being a city of arrival, Malmö has the responsibility of allocating the asylum seeking unaccompanied minors to other municipalities (kommunplacera). In 2015, when very high number of asylum seeking children without legal guardian arrived, almost 14 500 children were in transit and the responsibility of the City of Malmö (Malmö stad 2017b). 2015 is a great contrast to 2016, when 399 unaccompanied children arrived.

Figure 8. Reception of refugees per 1 000 inhabitants in Sweden's 20 biggest municipalities in 2016.
Source: City of Malmö (our translation).

Figure 9. Refugees received in Malmö, 2005–2016
Source: City of Malmö (our translation)

Native and foreign born are not living on equal terms and they are not equally dispersed in the city. Between 1990 and 2008 socioeconomic polarisation and ethnic segregation increased. Additionally, the neighbourhoods with poor and foreign born residents increased in relation to neighbourhoods with wealthy and native born as well as with mixed populations (Salonen 2012).

In addition, the population in Malmö is poor compared with the populations in Stockholm and Gothenburg. The table below shows that unemployment together with low levels of incomes are characteristic for Malmö. In Malmö the number of foreign born persons and persons with no access to unemployment allowance are higher than in the other cities as well as for the nation at large.

Figure 10. Share of population in Stockholm, Malmö, Gothenburg and Sweden.
Source: Socialstyrelsen, Öppna jämförelser ekonomiskt bistånd (our translation)

The city of Malmö is, in part due to its geographic location as an arrival and transit place of refugees and other migrants, a city facing challenges of inequalities and segregation. In 2016 the reception of refugees in Malmö was reviewed by the City Board of Auditors (Revisorskollegiet). The review identified a need to clarify aims and strategies for the reception of refugees and other migrants in a long-term perspective, as well as to facilitate collaboration between different bodies within the city. Additionally, the review pointed to the need to strengthen and evaluate actions for labour market integration, housing, education – specifically Swedish language education, the relation between health and employment and other dimensions of integration. To need to adjust the municipal reception of unaccompanied minors in relation to the state refunding is mentioned specifically, as well as the need of employing qualified teachers and produce study guides in the pupils' mother tongues (Malmö stad 2017, p. 29).

2.1 Integration, networks and Governance in Malmö

The first initiatives to manage the chaotic situation with exhausted, hungry and, sometimes, ill masses of people that arrived in Malmö as their first stop in Sweden, were civil society organisations and networks and civilians. When the City of Malmö and the Swedish Migration Agency responded to the situation, a tented reception centre was raised next to the Central Station offering, among other things, cooking facilities, a playground for the children, showers and toilets to the newly arrived asylum seekers. The early initiatives by civil society organisations and networks and civilians was perceived as outstanding; this is not how things are usually managed in the Swedish welfare state context where the responsibility is put on the state – not on private initiatives nor civil society. Hence, while civil society initiatives have been celebrated, also by the municipality and region, it is also significant that as the City of Malmö in a report mapping the refugee reception in Malmö, and make a list of important actors, civil society actors are not mentioned (Malmö stad 2017b). Yet, especially since the fall of 2015, several initiatives have been taken to increase the collaboration between public and civil society initiatives. There is however, no published report or review to rely on in order to describe this. Obviously, this will be an important contribution of the GLIMER project.

In wake of the fall of 2015, a regional agreement to support the integration of asylum seekers and refugees (Regional överenskommelse (RÖK) för att underlätta asylsökandes och nyanländas etablering) was concluded between, primarily, public agencies. The network for civil society organisation (Nätverket idéburen sektor) was included to represent civil society. The regional agreement relies on Partnership Skåne (Partnerskap Skåne) and is a way to formulate common goals in the reception and facilitate collaboration between various actors. These common goals are formulated in program declaration.¹⁰

Following on the government policy of a civil society, adopted in 2009 and briefly described above, followed initiatives of implementation on regional and local levels. In Malmö this work was initiated in 2014. On initiative of the Malmö umbrella organisation for civil society organisations (Malmö ideella paraplyorganisation, MIP), the city directory (kommunstyrelsen) decided to support an agreement between the city and civil society organisation within the social field. Next step in the process was taken in March 2016, when the city decided to finance the work leading up to an agreement. This work proceeded over the fall of 2016 and the spring of 2017, and in May 2017 an agreement was signed by the city mayor (kommunstyrelsens ordförande).¹¹ The agreement has the name 'The Malmö Spirit' (Malmöandan) and is an agreement of commitment between civil society organisations and the City of Malmö on what ethics collaborations in Malmö shall build on.¹² As the City of Malmö currently is reviewing its system for the reception of refugees, civil society organisations are consulted on the basis of the Malmö Spirit agreement.

Other examples of how the integration is managed in Malmö is the MILSA project,¹³ a support platform for migration and health. It is run by a network of stakeholders who in different ways encounter

10. Programdeklaration 2016–2019, <http://www.lansstyrelsen.se/skane/SiteCollectionDocuments/Sv/manniska-och-samhalle/integration/mottagning-och-etablering-av-nyanlanda/RÖK/programforklaring-rok-2016-2019.pdf>

11. 'Överenskommelsen Malmöandan – en processbeskrivning' (Agreement Malmö Spirit- a process description), link: http://docs.wixstatic.com/ugd/0b15cd_ec22b8e3b99546ee8a4a9fc2cbfd16a6.pdf

12. 'Överenskommelsen för samverkan mellan idéburen sektor i Malmö och Malmö stad. För ökad demokrati, delaktighet och jämlikhet i Malmö', http://docs.wixstatic.com/ugd/0b15cd_f2d5f2f84df84381a26fa72807de2c87.pdf

13. Link to project description, <http://www.lansstyrelsen.se/skane/Sv/manniska-och-samhalle/integration/partnerskap-skane/plattform-for-migration-och-halsa/Pages/plattform-for-migration-och-halsa.aspx>

issues related to health among refugees. MILSA also focuses on gender equality, and on mothers as important actors to improve the health of children, the education for better health and sports activities. There are also projects focused on language training and on extending the contact surface between refugees and established residents (I Malmö möts vi). In cooperation with the city there are many In cooperation with the city there are many projects targeting children and youth who are accompanied accommodated in family homes (e.g. Yalla jämställda barn), projects in cooperation the Children, the region and the city of Helsingborg to work out routines for the management of unaccompanied children that disappear, for example while waiting for an asylum decision (Inga Barn skall försvinna).

3. AN OVERVIEW OF THE WP TOPICS IN MALMÖ

WP3: Urban Regeneration, Accommodation and Exclusion

The backdrop to the socio-economic and ethnic segregation in Malmö is described as a series of events. Generally, socioeconomic and ethnic housing segregation emerged as a political problem in 1970s, as the Million Housing Program (Miljonprogrammet) was in the making. Malmö was hit severely by de-industrialization, from the late 1960s until the 1980s; the manufacturing industry, textile and clothing industry, the cement industry and the shipyard industry were either closed down or severely decreased. The population decreased due to out-migration of native born. It was at this time, that Malmö started to consider the inequalities in city. The native born population had an employment rate of 70 per cent, only slightly below the national average. The foreign born population was employed to an extent less than half of the native born, it reached only 34 per cent (Emilsson 2012). The economic crisis in the 1990s added on as unemployment rates increased. In addition, there were in-migration of foreign born, for instance refugees from former Yugoslavia. Hence, socioeconomic and ethnic housing segregation increased (Salonen 2012). Malmö started its transform from an industrial city to a 'knowledge-intensive economy' comparatively late. This has, in part, involved the branding of Malmö as knowledge based city moving away from images of a failed industrial city, and instead nurturing discourses of Malmö as the network city, the urban entrepreneurialism, flexibility, creativity, centre of the region, an enhanced focus on the region and also with important new markers in the infrastructure such as Malmö university, the new neighbourhood Västra hamnen (Western Harbour) which has replaced the former industrial shipping harbour with housing close to the water and the controversial skyscraper Turning Torso (Möllerström 2011; Emilsson 2012).

A motor in this regeneration process, was the former mayor, Ilmar Reepalu (mayor of Malmö 1995-2013). Reepalu, with a background as architect, was important to the new framing of the city as a centre for knowledge, internationally connected, urban creativity and entrepreneurialism etc. (Möllerström 2011, p. 74). On a national level, Reepalu loudly and widely critiqued the Own Housing (Eget boende, EBO) for asylum seekers, which meant that Malmö received many refugees in relation to its size and population.

The Commission for a Socially Sustainable Malmö (Kommissionen för ett socialt hållbart Malmö), often referred to as the Malmö Commission, was inspired by the WHO report 'Closing the gap in a generation' (CSDH 2008). The Malmö Commission appointed a number of panels with different focus areas, and which produced a number of reports on the situation in Malmö. ¹⁴The work of the commission has no particular focus on refugees and migrants, instead, relying on the concept of social sustainability, it emphasises a focus on the city as a whole. It problematizes socioeconomic and ethnic segregation, not only by looking at the poor neighbourhoods with many foreign born, but also the wealthy neighbourhoods with many native born. In fact, these neighbourhoods tend to be more segregated.

After the introduction of the Settlement Act (Bosättningslagen) in 2016 the pressure on the municipality has increased to arrange housing for newly arrived. In Malmö Stad a group was formed with representatives from different municipal bodies, "The creative group", the group is involved in

14. For information of the work of the commission, including links to all reports, see <http://malmo.se/Kommun--politik/Sa-arbetar-vi-med.../Socialt-hallbart-Malmo/Kommission-for-ett-socialt-hallbart-Malmo.html>

finding new solutions for organizing housing for newly arrived. In 2017 the municipality bought apartments in locations that was regarded to be “B” (parts of the center, Möllevången) and “C” (Rosengård) locations in the city and rented these apartments to newly arrived refugees.¹⁵ This was however met with political criticism and stopped in the same year. Other solutions are the mobile “module apartments” that are being placed in different areas in the city, such as parking lots. While organizing and providing housing for newly arrived is the responsibility of the municipality, there are however new local initiatives in regard to housing such as the example of cooperation between the civil society and the municipality is the NGO Refugees Welcome and Malmö to match newly arrived persons need for housing with accommodation let for rent by inhabitants of Malmö. A prior version of this project was initiated in 2015 through the municipal property owners (MKB) but encountered problematic issues as the offered housings not always met a proper standard.¹⁶ Perspectives on housing can however be related to broader issues such as residential well-being, safety, living standards, social integration etc. Locally civil society do play an important role in relation to such issues and perform a range of activities such as supporting homework for children and after school activities such as baking, theatre activities and arranging discos. There are also examples of how civil society engage in activities aimed towards newly arrived such as providing food as well as cultural activities, these activities do not necessarily take place in segregated housing areas but in central Malmö and provide important meeting spaces. Kontrapunkt is one such example of an NGO that very early became engaged in 2015 when refugees started to arrive to Malmö central, their activities, cooking and providing food and drinks for newly arrived as well as a “freeshop” that offer clothes for free. Other activities are aimed at asylum seekers such as legal advice but there are also culture events and course activities.

Making Malmö accessible as an inclusive space for newly arrived persons is also part of how the city work strategically through its cultural institutions such as the library that offer free wifi and has increased the numbers of computers. Another example is Malmö Konsthall that invites unaccompanied minors and newly arrived children to activities at the art museum.

15. <https://skl.se/integrationsocialomsorg/asylochflyktningmottagandeintegration/idebankforintegrationsarbetet/bostaderochbosattning/bostaderochbosattningnyanlandasetablering/denkreativgruppenochmalmostadskopavbostadsratter.11783.html>

16. <https://skl.se/integrationsocialomsorg/asylochflyktningmottagandeintegration/idebankforintegrationsarbetet/bostaderochbosattning/bostaderochbosattningnyanlandasetablering/malmostadisamarbetemedrefugeeswelcomesweden.11562.html>

WP4: Education and Developing Linguistic Competences

Swedish language education for immigrants became a political question in 1965 (Dahlström 2004). Then it was a trial project on the agenda of the Swedish National Labour Agency (AMS) and carried out by the Swedish National School Board. Education in the Swedish language was not organized due to a national model or part of any larger education project but organized in study circles and about 45 000 persons participated in the first years 1965-1966.

The language training course, Swedish for immigrants (svenska för invandrare, SFI) is since 1986 the responsibility of the municipalities (Dahlström 2004). All residents in Sweden who does not speak Swedish to the level of the training, has the right to participate in the teaching free of charge. Among refugees, the language training is typically among the first activates of the Establishment Program. While municipalities are obliged to offer the language training course, it is not necessarily the municipality who organises it. There are, in fact, many, also private businesses, who organise these courses. The language training is generally critiqued for long waiting lists, low quality and low results in the sense that comparatively many participants fail to pass the tests or otherwise complete the course. It was only in 2015, when the government introduced Swedish From Day One (Svenska från dag ett), that asylum seekers could access Swedish language training. Swedish From Day One is organised in the form of non-formal adult education and organized by Folk High Schools (folkhögskolor) and Adult Education Associations (studieförbund). Besides this, in Malmö there are several so called Language Café, run by the various actors. These are meeting points between newly arrived and others who wants to train their Swedish together with volunteers.

Children of school age, both during the asylum assessment and after, have the right to go to school. Since 2013 this right also includes children with an irregular status. The prior system for children received a lot of critique (Bunar 2017) since it put a focus on the linguistic competence with little access to other subjects. Among the consequences of this system were the lack of a coherent system made it unclear when children were to be transferred to regular classes, creating local and national inequalities in this matter, the newly arrived children became socially isolated from other children and did not receive necessary education in other subjects and there was confusion regarding if the regulations on bi-lingual assistance in the classroom were to be perceived as a right or not. In 2011 the Government introduced the Introduction Program at upper secondary level allowing for newly arrived students to study according to individual plans. The program allows for a focus towards reaching the goal of completion and more flexibility in relation to the individual student's needs in terms of level or format, the program might include taking courses also from the last year in the elementary school or becoming an apprentice in a company. Another reform was the amendment of the Educational Act in 2016 when four important components (Bunar 2017) was introduced: 1) the definition of who is a newly arrived child in relation to the educational system in Sweden, this can be a refugee, a child of a labour migrant, a child with Swedish parents born in another country etc., 2) Compulsory mapping of childrens' prior knowledge, 3) Preparatory classes where a student can spend a maximum of two years. 4.) Reallocating hours for newly arrived children in school, hours can be allocated to be used where they are needed but the total amount of hours per year is regulated as it is for all children in the Swedish educational system (Bunar 2017).

The organized reception of newly arrived pupils refers to all who have recently arrived to Sweden, independently of cause. In Malmö, the reception of newly arrived pupils starts with a mapping of prior knowledge and school experience. This mapping is centrally co-ordinated and provide a basis for a

decision on which grade the pupil will continue in. Newly arrived children aged 6–12 years are assigned to, and do the mapping, in a school close to their housing. Children aged 13–14 go to a specialised program to receive specific support before they are assigned to the relevant school. Children who are newly arrived and 15 years old go to a central preparation school (Dammfriskolan) as they prepare to begin secondary school (gymnasiet). Children and young adults in the ages of 16–19 go to Language Introduction (språkintröduktion). In Malmö that is a one-year programme, but pupils can continue their education within the programme at various levels during four years. The programme is intended to prepare for secondary school, adult learning programmes or a professional life. In a report from 2016 some problems with the Language Introduction was identified, for instance the organization of the Language Introduction and that the classes are overcrowded. While there has been a considerable increase of the number of pupils, the increase of schools offering the language introduction programme has been modest. Most schools offering the programme are public. The schools who run the programme have problems not only to manage the high number of pupils, but also to recruit teachers. Another issue is the results: among the students who entered the programme in 2011, only 9 per cent had graduated four years later (Skolverket 2016).

In June 2017 a new law, the Secondary School Law (Gymnasielagen) was introduced. This opens up for some asylum seeking pupils, accompanied and unaccompanied alike, to receive a temporary residence permit so that they can complete school.

Moreover, in 1970 the first mother tongue language training for children aged 7–15 was organized. This training was regarded a strategic and politically important part of a multicultural society. Native language education has undergone reforms and it is more selective on who has the right to enter this education and the financial support to arrange education have been cut (Dahlström 2004).

WP5: Integration into the Labour Market and Skills Training

In Sweden, asylum seekers have the right to work if they fulfil the requirements on identification, providing papers, passport, birth certificate etc. that are approved by the Swedish Migration Agency. All newly arrived refugees have the right work and the Swedish introduction program for refugees, the Establishment Program, is organised by the Swedish Employment Agency and the program entirely focussed on labour market integration. The municipality where the refugee resides is expected to organise housing, schooling and labour market integration on the local level. Activities within the Establishment Program can be labour related projects aiming at facilitating a faster integration into the labour market (e.g. Yrkes-SFI i Skåne, Etablera flera, Hela familjen 2.0). These projects sometimes involve language training, sometimes specific professional languages, and they can also be related to higher education. Other activities focus on the family and its members, connecting issues such as social integration, the children's education and the importance of parents' labour integration.

Since it was implemented in 2010, it has had a limited, but yet positive effect on labour market integration, in comparison to the previous introduction program. As a deficit, women and men are treated differently. Women are generally allocated fewer activities, to a larger extent 'empty' activities, and receive less attention from the case worker (Larsson 2015).

Asylum seekers have the right to work under certain conditions. One crucial factor is that the asylum-seeking person can provide identification papers (passport, birth certificate etc.) that are approved by the Swedish Migration Agency. This is however something many asylum seeking persons are unable to do, since many lack their papers. An employment, living up to certain specified criteria, opens up for the possibility to apply for a work permit, instead of asylum. This possibility, that is regulated by law, goes under name of changing track and is part of the demand driven labour immigration regime that was implemented in 2008, but very few asylum seekers have used this possibility (Bevelander et al. 2014). 'Fast tracks' (snabbspår) are provided for newly arrived refugees with certain higher education degrees, for instance social work, dentistry, nursing and teaching. The intention is to facilitate integration into specific professional areas. In Malmö, this is part of the regional agreement between the city, the Swedish Migration Agency, the region, representatives for the civil society and Malmö University (Regional överenskommelse, RÖK).

Generally, programs for introduction and labour market are organised by public bodies and contracted so called complementing actors (kompletterande aktörer). Civil society organisations, including immigrant organisations, play no or a marginal role in this. When civil society organisations participate, they do it under the same conditions as private businesses, often having their specific knowledge and competences overlooked (Hellström 2014).

In response to the municipal responsibility to support labour market integration, the city of Malmö has established a special unit, WorkMalmö (JobbMalmö), that is responsible for labour market integration. This unit works in collaboration with the Swedish Social Security Agency (Försäkringskassan), the Swedish Employment Agency and other agencies. The WorkMalmö is divided into different areas that chart and map prior education and professional experience, coaching, health activities, work training, language practice etc. Many of the programs include measures for refugees and other migrants, such as language training, PTSD-programs etc. WorkMalmö also organizes internships, both within the municipality and externally in private companies.

WP6: Gender Dynamics of Reception and Integration

The Swedish welfare state model relies on a dual-earner model. This family model was introduced in the 1970s by way of replacing family with individual taxation, the introduction of public childcare, and by embracing ideologies of gender equality and gender equality of opportunities. In a comparative study on care, work and welfare, Sweden was depicted as a country with a small family and a big state, meaning that the state takes on a comparatively large proportion of care work as both women and men are expected to enter the labour market (Daly and Rake 2003). Sweden has a pronounced policy on gender equality of opportunity aiming at women's and men's equal power to shape society and their lives¹⁷ and the government brand itself as 'the world's first feminist government'. It is also true that Sweden repeatedly has been top ranked in the Gender Equality Index (European Institute for Gender Equality 2017). The response to gender dynamics in Swedish reception and integration must be understood against this backdrop.

The government is concerned about the weak labour market integration among refugee and other migrant women. This concern is not solely based on an ideology of gender equality, but also the fact that many parts of the Swedish social security schemes, such as unemployment benefit, sickness benefit, parental benefit, temporary or long-term care child benefit, retirement pension, etc. are based on previous incomes. If you have no employment history, you will only receive a small basic benefit, often too small to live on. And, following on the individual taxation, most household needs two salaries to make ends meet.

Hence, in 2011 the government appointed a special government investigation to propose intervention for an increased labour market participation among newly arrived foreign born women and family member immigrants (Dir. 2011:88). An important aspect here, was the use and sharing of the parental leave insurance. The two reports that followed (SOU 2012:9; SOU 2012:69) show that refugee women and men are as eager to find an employment as a native born, but they seem to have higher thresholds to pass, including labour market discrimination. Immigrant mothers use more parental leave immigrant fathers, and the reports discuss to what extent the parental leave might be regarded a benefit or a trap (for women). The final report identifies women with no or very short schooling background as in particularly vulnerable. In addition, the activities the Swedish Labour Agency can refer Establishment Program participants to, are inadequate for this group. Hence they propose special courses on Folk High Schools (non-formal education schools) (SOU 2012:69), which were introduced in 2014. This is also a way to engage civil society in the reception of refugees.

Having outlined the Swedish welfare state normative approach to family life and labour market participation, it shall also be emphasised that Sweden, of course, in practice often is far from a country of gender equal opportunity. The asylum investigation has, for instance, in Sweden as elsewhere, been criticized for its gender blindness or reliance on male stereotypes when assessing for asylum applications. Not only has a male norm been used in the asylum process but also an adult norm. UNHCR declare that child and gender perspectives shall be developed and used when interpreting the 1951 Geneva convention in order to recognize relevant forms of persecution (Bexelius 2008; UNHCR Excom Conclusion 2007).

17. Mål för jämställdhet, regeringens hemsida, <http://www.regeringen.se/regeringens-politik/jamstalldhet/mal-for-jamstalldhet/>

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Governance and the Local Integration
of Migrants and Europe's Refugees

Work Package 2: Italy and Calabria

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1. APPROACHES TO ASYLUM AND INTEGRATION IN ITALY

1.1 From Constitutional Republic of 1948 to 1990

The right to asylum in Italy is enshrined in article 10.4 of the Constitution, granting protection to “the foreigner who is denied in his country the effective exercise of the democratic rights guaranteed by the Constitution”. Over the years, different laws regulating the asylum issue have been put in place, notably the so-called “Martelli Law” of 1990.¹ Until the beginning of the 1980s, Italy was considered by the international community almost exclusively as a transit route for refugees to other countries (Petrović, 2011: 35). Between 1980 and 1989, 11,831 asylum applications from non-European countries were made in Italy (Hein, 2010). We must remember that the Martelli Law only regulated some fundamental aspects of care given to displaced migrants. This act recognized a contribution of first assistance provided by the Prefectures² to all asylum seekers “without means of subsistence or hospitality in Italy”. The continuous waves of forced migration in the 1990s, especially from the Balkans, destabilized the asylum system envisioned by the Martelli Law.

1.2 From Emergencies of 1990 to 2002

The Martelli Law did not deal adequately with the subject of asylum in Italy and did not address the lack of a real reception system for forced/displaced migrants. To deal with the emergencies of the 1990s, the Italian government used numerous decrees to deal with the problems arising from the mass arrival of migrants.

The major emergencies of the 1990s were:

- From 1990 to 1991, Albanian and Somali crises
- From 1991 to 1997, the exodus from the former Yugoslavia and the second Albanian crisis
- From 1998 to 2000, Kosovo emergency

In 2001, starting from the experience of decentralized and networked reception activities, carried out between 1999 and 2000 by associations and NGOs, the Ministry of the Interior – Department of Immigration and Civil Liberties, the National Association of Italian Municipalities (ANCI) and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) signed an agreement for the establishment of the “National Asylum Programme” (PNA).

The Protection System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (SPRAR) was created by Law no. 189/2002 and is made up of the network of local institutions that implement reception projects for forced migrants by accessing, within the available resources, the National Fund for Asylum Policies and Services, managed by the Ministry of the Interior (and provided under the Government finance law).

1 One of the principal aims of this law was the regularization of immigrant workers, who were exploited as irregular workers. This law did not create an organic framework for the future, but rather an economic view of immigration, which remains a constant of Italian immigration legislation.

2. In Italy a Prefecture (Prefettura) is the representative of the Government in each province and is linked to the Ministry of the Interior.

1.3 North Africa Emergency of 2011 (ENA) and its Impact on the Accommodation Asylum System

In the period between 2002 and 2011, the increase in the SPRAR system was constant, even if contained in the numbers (1365 places in 2003, 4388 in 2008, 3979 in 2012). Alongside the SPRAR system, other government reception facilities have been set up, spread throughout the country. These are the reception centres for asylum seekers (CARA) established by Presidential Decree 303/2004 (later, regulated by Legislative Decree - LD 25/2008) to allow for the identification of the migrants and to provide accommodation during the procedure for the recognition of international protection. 2011 represents a crucial year in the history of Italian hospitality for migrants. As a result of the political upheaval in North Africa (Arab Spring), by means of the Prime Ministerial Decree of the 12 February 2011, Italy declared a State of Emergency aimed at responding to the extraordinary flows of migrants arriving by sea from Tunisia, Libya, Egypt, Yemen and Bahrain.

The Italian government reacted to such events by taking the important decision to grant humanitarian protection visas to all the citizens (around 11,000) who arrived in Italy between January and April 5th 2011. On April 6th 2011, the government passed the “Humanitarian emergency of citizens coming from North Africa” Decree – also known as the “North Africa Emergency plan” (ENA) – which appointed the National Civil Protection as the responsible mediator for the management of the reception of asylum seekers and migrants coming from North Africa.³ This agency was charged with the implementation of an extraordinary reception plan with the purpose of distributing migrants all over Italy, according to the lodging capacity of each region. In 2012 in these governmental centres there were 20,000 persons. On 17 September 2013, the Ministry of the Interior issued a decree that foresaw an increase in the accommodation capacity of the SPRAR system to reach up to 16,000 places in the period 2014-2016.

In order to promote accession to the SPRAR system by a larger number of local authorities, LD 142/2015 introduced the possibility of derogating from the limit established by law, under which State funding cannot exceed the quota of 80% of the total cost of each project. On 10 August 2016, the Ministry of the Interior issued a decree to facilitate the accession of municipalities to this funding making it possible at any time without deadlines.

On 11 October 2016, the Government issued a Decree to promote the expansion of the SPRAR system. The Ministry aims to encourage municipalities to host asylum seekers in their territory, inviting Prefectures not to open new extraordinary centres (e.g. CAS) or to gradually close the existing ones in those territories where the municipality already participates in SPRAR (the so called ‘safeguard clause’). In the last five years, funding for the SPRAR reception capacity has grown exponentially: from 3,979 places financed between 2012 and 2013 and then to 20,965 financed for 2014-2016, in addition to places planned for 2016-2017 (in 2016, 34,039 beneficiaries and 26,012 places).

Nevertheless, the growth of the SPRAR system is not sufficient to meet accommodation needs, and SPRAR places cover only 17.7% of the effective reception demand. In October 2016, the Ministry issued a Decree concerning a plan to improve the accommodation system in order to obtain a gradual and sustainable distribution of asylum seekers and refugees across the country (the regions of Calabria, Lazio, Sicily and Apulia amount to more than 55% of available places). This plan envisages

3.. Since 1982, the Civil Protection Department (Dipartimento della Protezione Civile) has had a guiding role, in agreement with regional and local governments, in projects and activities for the prevention, forecast and monitoring of risks, exceptional events and natural disasters.

the phasing out of the CAS [Centres of extraordinary reception], with a view to the consolidation of a uniform reception system obtained through an expansion of the SPRAR system. The so-called “Minniti-Orlando Decree” (LD 193/2016 and later L.225/2016) provided financial incentives for municipalities involved in the reception system, allocating 500 euros to each municipality for each asylum seeker hosted in its territory, not distinguishing between accommodation in SPRAR and CAS or governmental centres. However, such prospects will not easily convince municipalities to participate in SPRAR and, until SPRAR projects are sufficient in number, it will not be possible to close existing or refuse to open new temporary accommodations centres.

1.4 The Complexity of the Italian Accommodation Asylum System

The previous summary about the Italian context, shows there is not an organic legal framework for dealing with reception and integration governance, since the relevant provisions have been issued following the EU directives and are mainly collected in three decrees (LD 140/2005; LD 251/2007⁴; LD 142/2015⁵) in coordination with the main law concerning migration and the legal status of migrants (LD 286/98, “Consolidated Act on provisions concerning immigration regulations and the conditions of foreign nationals”).

In Italy, there is no uniform reception system. The LD 142/2015 amended Procedure Decree n. 25/2008 and repealed the previous Reception Decree 140/2005, without substantially modifying the previous reception system.

LD 142/2015 articulates the reception system in three phases:

1. First aid and assistance: operations that continue to take place in the centres set up in the principal places of disembarkation (Calabria, Sicily and Apulia) that is CPSA⁶, CARA⁷, CDA, Hotspots.⁸
2. First reception phase: to be implemented in existing collective centres or in centres to be established by specific Ministerial Decrees (so called regional or interregional HUB). In case of unavailability of places, refugees or asylum seekers are to be hosted in temporary structures (CAS).
3. Second reception phase: carried out within the structure of the SPRAR system.

In case of temporary unavailability of places in the first and second reception centres, LD 142/2015 provides for the use of emergency centres (CAS) identified and activated by the Prefectures, in cooperation with the Interior Ministry. The CAS activation is reserved for emergency cases of substantial arrivals but applies in practice to all situations in which the places in ordinary centres are not sufficient to meet the reception demand. The CAS are specifically designed not only for the first accommodation phase but also to provide second-phase reception for the time “strictly necessary” until the transfer of asylum seekers to a SPRAR structure.

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4. LD. no. 251/2007 “Implementation of Directive 2004/83/EC on minimum standards for the qualification and status of third country nationals or stateless persons and refugees or as persons who otherwise need international protection and the content of the protection granted”.

5. LD. no. 142/2015 “Implementation of Directive 2013/33/EU on standards for the reception of asylum applicants for the reception of asylum applicants and the Directive 2013/32/EU on common procedures for the recognition and revocation of the status of international protection”.

6. The CPSA (First aid and Reception Centres) created in 2006 for the purpose of first aid and identification before asylum seekers are transferred to other centres. They are reception services for temporary stays.

7. The CARA (Centres for accommodation of asylum seekers) are collective governmental centres. These structures provide for a first point of contact for undocumented migrants and asylum seekers. People are allowed to stay accordingly with the identification procedure or the decision of the international procedure. The purpose of CARA centres is to offer hospitality to asylum seekers when justified by needs of identification, medical tests to ascertain vulnerability, to take into account for a later and more focused placement.

8. The Hotspots approach is part of the European Commission’s European Agenda on Migration. It is generally described as providing “operational solutions for emergency situations”, through a single place to swiftly process asylum applications, enforce return decisions and prosecute smuggling operations through a platform of cooperating among the EASO, Frontex, Europol and Eurojust.

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The law does not specify any time limit for the stay of asylum seekers in these centres. It only states that applicants have to stay in these centres for the time necessary to carry out the necessary procedures (related to their identification) or for the time strictly necessary to be transferred to SPRAR structures. The facilities designed to accommodate asylum seekers in this phase are collective reception centres, until now characterised by large structures, isolation from urban centres and poor or otherwise difficult contacts with the outside world. In general, governmental centres (CARA, CPSA, CDA) are very often overcrowded. Accordingly, the quality of the accommodation service offered is not equivalent to the SPRAR centres or other reception facilities of smaller size.

1.5 The SPRAR System

As stated previously, the second reception phase is provided under the SPRAR system which was established in 2002 by Law no. 189/2002. SPRAR is a publicly funded network of local authorities and NGOs which accommodate asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection. It is the first national system for the reception of asylum seekers and refugees and was rolled out across Italy with the engagement of national and local institutions, according to a sharing of liability between the Ministry of the Interior and local authorities. Through this law of 2002, the Ministry of the Interior established the coordinating organization of the system – the Central Service (Servizio Centrale) which provides information, advice, monitoring and support to local bodies – and is managed by ANCI. The SPRAR system is comprised of local bodies that are granted access, within the threshold of available resources, to the National Fund for Asylum policies and services, in order to carry out projects for integrated reception. At a local level, municipalities, with the priceless support of actors in the third sector (associations and NGOs), ensure “integrated reception” activities that go far beyond the mere supply of accommodation and meals, including many different activities aimed at leading towards socio-economic inclusion.

The primary objective of the SPRAR, as we can read on the website, is: “to provide support for each individual in the reception system, through the implementation of an individual programme designed to enable that person to regain a sense of independence, and thus facilitate the effective involvement of life in Italy, in terms of employment and housing integration, access to local services, social interaction and scholastic integration for minors”.⁹ The main features of the SPRAR protection system are:

- The public nature of the resources made available and the authorities politically responsible for reception services, namely the Ministry of the Interior and Local authority institutions, according to the logic of multilevel governance;
- The synergy available locally with so-called “managing bodies”, actors in the third sector (voluntary sector organisations – associations, NGOs, cooperatives) that make a valuable contribution to the performance of the various activities;
- The voluntary nature of the commitment undertaken by local authorities in participating in the network of reception projects;
- The decentralisation of the “integrated reception” activities, throughout Italy (especially in Sicily, Calabria, Apulia, Lazio);
- The promotion and development of stable, solid and interactive local networks, involving all actors and selected stakeholders to ensure the success of the reception, protection and inclusion measures for forced migrants.
- The reinforcement (or implementation) of local services, designed to benefit the entire community, both indigenous residents and migrants.

9. ANCI & Others, Report on international protection in Italy 2015, available on <http://www.sprar.it/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/Rapp-Prot-Int-2015-Synthesis-EN.pdf>

Local institutions, in collaboration with the third sector, implement local reception projects, bringing together SPRAR's guidelines¹⁰ with the specificities of the different territories. Depending on the purpose, capacity and expertise of local stakeholders and taking into account the available resources, welfare tools and the social policy strategies adopted over the years, local institutions choose the type of reception services to be provided and the beneficiaries of their activities. Projects may be focused on individual adults and nuclear families (considered as ordinary categories), or on a range of specific categories such as single-parent families, single pregnant women, unaccompanied minors, victims of torture, individuals needing continuous care, those with psychiatric problems and people with physical and mental disabilities.¹¹

Any local project within the Protection System, under the provisions of integrated reception measures, and in addition to accommodation and meals, provides for social assistance activities to gain a better knowledge of the territory and access to local services (i.e. social and health assistance).

In addition, activities are organised to facilitate the learning of Italian, including adult education, access to schools for minors subject to compulsory education, further legal guidance activities on the procedures for the recognition of international protection, the duties and rights of the beneficiaries according to their legal status, cultural-linguistic mediation, orientation and access to local services in the area, professional requalification, orientation and facilitation to work integration, as well as orientation and integration into the housing market.

Generally, the SPRAR projects are small to medium sized projects. The coordinative body checks regularly to see if the projects comply with the minimum criteria as laid down in the SPRAR guidelines. The structures available to host asylum seekers and refugees, according to data for 2016, mainly consist of flats (83.3% of the total number of facilities), small reception centres (10.3%), and community homes (6.6%) which are mainly given to unaccompanied minors. Each SPRAR structure is run by different entities (NGOs, third sector bodies, Caritas) and as a consequence the quality of services differ from one project to another, even though the minimum standard should be guaranteed in all centres throughout Italy.

10. The manual providing the guidelines for intervention under the integrated reception scheme for immigrants. More information available at <http://www.SPRAR.it/tag/manuale-operativo>

11. In 2016, there were 508 projects for ordinary categories, 99 projects for unaccompanied minors and 45 projects for persons with psychiatric problems.

1.6 Differences Between First Reception Centres and the SPRAR System

In the first reception centres and in the CAS, reception conditions only have to satisfy a basic level. In the SPRAR projects, on the other hand, they have to develop so called “integrated accommodation”, centred on individual paths towards integration and aimed at providing the person hosted with all the tools necessary to regain individual autonomy. LD 142/2016 states that in the first reception centres and in the CAS the following must be respected: private life, gender and age specific concerns, physical and mental health, the family unit and the safety of vulnerable persons. Measures to prevent any form of discrimination, violence and to ensure the safety and security of applicants must be adopted. SPRAR projects go further by providing interpretation and linguistic-cultural mediation services, legal counselling, Italian language classes and access to schools for minors, health assistance, and socio-psychological support for vulnerable persons etc. Law no. 142/90 also states that asylum seekers are free to leave the reception centres during the daytime but have a duty to re-enter during the night time. Such curfews are not provided by law for the SPRAR structures and are applied by the bodies managing the project. Reception conditions vary considerably among different accommodation centres and also between the same type of centres. While the services provided are the same, the quality can differ depending on the management bodies running the centres.

LD 142/2015 stipulates that the governmental first reception centres are managed by public local entities, consortia of municipalities and other public or private bodies specialised in the assistance of asylum seekers through public tender. Moreover, the Ministry of Interior adopts a decree on the call for tender for the supply of services for the functioning of the first reception centres and of temporary accommodation structures (CAS), which is more than required of Centres for Identification and Expulsion (CIE now known as CPR) and the Centres of First Aid and Reception (CPSA) in order to ensure uniform reception levels throughout Italy. The perennial ‘migration emergency’ has necessitated a certain amount of improvisation by local actors and allowed the entry into the accommodation network of bodies that lack the necessary skills in dealing with displaced persons and are often only interested in making a profit. One only needs to read the reports published throughout 2016, by NGOs such as MEDU, NAGA, LUNARIA and LasciateCIEntrare together with LIBERA and CITTALIA. These reports show the enormous problems and deficiencies of many CAS including: unsuitable reception structures, lack of hygiene or safety conditions for both guests and workers; lack of training for those working there and staff shortages. The lack of places in the second phase reception centres casts doubt on the functioning of the entire integration mechanism, which is intended to follow the different phases. The CAS system has expanded to the point of being absorbed into the ordinary system, if not entailing a total reorganisation of the reception system.

2. CALABRIA, IMMIGRATION AND ASYLUM

Calabria is a region in the South of Italy with an immigration history that was dominated by outward migration that started in the latter part of 1800s. The so-called “migratory chains” (Reyneri 1979) oriented the fluxes towards the USA, Brazil, Argentina and Canada. In the reconstruction, post-war years and during the industrial era (1950s-60s) people emigrated from Calabria to northern European countries. These fluxes from southern Europe were the results of agreements between the origin and destination countries aimed at organizing the exchange of labour power for resources, which were to sustain industrial development in Italy. These same years were characterized by an intense internal migration from the southern to the northern Italian regions. The villages in the interior of Calabria were deeply transformed by the exodus of peasants and artisans who left their hometowns to be employed in Northern Italy, inside the “industrial triangle”, encompassing the cities of Turin, Milan and Genoa, which then represented the core zone of the country's development. There is abundant literature on the phenomenon of the rural exodus in Italy, strongly pushed by flawed policies of land distribution (with the agrarian reform) and welfare policies of income distribution (Perna 1994). The effects of this emigration were environmental decline and high levels of depopulation. This meant an internal shift of people in Calabria towards coastal areas and urban centres (both within and outside the region) that characterised the post-industrial years (the 1980s and 90s) leading to severe depopulation. The growth of foreign manpower taps into the margins of a broken local welfare system, in line with a model which is reproduced at a national level. Calabrian citizens face a condition of territorial inequality with regard to civic rights on the side of access to resources and to public services compared to some regions of Northern Italy (Fantozzi, 2012). In a welfare state based on the role of the family, which provides indirect support to incomes, migration becomes one pillar of the welfare state in Calabria. In particular, following a triple discrimination path related to ethnic group, social class and gender, since the 2000s there has been a wave of migration of women from Eastern Europe to Italian cities, small towns and villages, who move there to work with the elderly and disabled people, due to a lack of home care services (Andall, 2004). The theory of labour market segmentation is helpful to understand the phenomenon of migrant labour in Calabria. The arrival of migrants from Eastern Europe at the beginning of the 1990s in the agricultural plains of Calabria has created a subtle competition mechanism between them and those migrants from the Maghreb who had established themselves earlier there (De Bonis, 2005). These processes are amplified by increasingly stricter immigration laws such as the Law 94 of 2009, which criminalized irregular immigration.

Migrants coming from Romania, which joined the EU in 2007, had the right to move freely and were supposed to enjoy a stronger citizen status, but they have instead become newly exploited manpower subject to retaliation by their employers and caporali - bosses who with such migrants could avoid the risks related to hiring foreign (and therefore illegal) non -EU migrants (Colloca and Corrado, 2013).

Since the year 2000, there is a growing presence of irregular migrants in Calabria, from a variety of destinations, with a rising number of asylum seekers and individuals who fall under other forms of humanitarian protection (MSF, 2005). This is characterized by seasonal labour in the Calabrian agricultural sector. Medici Senza Frontiere (MSF, 2015) has documented, in the agricultural plains of Southern Italy, the unacceptable living conditions of many asylum seekers or migrants entitled to international protection, who are often not admitted to the reception centers due to lack of space. This includes people in transit toward other European countries and refugees that were not able to

to complete their social inclusion programmes. Asylum seekers represent the weakest component of the migrant population as they are exposed to a “bureaucratic labelling stereotyping” (Zetter, 1991), a process of institutional discrimination fostered by administrative procedures, political marketing strategies and media messages of fear. In such a political-institutional context, the refugee becomes a burden for the local welfare state. The case of Crotone, the town that hosts the “S. Anna” Reception Centre for asylum seekers, the biggest of its kind in Europe until 2001, clearly shows the social segregation between refugees and local residents. The charitable approach to the reception of asylum seekers only marginally focuses on mutual aid, legal assistance and training for work services (MSF 2006). Thus, refugees often find themselves in a condition of social and juridical subalternity which continues in their life out of the reception centre (Agier, 2002).

2.1 Integration, Governance and Networks in the Small Towns of Calabria

The number of refugees and regular immigrants in Calabria has jumped since the last census in 2011, where regular immigrants totalled 66,925, to reach 91,354 in 2015, with an increase of 35.5% (equivalent to 4.6% of the regional population). The migrant presence in the region, in tune with the national trend, has grown especially in the small towns, as an effect of the functioning of transnational migrations from the Maghreb (Morocco, Tunisia and Algeria) and Sub-Saharan Africa (mainly Senegal). Furthermore, the presence of women, accounting for slightly more than 50% of the migrant population (IDOS, 2017), constitutes what has been described as the “invisible” welfare of the region (Ambrosini, 2013). The different experiences of reception for refugees that are promoted to address local processes of exodus and depopulation contribute to the geographical distribution of the migrant population.

Among the Italian regions, Calabria is the first within the national integrated reception system in terms of the numbers of municipalities involved (104 of the 775 Italian municipalities that are members of the SPRAR). Calabria is also the second among the Southern Italian regions concerning the total number of migrants hosted, both for men and women (3,507) after Sicily and Lazio. Furthermore, it is worth noting that the number of migrants hosted within the SPRAR system is higher in the South than in the North and Centre of Italy (see figure 1). Calabria, is also the second region in Italy, after Sicily, in terms of the percentage of unaccompanied foreign minors out of the total number of refugees hosted [392 out of 3110] (SPRAR 2017).

Figure 1: Numbers in SPRAR system nationwide (Source: Report SPRAR-CITTALIA 2017)

Figure 2: Refugees in SPRAR in Calabria (Source: Report SPRAR-CITTALIA 2017)

In the Locride area, a rural zone inland from the Ionian coast, the reception of refugees has become an important resource for local development. In those municipalities, the migrant population is above 15%, such as in the small town of Riace, where migrants account for 16.8% of the total population (ISTAT data, 2015). In spite of the stabilization processes that have been undergoing in the last decade regarding migration, when reflecting on the integration of refugees in Calabria it is essential to consider the element of transience. The reasons for this can be found in the processes of “differential inclusion” (Mezzadra and Neilson, 2016) which affect the migrants who are not able to complete the

schemes of socio-economic integration in the short-midterm. The data found in the SPRAR report (SPRAR, 2017) show that in 2016 a total of 12,171 individuals have ended their time within the SPRAR reception system, of whom: 41.3% have completed their individual project of inclusion (socio-economic integration) and 29.5% have left the reception system before the end of their individual project. The beneficiaries of SPRAR projects in Calabria are negatively affected by the context, a region much weaker than others in the planning of paths of autonomy for immigrants who end their time within the projects, owing to an inadequate welfare system and job scarcity in the local labour market. Even the high standards reached by the current reception system are not enough. The local institutions (both the regional administration and the municipalities that host the refugees) and the social workers operating in the projects know that they have to deal with a wider strategy of local development, where the reception of immigrants can factor in as an added asset.

Looking at new forms of governance and network building among social actors, municipalities, provinces and the regional administration have gained more relevance in the planning of schemes for the integration of the beneficiaries - and the possibility for them to regain their autonomy. Such a process is visible in the actions and practices of reception born from the experiences of re-population of the territories. These have led to very innovative action plans and norms in comparison with the national context. The Regional law n.18/2009 includes the reception of immigrants into the measures of sustainable development in rural areas with a high rate of depopulation. Until now, this Regional law has not yet been fully implemented and the perception of the presence of refugees as an asset for the territories is deemed of secondary importance compared to the responsibility for welfare held by the municipalities, albeit within the existing support from the national protection system.

The key principles set in the Regional Law n.18/2009 have also been mentioned in the spending plans formulated in the POR (Operative Regional Plan) for Calabria FESR 2007/2013. This introduces a specific action aimed to attract new inhabitants into the marginal zones, including migrants, contained in the PISR (Integrated Plan of Rural Development) named as "Reversing depopulation in the internal areas". Still in the POR 2007/2013, issued by the Regional administration, there is a definition of the figure of the intercultural mediator, highlighting his/her importance in dealing with the migration phenomenon, in relation to the "critical issues concerning the reception, job placement, social inclusion and the opportunities of access to local welfare" for migrants and refugees. The POR Calabria for the 2014-2020 period also contains an ad hoc thematic objective (OT9) named "Social inclusion and action against poverty", which calls for project proposals and actions for the social inclusion of migrants and their families". Furthermore, the Memorandum of Understanding signed by 190 Calabrian municipalities in 2017 to become members of the national system of protection for asylum seekers and refugees (SPRAR), in order to adhere to the ANCI Plan for implementing the integrated reception scheme in Calabria, has seen the regional administration facilitating the setting up of a partnership among municipalities.

3. INTEGRATION IN CALABRIA

3.1 Initiatives of Urban Regeneration

In Italy's migratory policies, municipalities play the role of welfare institutions in charge of the social inclusion of migrants, with the specific task of planning measures and actions under the guidelines set by the regions (Caponio, 2004). The funding destined to the municipalities which join the SPRAR system is aimed at both planning "social scale" economies (services for refugees within a wider welfare context) and reinforcing services that benefit all citizens, both locals and migrants. Among the actions recommended by the SPRAR manual, a central role is given to Memorandums of Understanding among local institutions and agents, such as Local Health Agencies, schools, Work Inspectorates and local economic actors with the twin goals of building a space of social cohesion around the refugee and optimizing the use of local welfare resources. These processes of bottom up participation can be explained by a series of studies that focus on the concept of the "act of citizenship": those practices that facilitate the access and enjoyment of rights, through the negotiation of citizenship boundaries (Mezzadra, 2007; Albert et al. 2001; Walters, 2004; Ambrosini 2014). Such an approach, in Ambrosini's view, seems particularly poignant in relation to the governance model of migration in Italy where elements like recognition, legitimacy, access to rights and social benefits for migrants and refugees have been locally formulated first of all within the economic and social sphere, and only later formalized by state institutions (Ambrosini 2014; 2011).

Following this theoretical approach, we argue that the experiment of integrated reception schemes for immigrants in Calabria has contributed to shape so-called "bottom-up welfare" (Elia 2013) which results in actions of urban regeneration in different strategical sectors where citizenship rights for both new and old residents are at stake. For instance, in the municipalities of Riace, Badolato, Caulonia and Stignano, on the Ionian coast in the south of the region, the funding coming from the network Rete dei Comuni Solidali (The Network of Supportive Municipalities)¹³ has enabled the implementation of initiatives for the renovation and maintenance of the historic, environmental and artistic heritage of these areas, with the aims of sustaining the reception of refugees and promoting responsible tourism to create more job opportunities for all residents. In Lamezia Terme, a medium-large town in Calabria, through the "Security" funds of PON Calabria 2007-2013 destined for the implementation of the "Convergence" objective, an urban park was recovered and converted into a space for socialization and a hub for social projects for refugees and locals.

In what Giddens (1998) defines as "safe public space" (alleys, squares and parks) alternative forms of recognition of diaspora communities materialize. For instance, the SPRAR projects in Lamezia Terme, whose beneficiaries are young refugees and unaccompanied minors, run their activities in buildings confiscated from the mafia. In the municipalities of Riace and Caulonia cultural events such as the inauguration of a square, didactic and educational activities, and saints' festivals, help integrate the refugee families into the ordinary life of the localities, and contribute to undermine the control of the mafia over the area.

What these experiences have in common is a model of cooperation between municipalities and non-profit organizations with a solid experience in the social sector that facilitates job-placement. The Agora Kroton cooperative of Crotona, the Comunità Progetto Sud organization in Lamezia Terme, the Kasbah

13. More information available at <http://www.comunisolidali.org/>

association in Cosenza, La Casa di Abou centre for unaccompanied minors in Acri and the Città Futura cooperative in Riace, for instance, have all been able to establish job placement projects in the sectors of organic and responsible agriculture and of fair trade. An essential element common to such experiences is the attention paid to tutoring activities and to the empowerment of beneficiaries in the job placements, in order to enhance their abilities, skills and safeguard the right to work for refugees in a context where informal labour is dominant. The women refugees have often become co-producers of services by being hired as trainers, intercultural mediators and peer-tutors for the newcomers.

These aspects are particularly evident on the side of social scale-economies which have led to a series of socio-educational services for children and the youth. We can find examples in the small towns of Riace, Caulonia and Acquaformosa (a small arbëreshë village at the border of Pollino National park), where the funds from the SPRAR system are being used to support scholastic and extra-scholastic activities; sport and recreational activities, destined for both refugee and local children.

Although these practices reveal the existence of new forms of governance in the inclusion of refugees, they also demonstrate critical elements that could compromise the process of integration of refugees into the territory:

- the fragility of a regional network for integrated reception in relation to job training and work chains;
- a precarious system of social inclusion and job placement from the perspective of short-term integration;
- the weakness of local development strategies linked to welcoming refugees;
- the loss of expertise, local knowledge and connections in the migration crisis.

3.2 Education and Developing Linguistic Competences

Access for minors who are not Italian citizens is guaranteed in primary schools under the same conditions as Italian nationals, regardless of any time limit (Law no. 296/2006 and Ministerial Decree of 22/08/2007). Specifically, foreigners currently in the country, insofar as they are subject to obligatory education (Article 45 of the Decree of the President of the Republic No. 394 of 31 August 1999) are evaluated in the same form and manner envisaged for Italian citizens. Pupils with non-Italian citizenship refer to all those, even if they were born in Italy, who come from parents who do not hold citizenship. For the purposes of integration and inclusion, we can logically distinguish between: children who live in an environment where Italian is not the main language; pupils from other countries, without family protection (so-called unaccompanied minors); those that come from mixed couples; foreign and itinerant minorities, such as the Roma and Sinti ethnic groups, as well as children coming from international adoptions.¹⁴ In any case, with regard to the measures and procedures to be adopted, article 38 of the Consolidated Law on Immigration [Testo Unico Immigrazione] states that foreign minors present in Italy are subject to compulsory schooling and all the provisions in force concerning the right to education, access to educational services, participation in the life of the school community, which is independent from their legal situation within the territory of the State.¹⁵ The latter provision also applies in relation to the status of family members (Miazzi, Perin, 2009: 198).¹⁶ Therefore, the education of foreigners in Italy is not related to holding a residence permit or even to citizenship, as expressly provided by the Decree of the President of the Republic of 31 August 1999, no. 394. In particular, we can read in this legislative act that school enrolment can take place at any time of the year and that it is up to the Faculty Board to formulate proposals for the allocation of foreign pupils in classes, avoiding the establishment of sections where their presence is predominant. It is still the responsibility of the “College of teachers” to determine the necessary adaptations of the teaching programmes in relation to the levels of competence of the individual pupils.

Furthermore, to support the teachers' action, the Ministry of Education (MIUR) is entrusted with the task of laying down provisions for the implementation of national and local training and refresher courses on the issues of intercultural education. Further support actions for teaching staff involved in schools with a strong immigration presence are defined by Ministerial Circular no. 155 of October 26, 2001, implementing Articles 5 and 29 of the “National School Contract”. This includes additional funds to pay for teaching activities assigned to schools with a percentage of foreign and nomadic pupils exceeding 10% of the school's intake. The mechanism for allocating funds to schools can be reviewed and modified following this criterion.

Article 6 of the Consolidated Immigration Act details the general obligation to exhibit any type of document that can confirm the regular presence in the State at the offices of the public administration, for the purpose of issuing licenses, authorisations, registrations and other measures of interest to the foreigner, which explicitly excludes all documents related to inclusion and enrolment in compulsory education institutions (Cherchi, 2012). It is therefore the responsibility of the State (for the general criteria) and to the Regions and local entities in the forms of implementation (Article 3.5 of the Consolidated Act on Immigration), to take charge of the activation of all the complex mechanism of

14. Ministry of Education, Linee guida per l'accoglienza e l'integrazione degli alunni stranieri [“Guidelines for the reception and integration of foreign students”], Rome, 19 February 2014, pp. 4-6. Available at http://www.istruzione.it/allegati/2014/linee_guida_integrazione_alunni_stranieri.pdf

15. Legislative Decree No. 76 of 15 April 2005.

16. This is particularly important precisely in relation to the condition of the family member who, in an irregular residence situation, could put at risk the education of the minor he or she is in charge of.

measures that favour the insertion of the migrants, to keep school policies and educational support policies joined together within a single content (Violini, 2007: 18). However, even though current current legislation seems to pay particular attention to multi-cultural education as a form of integration (Luciano, Demartini, Ricucci, 2009: 113), the central attempt to identify an Italian model of integration clashes with a situation which is still very dynamic, not just in terms of migration flows, but also in terms of education policies, characterised by a phase of great transformation and the rationalisation of resources (Santero, 2001: 9).

According to the Ministry of Education, during the 2007/08 school year, the Ministry's registration system introduced for the first time the distinction between “foreign pupils born in Italy” and “foreign immigrant pupils” (who had spent one year in the Italian school system). In Italian schools, foreign students increased by +20.9% (from 673,592 to 814,187 units) between 2009/10 and 2014/15, compared to a decrease of -2.7% among Italians (from 8,283.493 to 8.058.397 units) and a decrease of -0.9% in the overall school population (from 8.957.085 to 8.872.584 pupils). Conversely, compared to the territorial distribution of registered students of immigrant origin, we note that the highest numbers of students are registered in Emilia-Romagna. However, in terms of the incidence of students with non-Italian citizenship within the total of registered students, the greatest numbers are to be found in Lombardy and Umbria, followed by Tuscany and Veneto.

Figure 3-4: Source- MIUR Statistical data

31% at the national level. However, the highest percentages of pre-schools with a foreign majority are recorded in some regions of the South: Calabria 85.7% and Sicily 63.6% (MIUR, 2017). From the beginning, Italy opted for full integration of immigrant pupils in the school system and for intercultural education as a transversal dimension that is common to all subjects and teachers. Integration begins with acquiring the ability to understand and communicate in Italian. As already mentioned, one of the main changes that have taken place in the last ten years is the increase in the participation of foreign students in upper secondary education. Linguistic difficulties are one of the key reasons for school failure: this strongly contributes to academic failure that, in Italy, reached 63% in 2014/15 and this phenomenon encourages early school leaving (Mochi, 2017). For this reason, ministerial guidelines emphasise the importance of this linguistic issue.

From the age of 16, foreign minors who have not yet completed their compulsory education, can be admitted to attending in Permanent Territorial Centres (CTP) [Centri Territoriali Permanenti] offering Italian courses, but also cultural activities, education and training for adults and elements of civic education and citizens' rights and duties. These training points allow users to support and develop integrated paths between school education, vocational training and evening courses at technical schools, where they can obtain degrees and language skills. Starting from the 2014/2015 school year, the Provincial Centres of Adult Education [Centri Provinciali di Istruzione per Adulti] (CPIA) have been added to the CTPs. The purpose of the CPIAs is social cohesion and the creation of development opportunities through collaboration with the Regions, the employment centres or other work agencies, accredited for vocational training.¹⁷

In Italy, about 70% of foreign students (according to the MIUR Statistical Office) choose technical and vocational education and training courses. Many sociologists have labelled this choice as "training segregation" or "school segregation", a phenomenon that is in focus but needs to be further explored. The guidelines also recommend that networks of schools, local authorities, regional education offices, training institutions and other stakeholders promote training initiatives for teachers and heads of schools. These plans should focus on acquiring organisational skills and on providing teaching methodology tools useful for overcoming the weak points of foreign pupils and for developing intercultural education.

In 2014, the MIUR established the National Observatory for the integration of foreign students and for Intercultural matters, with the aim of identifying solutions for an effective adaptation of school integration policies to the real needs of an increasingly multicultural society in constant transformation. The Observatory, which carries out consultation and monitoring tasks, promotes and suggests policies for the integration of foreign pupils, monitoring their implementation. It is chaired by the Minister and it includes representatives from research institutes, associations and bodies that play an important role in integrating foreign pupils and intercultural students, as well as experts from the academic, cultural and social worlds and heads of schools. In September 2014, the Observatory drafted the document "Diversi da chi? Recommendations for the integration of foreign pupils and for interculture", which provided recommendations and operational proposals derived from best practices in schools for a more effective organisation of reception and integration of pupils with non-Italian citizenship. The recommendations follow the Guidelines in emphasising the importance of learning Italian as an L2 language for the so-called "second generations" and recommend the establishment of permanent language workshops in schools taught by teachers specialised in teaching the Italian language who are able to coordinate the work of linguistic simplification of the contents of the different school subjects. This implies a systematic commitment to teacher training, but not only for teachers of Italian language, insofar as the responsibility for learning the language of instruction cannot be delegated exclusively to them.

17. In Italy, it was decided to maintain the same system of learning Italian as a language of communication, both for children and adults. People who cannot be enrolled in school programs are obliged to attend courses in CPIA, especially if they are included in the SPRAR system

3.3 Integration into the Labour Market and Skills Training

Italy appears as one of the most permissive countries in terms of access to the labour market for asylum seekers: the possibility of work is allowed after 60 days from the submission of the application (previously it was 6 months). However, participation in the labour market could entail loss of entitlement to reception facilities (LD 142/2015) in case of sufficient economic means. Even if refugees start working, their simple residence permit cannot be converted into a work residence permit. In addition, LD 142/2015 states that asylum applicants living in the SPRAR centres may attend vocational training when envisaged in programs adopted by the public local entities. The SPRAR has implemented standardized integration programs. Asylum seekers or beneficiaries of international protection accommodated in the SPRAR system are generally supported in their integration process, by means of individualised projects which include vocational training and internships. SPRAR is the only integrated system that provides this kind of service to the beneficiaries. Vocational training or other integration programs can be provided also by the means of National public funds (8xmille) or the Asylum,

Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF).¹⁸ In this case, the Ministry of Interior can finance specific projects run by NGOs at the national level concerning integration and social inclusion. The projects financed under AMIF are, however, very limited in terms of the period of activity and the number of beneficiaries. Municipalities can also finance vocational training courses, internships and specific employment bursaries [borse lavoro].

This fund is available both to Italians and foreigners, including asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection. The possibility to attend vocational training courses or internships is considerably limited in the case of those asylum seekers accommodated in governmental centres. Even though the law makes a generic reference to the right to access to employment without indicating any limitations, and in theory being entitled to enlist into Provincial Offices for Labour, in practice, asylum seekers face difficulties in obtaining a residence permit which allows them to work due to the delay in the registration of their asylum claims, on the basis of which the permit of stay will be consequently issued. These constraints to access the labour market can be related to the acceptance rate, in order to verify whether the level of permissiveness at the time of reception of the asylum application is associated with greater openness in the regulations governing access to the labour market. In this sense, Italy maintains a high level with regard to acceptance and for intermediate number of days to allow entry into the labour market.

18. The Otto per mille represents a part of tax contributions that can be designated to a religious organisation or to the Italian state which uses this money for social assistance schemes.

Figure 5: Source - Banca d'Italia - Calculations based on Eurostat data and report Aida

Refugee and asylum seeker integration into the Italian labour market, relative to native residents and immigrants who arrived for economic reasons, is measured by the ISTAT workforce survey (2009-2015). Regarding the percentage of foreigners active in the labor market, The share of males including refugees and asylum seekers is around 55%, compared to 46% for other immigrants and 48% for native residents. Moreover, compared to economic migrants, foreigners who entered through humanitarian protection are less educated and have a significantly higher mean age.

Figure 6: Source - Labour Force Survey, ISTAT. - Estimates made for the years 2009-15.

The refugee/native employment gap is inversely related to length of stay in the country, which confirms, after ten years from entry into Italy, that there is an approximate 2 percentage point penalty. For other immigrants, in the same period of time, the gap with respect to Italian residents is reduced and reversed, favouring the probability of employment of foreigners by about 3 percentage points.

With regard to public policies, 17 regional integrated plans were drawn up during 2015 which envisage the definition of preparatory actions for organizing, structuring and testing the system of integrated national services aimed at the immigrant population, with a view to facilitating access to services and enhancing public-private networks. During 2016, due to delays in the activation of project activities, many Regions sent an extension request, which was granted to all 17 signing Regions, postponing the deadline for the conclusion of the preliminary actions as of 30 June 2017 (Ministerial Note no. 35/002585 of 30/06/2016). The monitoring of the Integrated Plans was completed in December 2016, and the mid-term monitoring report was prepared. This activity made it possible to gather precise information on progress made, especially starting from the differences between the planned and actual actions and the critical elements that emerged in the monitored period, especially regarding the governance and resource planning (AMIF,¹⁹ other regional and national funds²⁰). Following the unanimous request of the Regions for an extension for the closure of the preliminary activities of the Integrated Regional Intervention Plans, in February 2017 the Ministry granted a deferment of the terms to 30 June 2018.

Compared to the general foreign population, from 2009 to 2016 the number of foreign workers progressively increased in Italy (from 1.8 million to 2.4 million) in line with the overall foreign presence (which increased from 3.4 to 5 million). The incidence on the total number of employees progressively increased, from 7.9% to 10.5%, with a consistently higher incidence than the demographic one, thanks to a greater presence of migrants with working age. With the exception of other European Union countries, Italy recorded an employment rate of immigrants (i.e. relative to persons aged between 15 and 64 years) higher than that of autochthonous people (59.5% against 57.0%). This is mainly due to the strong presence of the inactive Italian population, especially in the South and among women, but also to the greater propensity of the immigrant family members (e.g. those who arrived through family reunification) to enter the labour market, often to the detriment of educational and vocational courses.²¹

Calabria was the first Italian region to adopt a law that promotes the reception and integration of refugees in the country, combining it with the socio-economic development of the area. Other relevant legislative measures included the Regional Council Decision no. 93/2006 (on sensitive data) and Regional Council Decision no. 55/2012 (on language teaching) while other partially relevant documents include articles 10 and 12 of Law no. 32 of 1996 (residential construction) and article 3 of Law No. 23 of 2003 (social welfare services). With regard to the Integrated Plan of Interventions, the Region funded 5 preliminary actions and an indicative budget of 106,117 euros.

According to ISTAT data (annual average since 2013), in Calabria, the employment rate of the non-European foreign population (15-64 years of age) is 43.5%; a value of about 4 percentage points higher than the regional total (39%). The unemployment rate (15 years and over) of non-European foreigners is

19. Programma Nazionale Italiano Fondo Asilo Immigrazione ed Integrazione [Italian National Program for Asylum Immigration and Integration] 2014 -2020; Note No. 8875 of 9 October 2014

20. As part of the collaboration between the Ministry of Labour and the Regions, the following projects have been planned: Paths, INSIDE, Youth 2G, Migrants integration portal and other projects that can be consulted on <http://www.lavoro.gov.it/temi-e-priorita/immigrazione/focus-on/politiche-di-integrazione-sociale/Documents/Attivita-conclude.pdf>

21. Leone Moressa Foundation, Annual Report on the Economy of Immigration. Edition 2017, 171-177.

significantly lower than that of the overall regional rate (10.7% compared to 22.2%), lower also compared to EU foreigners (18.9%). Among the employed population, 56% have low educational qualifications: only primary school education (21.7%) and first level secondary school (41.2%); while, among employed EU citizens, second level of secondary school prevails (55.4%). There is a significant number of non-EU employed persons who do not have any qualifications (8.8%).

In general, the reality of immigrant labour reflects the historical fragility of the Calabrian economy, characterised by a high level of “tertiarisation of the productive system”, by low labour productivity and by high fragmentation and parcelling of the entrepreneurial background (Pugliese, 2013). In reality, there is a sort of adaptability of foreigners to the characteristics of the local labour market which conditions and directs immigrant work towards specific occupational niches (especially in the case of the tertiary sector and the agricultural sector), due to the other productive sectors being able to drive the economy. Unfortunately, these are two sectors at high risk of labour exploitation, favoured by situations of vulnerability, with an associated downward slipping of the classification and qualification levels.

3.4 Gender Dynamics of Reception and Integration

Applying theories and investigating the dynamics of gender, with respect to the migratory phenomenon, requires a lot of effort: we cannot simply refer to a migratory experience, but rather to a complex journey that changes gender relations (Tognetti Bordogna, 2014). The status and the attention offered by the reception system and the subsequent integration to the achievement of international protection is different according to the individual.

According to estimates by CITTALIA Foundation, in 2016, a total of 123,600 applications for international protection were presented: an increase of +47% compared to 83,970 in 2015. In the vast majority of cases, the applicants originate from the African continent (in over 7 cases out of 10) and are male (85%), although there has been a noticeable increase in applications submitted by women (rising from 11.5% in 2015 to 15% in 2016). Following the trend of the last few years, the most represented nation is Nigeria, both in adults and in unaccompanied foreign minors.

Figure 7: Source - UNHCR Statistical elaboration - 2016

Women's migration is a phenomenon that is in part different from that of their male counterparts, both in terms of the reasons that motivate leaving (often linked to violence at home or forced marriages) and in terms of autonomy in decision-making, and also for the risks to which women are exposed: from trafficking for prostitution to violence during the journey. Data from international organisations report a surge in trafficking victims.

Figure 8: Source - IOM - Study on migrants' profiles, drivers of migration and migratory trends

Italy has an efficient system to protect trafficking victims, both in terms of current legislation, as well as that of the interventions implemented by public and private social organisations that provide protection and assistance programmes aimed at foreign people who have been the victims of slavery, trafficking or other serious forms of exploitation (Olivito, 2015). The "anti-trafficking system" has come to life, launching the first assistance programmes in favour of foreign people who are victims of serious exploitation, even before the international provisions recalled above. Article 18 of Legislative Decree 286/1998 contains provisions that have been considered progressive and have constituted a model for other European systems. Even today, it is an important tool for the protection of foreign persons who are victims of trafficking or serious exploitation. The rule of the Consolidated Law, in combination with the provisions of art. 27 of the implementing regulation, adopted with Presidential Decree 394/99, provides for the issuance of a special residence permit in favour of foreign persons who have been victims of violence or serious exploitation and who are exposed to a real danger for their safety because of the statements made in criminal proceedings or because of the decision to escape a situation of exploitation.

According to the GRETA report,²² the Regional Commissions, responsible for examining asylum applications and recognizing international protection, have received instructions on how to identify victims of trafficking among applicants for international protection: the interviews must be conducted in a gender-sensitive method, with the interviewer and the interpreter of the same sex as the applicant, and the so-called trafficking indicators must be used, also collaborating with NGOs, or the IOM, as part of the interview process. This procedure, however, takes place with such haste, that the victims of trafficking are often not even aware of their condition; they may give 'wrong answers', indicating an economic motive for their migration which results in their eventual expulsion. For the SPRAR, applications for

22. Report on Italy under Rule 7 of the Rules of Procedure for evaluating the implementation of the Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings, <https://rm.coe.int/16806edf35>

for international protection relating to gender include acts of trafficking in human beings, sexual violence, domestic and family violence, forced family planning, female genital mutilation and discrimination by social background. In the first months of 2017, women obtained 24% of all applications for asylum protection, 7% of subsidiary protections, 29% of humanitarian protections of proceedings with positive results (Chamber of Deputies, 2017: 44).

The foreign population residing in Calabria as of 31 December 2016 amounted to 102,824 people, or 5.2% of the total population. Women represent 50.1% of foreign residents, in particular there is a significant female presence in the province of Cosenza (53.3%) and Vibo Valentia (52.8%). The case of refugees within the SPRAR network is more complicated to measure, since national reception projects register gender only for the purposes of residence permits or international protection. In any case, the data for 2016 is still valid, so that in Calabria there are 4.3 migrants received for every 1,000 citizens (ANCI, 2017). The in-depth study of gender dynamics can be important, with respect to the Calabrian context, to understand the role that women play in the process of urban regeneration and restocking of small reception areas. In some well-known examples (e.g. Riace), thanks to the presence of women, it was possible to activate a series of services within the community and rediscover professional skills no longer present in the existing population. Indeed, the inclusion of women can take place in the SPRAR second reception projects, through dedicated lines of intervention, such as:

- recovery of work experience
- language skill enhancements
- dedicated social welfare assistance
- specific treatment for vulnerable cases

However, the inclusion of migrant women in recent years has also affected regional institutions and NGOs in the area that proposed initiatives to empower women immigrants, acquire knowledge and develop the skills necessary to conduct a dignified life, in the areas of advice on legal problems, job opportunities, training inclusion, labour market guidance.²³ In the Calabrian context, some projects of social integration have also been promoted, specifically dedicated to the female population²⁴ or inter-regional plans, with the aim of improving the employment levels of immigrant women and stimulating the establishment of a dedicated local welfare system.²⁵

23. "Women's Help Desk" project http://www.serviziformazione.it/bandi/Progetto_Donna.pdf

24. AMBI Project, <http://www.esperienzeconilsud.it/progetto-ambi-accoglienza-mamme-e-bambini-immigrati/>

25. F.I.D.U.C.I.A. Project, <http://www.esperienzeconilsud.it/fiducia-famiglie-immigrate-donne-unite-nei-centri-per-linclusione-lavorativa-anolf/>

Appendix A: Abbreviations and Acronyms

ANCI - National Association of Italian Municipalities [Associazione Nazionale dei Comuni Italiani]
CARA - Reception Centre for Asylum Seekers [Centro di Accoglienza per Richiedenti Asilo]
CAS - Extraordinary Reception Centres [Centro di Accoglienza Straordinaria]
CDA - Reception Centre [Centro di accoglienza]
CIE - Centre for Identification and Expulsion [Centro di identificazione e espulsione]
CPIA - Provincial Centres for Adult Education [Centri Provinciali per l'Istruzione degli Adulti]
CPR - Permanence for Repatriation Centre [Centro di permanenza per il rimpatrio]
CPSA - Centre of first aid and reception [Centro di primo soccorso e accoglienza]
CTP - Permanent Territorial Centres [Centri Territoriali Permanenti]
ISTAT - National Institute of Statistics [Istituto nazionale di statistica]
MIUR - Ministry of Education, University and Research [Ministero dell'Istruzione, Università e Ricerca]
PISR - Integrated Strategic Regional Project [Progetto Integrato Strategico Regionale]
POR - Regional Operational Plan [Piano Operativo Regionale]
SPRAR – Protection System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees [Sistema di Protezione Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati]

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Work Package 2: The UK and Glasgow

Nasar Meer, Tim Peace and Emma Hill

1. APPROACHES TO ASYLUM AND INTEGRATION IN THE UK

Integration is a concept with a long history that goes to the heart of how we understand the kinds of social relations that characterise modern societies, from rural to urban, from kinship to community. This dynamic has been recast in thinking about the integration of new groups, voluntary and involuntary migrations, and the UK as well as most European countries presently occupied with coming to terms with how this renews and/or unsettles established social and political configurations. Here integration starts to become a debate that describes not only processes of change that occur among groups, but what a principled position on that change should resemble.

What are the public philosophies of integration policy and discourse in the UK? From the postwar period onwards, the way in which integration has been mobilised is closely related to dominant political attitudes towards immigration, race and nationhood, and its frame of reference has evolved in parallel with political and social change. If integration is an historically inconstant concept, then neither UK Government integration programmes nor their governance have necessarily shared the same concerns or motivations. Over time, UK approaches to 'integration' have taken divergent approaches to who is 'eligible' for integration (asylum seekers, refugees, economic migrants?), how those eligible might integrate (assimilation, multiculturalism or other alternatives¹) and how programmes of integration might be managed (by communities, through local government, by reserved or by devolved administrations). These approaches and their inconsistencies are contextualised and traced below.

Despite political and contextual differences, there are also some points of commonality in a 'UK-approach' to integration. UK Government policy has consistently relied upon the role of community and third sector organisations to provide support where policy provisions are limited. In the last two decades, this reliance has occurred alongside a turn towards deterrence, exclusion and border control. At the turn of the Millennium, influential legislation restricted asylum seekers' access to accommodation, employment, welfare and education, and placed them at the margins of state provision. As a result, in this period, third sector, grassroots and advocacy support networks have grown (Barclay et al., 2003). Glasgow is particularly well-known for its multi-agency networks and integration support (Darling 2016). Its networks have arisen in the additionally complex circumstances following the devolution of government in the UK in 1998 and from which a distinctly 'Scottish approach' to integration has emerged. Today, integration support in Glasgow involves coordination between community groups, third sector organisations, devolved, reserved and local government and privatised contractors. With so many stakeholders involved in the integration of displaced people, integration processes have the potential to be unwieldy and unsuccessful, yet Glasgow is seen to have responded well to these circumstances.

¹ See Meer and Modood, 2012

1.1 1945-late 1990

The UK claims a long history of accommodating displaced people (Hynes, 2011, Laachir, 2011, Hill, 2016). Prior to the twentieth century, the UK had historically offered groups of people with a shared ethnicity, religion or nationality safety from specific instances of persecution (Pirouet 2010). Whilst instances of this type of contained resettlement also continued in the twentieth century, in the latter half of the century, the patterns of, reception arrangements for and political responses to displaced people arriving in the UK increasingly changed (Griffiths et al., 2005). The change in matters relating to asylum and displaced people might be traced to several developments in the post-war period (Pirouette, 2010). Following the formation of the United Nations after the Second World War, the UK was party to the 1948 UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights (United Nations General Assembly, 1948), and three years later, a signatory to the 1951 UN Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees (UNHCR, 2010). Under these agreements, which enshrined the reception of refugees in a human rights framework, the UK was obliged to make specific provision for people who claimed refuge or asylum. In the years immediately following the agreements, provision for displaced people initially remained informal, but throughout the 1960s and 70s, entry and settlement procedures came under ever-increasing scrutiny (Boswell, 2017).²

The increased scrutiny of this period was a result of a growing hostile approach of the UK towards migration from Commonwealth countries (Meer and Modood, 2009, Hynes 2011, Griffiths et al., 2005). In 1948, the British Nationality Act had granted freedom of movement to all formerly or presently dependent, and now Commonwealth, territories by creating the status of 'Citizenship of the United Kingdom and Colonies' (CUKC) (Meer and Modood, 2009). Legislation throughout the 1960s and 70s significantly curtailed this status, and in the Immigration Act 1971 'ended major, permanent, primary migration from Africa, the Indian subcontinent and the African-Caribbean' (Hynes 2011, p.9).³

The British Nationality Act 1981 withdrew a right to settlement to most Commonwealth citizens. Griffiths et al observe that this has meant that the roots of the UK's approach to asylum are grounded in the 'framework of racialised immigration control' (Griffiths et al. 2005, p.6). As a result, they note, when attention has been given to matters of asylum, it has focused upon border and ethnic control rather than settlement or integration (Ibid). Where issues of integration have been considered, Ager and Strang note, they have, 'since the first Race Relations Act (1965), been primarily considered in the context of race relations', whilst emphases on 'social inclusion' have only more recently emerged (Ager and Strang, 2008, p.179).

In this period, and outwith their remit of ethnic and bordered control, government provisions for integration have been defined as at best 'laissez faire' (Zetter et al., 2005, p.171) and 'ad hoc' (Wren, 2007, p.392). In particular, the government relied upon 'Refugee Community Organisations' (RCOs) to provide practical and pastoral support to new arrivals, and saw RCOs as 'unofficially fulfilling [government] duties under the 1951 Geneva Convention' (Zetter et al., 2005, p.171). Other responsibilities for asylum seekers and refugees – such as housing and healthcare – were outsourced away from central government to local authorities (Schuster and Bloch, 2005, p.3). Meanwhile,

2. Boswell (2017) notes that in the early 1960s, the UK was unconcerned with the entry of asylum seekers and operated a policy that if people were able to evade the attention of the state for 24 hours, they could stay. There was increasing discontent with this approach from the mid-60s onwards.

3. Hynes also observes: 'the Act came into force on 1 January 1973, the same day the UK joined the Common Market, so migration within Europe was opened at precisely the same time legislation excluded those from outside Europe' (Hynes 2011, p.9)

successive governments strongly emphasised the role of the 'local community' on managing refugee integration, an emphasis which was also seen as a cost-saving opportunity (Wren, 2007, p.392).

Sales (2002) notes that such was the emphasis on 'local provision' for displaced people, that the boundaries between statutory and voluntary provision became increasingly indistinct (Bloch and Schuster, 2002).

Until the 1980s, the UK had historically received refugees in markedly lower numbers to other European countries (Griffiths et al., 2005). However, from the 1980s to the mid-2000s, the UK developed from a marginal recipient of refugees and asylum seekers to one of the main European recipients. Asylum applications increased from the late-1980s and (excluding dependents) peaked at 84,100 in 2002 (Binder, 2016):

Figure 1: Asylum application outcomes, 1987-2016. Source: (Binder, 2016)

The increase in asylum-seeking arrivals between the late 1980s and early 2000s marked a noticeable change in government approaches to border control and integration, which increasingly began to target asylum seekers and refugees with policies of 'institutionalised exclusion' (Carter and El Hassan, 2003, pp.10-11) and 'deterrence' (Hynes, 2011, p.12), including detention, destitution, dispersal and deportation.

1.2 Late 1990-2010

In 1997, a change of government led to a change in approach both towards 'integration' and towards asylum seekers and refugees in the UK. The Immigration and Asylum Act 1999 (UK Government, 1999) (IAA) was instrumental to this change. Keen to fulfil the tenants of the government's 1998 Firmer, Faster Fairer White Paper (UK Government, 1998a; see also Darling 2016a, p.488), the Act sought to actively manage the settlement of and provision for displaced populations through a contradictory combination of deterrence measures and enhanced support for 'integration' activities (Mulvey, 2015, p.359). The government began this process by separating the categories of 'asylum seeker' and 'refugee'. Under this categorisation, refugee populations were understood as a group in specific need of integration support (Spencer, 2011, p.216; Mulvey, 2015, p.357). The government introduced programmes such as the Strategic Upgrade of National Refugee Integration (SUNRISE) and the Refugee Integration and Employment Service (RIES) (Mulvey, 2015, p.359). In the meantime, the MacPherson Report (1999) and the Race Relations (Amendment) Act (2000) represented initial attempts to move away from approaches to community relations that were primarily concerned with bordered and ethnic control towards approaches in favour of social inclusion and institutional accountability. However, whilst these measures were designed to better support refugee integration, they also set limits on who was considered eligible to integrate. Under UK Immigration law, an asylum seeker is not considered a 'refugee' unless they have been granted status by the UNHCR, or they gained 'leave to remain' in the country. As a result, under New Labour policy, asylum seekers were not seen as eligible for integration support in the UK. This means that subsequent New Labour policies concerning asylum seekers could arguably not be framed in terms of 'integration'. However, the measures enacted upon asylum seekers have since impacted their subsequent experiences as refugees (Ager and Strang, 2008, p.179), and substantially shaped the broader immigration landscape in the UK. Furthermore, the starting-point of the integration 'process' remains disputed (APPGR, 2017), not least by the Scottish Government, which maintains that it begins from the point of arrival (Scottish Government 2017a) (more below). Measures enacted upon asylum seekers are therefore in need of consideration.

Outwith the provisions granted for refugees, the IAA placed enhanced restrictions on asylum seekers' access to education, accommodation and welfare. It established the National Asylum Support Service (NASS), which removed local government from service provision and placed responsibility for arrival, housing and welfare provision with central government (Schuster and Bloch, 2005, p.3). Under NASS, support provisions were restricted, and allowed asylum seekers access only to capped, cash-only support and access to no-choice accommodation in a NASS-designated location (Sim and Bowes, 2007). The introduction of no-choice accommodation for asylum seekers ran in parallel with policies that established dispersal as a key immigration policy. The New Labour government saw dispersal as a solution to the (then) increasing number of people seeking asylum in the UK, and framed the policy in the 'ideologically problematic' (Wren, 2007, p. 392), terms of 'burden sharing' (2002). A scheme was introduced to 'redistribute' newly-arrived asylum seekers away from south-east England to other parts of the UK. With a surplus of social housing,

Glasgow City Council was one of the first local authorities to volunteer to host the Dispersal Scheme and has since received the largest number of 'Dispersed' people of all councils in the UK (de Lima, 2012, p.100).

The constitutional settlement that is enshrined in the Scotland Act (1998) officially 'reserves' migration policy to the Westminster government. So Scotland cannot initiate macro migration policy. Given the distinctiveness of Scottish conditions, including population dynamics and civil society, there is nonetheless an acceptance that a multi-level logic will feature in the incorporation of migrants and refugees in Scotland. This is accompanied with the acceptance that societies have grown so complex, dynamic and differentiated that no single public policy approach commands hierarchical control (Sabel and Zeitlin, 2012). In our case, this also required an understanding that the governance of migration needs to grasp the role of networks that blur boundaries between state and civil society, and which rely on organisations and NGOs at various levels of consultation and partnership. Though the NASS system is administrated by the UK Government, accommodation provision has been outsourced to a combination of local authorities, private landlords and housing associations. Other support services (i.e. health and education) remain the responsibility of devolved and local government (Wren, 2004, p.393); however, Kelly suggests that the creation of NASS has reduced the capability of local authorities to prepare these services for dispersal (Blinder, 2016). In Scotland, devolved infrastructure and differences in English and Scots Law made integration provision even more complex (Cairney, 2006, p.431).

Figure 2: Devolved and reserved dynamics between the UK and Scottish Governments.
Source: Scottish Parliament (2018)

Since the 2000s, the infrastructural complexity of the Dispersal Scheme has run alongside UK Government policies more overtly orientated towards exclusion and deterrence. Throughout the 2000s, the IAA and other legislation⁴ were mobilised to restrict access to welfare provision and exclude asylum seekers from civic and social aspects of the state (Griffiths et al. 2003, p.3; see also Pirouet 2010, Bloch and Schuster 2000s, p. 395, Geddes 2003, Rosenberg, 2008, p.16). In 2002, legislation (UK Government, 2002a) was passed that restricted asylum applicants from working or undertaking vocational training until they gained leave to remain. Legislation in 2005 (UK Government, 2005) replaced Indefinite Leave to Remain (ILR) with a limited five year Refugee Leave, a decision which, Rosenberg comments, 'undermine[d] the Government's commitment to refugee integration by extending the uncertainty of immigration status' (Rosenberg, 2008, p.78).

Despite ostensible support for multiculturalism, integration approaches under the New Labour government were critiqued as closer to 'assimilationist' models (Back et al., 2002), which placed the burden on displaced people to adapt to dominant 'British values' (Home Office 2005) even as it increasingly restricted their access to the state, statutory support and participation in civic society.⁵ Alongside the diffuse and incomplete infrastructure of the new dispersal programme, and the complex needs of multiple stakeholders, local agencies and new arrivals alike were also faced therefore with the consequences of increasing erosion of welfare rights. In many cases, local communities and third sector organisations stepped in to fill the gaps in the Dispersal infrastructure, or to account for the more deliberate exclusions of government welfare policy (Barclay et al. 2003).

Over the following decade, many dispersal sites developed multi-agency networks that worked across government, the third sector and civil society to support the integration of asylum seeking and refugee populations.

The political situation altered again after the election of a Conservative/Liberal Democrat UK Government in 2010. Funding for government-led refugee integration programmes was withdrawn, and though the perceived 'failure' of minority groups to 'integrate' remained a favoured complaint of political and media elites (Mulvey, 2010, p.452), 'integration' has remained conspicuously absent from policy since 2010. The UK's current lack of integration strategy has been critiqued by the UNHCR and internal government inquiries (UNHCR, 2017b, APPGR 2017, p.12) In the absence of integration-specific approach, other policy and legislation have instead set a precedent for statutory provisions for refugees. Though asylum seekers do not qualify for many of the welfare provisions targeted by austerity measures, austerity has nonetheless negatively impacted many of the service-providers (such as local authorities, health and educational services, and NGOs) that support asylum seekers, which have been expected to 'do more with less' (Darling 2016a, p.487). Darling also suggests that the logic that informs austerity has also contributed to increased privatisation and a loss of public space (Darling, 2016b).

This approach has extended into the existing integration infrastructure over which the UK Government has power. In 2012, accommodation contracts, previously awarded to local authorities and NGOs, were transferred to private security companies, G4S and Serco, resulting in upheaval and eviction threats (Piacentini 2012) (more below). Recent outsourcing of advisory services previously provided by local stakeholders has been strongly critiqued for diluting local response capacities (APPGR, 2017, p.25, Burka et al., 2017).

4. Summaries of immigration and asylum legislation passed between 1999 and 2010 can be found in Piacentini (2012) and between 1905-2009 in Hynes (2011, p.11)

5. See for instance, Home Office (2005), which defines integration as 'a process that takes place when refugees are empowered to achieve their full potential as members of British society, to contribute to the community and to become fully able to exercise the rights and responsibilities shared with other residents'. See Solomos (2004) for discussion of discourses surrounding 'British Values'.

Meanwhile, the poorly structured ‘move on’ period continues to cause issues once asylum seekers have gained leave to remain and are obliged to leave NASS accommodation and register for poorly administrated welfare support within 28 days⁶ (APPGR, 2017). Alongside austerity measures, other government initiatives have impacted integration provision. The trend, started under New Labour (Mulvey, 2010, p.448), of linking migration with criminal activity (‘crimmigration’ (Stumpf, 2006)) – is now manifest in the contemporary government’s focus on securitisation. Though the Prevent Programme (UK Government, 2011) does not explicitly target asylum seeking and refugee groups, its failure to separate matters of community engagement and surveillance has created a particularly hostile atmosphere for many minority groups (O’Toole et al., 2013). The expansion of the existing ‘deport first, appeal later’ initiative in the Immigration Act 2016b to all migrant groups (including asylum seekers) has also added pressure to an already hostile environment (Yeo, 2016).

The asylum seeking and refugee context in the UK is now very different to that of the early 2000s. Since their peak in 2002, asylum applications to the UK have declined (see Figure 1 above). A slight increase between 2012 and 2016 preceded falling figures in 2017 (Refugee Council, 2017).

	Decisions	Refugee status	Humanitarian Protection	Discretionary Leave	Other Grants	Refusals
Iran	695	332	2	0	15	346
Iraq	417	45	8	0	26	338
Pakistan	410	55	0	2	1	352
Sudan	335	267	0	0	0	68
Eritrea	314	259	1	0	0	54
Afghanistan	302	100	4	2	44	152
Bangladesh	269	6	0	0	1	262
India	226	1	0	2	0	223
Syria	214	179	0	0	2	33
Nigeria	203	17	0	1	8	177

Table 1: Asylum decisions by nationality, Q2 2017, top ten countries for number of decisions. Source: Refugee Council (2017)

These declining figures are despite growing global numbers of displaced people (UNHCR, 2017a). In fact, within a European context, the UK’s share of asylum applications has remained fairly numerically consistent, despite a sizeable overall increase in applications to the EU 28 (see Figure 4 below).

6. A period which the APPGR has described as unrealistic in the context of the UK benefits system (APPGR 2017). This is likely to get worse as the Universal Credit programme is established.

Figure 3: Asylum claims in the UK and Europe, 2008-2016. Source: Blinder (2016)

People brought to the UK under refugee resettlement programmes are not included in these figures. In 2014, in response to the ongoing conflict in Syria, the UK set up the Syrian Vulnerable Person's Relocation Scheme (Home Office, 2015), which committed to resettling 'hundreds' of particularly vulnerable people over a period of three years (UK Government, 2014). Following public pressure after widely publicised images of the death of Alan Kurdi (Kingsley, 2016), in 2015 the government extended the Scheme and committed to settle 20,000 Syrian refugees over five years. In 2016, 4,369 Syrians were resettled through the Vulnerable Persons Resettlement Programme (Refugee Council, 2017), the large majority in Scottish local authorities (Addley and Pidd, 2017).⁷

In spite of the therefore significant contextual differences between the contemporary immigration environment and the environment in which the IAA came into force, current integration initiatives continue to be based upon those put in place by New Labour. Despite criticism of a 'two tier' approach to provision for asylum seekers and refugees (APPGR, 2017), the UK Government persists in separating provisions for integration by those who have leave to remain and those who do not. Meanwhile, although the government has placed increased emphasis on deterrence, exclusion and surveillance of asylum seekers, it has failed to address existing issues within integration infrastructure (such as the gaps caused in the 'move on' period). In many cases, existing integration infrastructure has been placed under additional pressure by government policy. The recent Casey Review recommends that the UK Government address its current approach to integration, and advocates for policy that foregrounds integration as a two-way process (Casey, 2016) but this has gained little political traction. The absence of an overt integration strategy in UK Government policy now also is in marked contrast with contemporary Scottish Government approaches, which, within a fairly narrow range of policy issues (Cairney, 2012), have 'diverged' (Mulvey, 2015, p.358) from those espoused by Westminster.

7. Syrian people have also arrived in the UK via the asylum application process – see Table 3 below.

2. SCOTLAND, IMMIGRATION AND ASYLUM

Following significant numbers of Scots leaving the country from the eighteenth century onwards, Scotland has historically been mythologised as a nation of emigration rather than immigration (Arshad 2008, Devine 2001). However, Scotland might also be considered as a nation of immigration that has historically seen both European and global arrivals (Equalities Opportunities Programme, 2012), as well as internal migration from the rest of the UK. Prior to the twenty-first century, it had some experience of accommodating asylum seeking and refugee groups, predominantly through resettlement programmes for groups of particular ethnicities (Piacentini, 2012). Nonetheless, at the turn of the Millennium, Scotland was less racially, ethnically and religiously diverse than its urban counterparts in other parts of the UK (GCPH, 2014). This started to change with the implementation of the Dispersal Scheme by the UK Government. At the beginning of the Scheme, Glasgow was the only recipient of displaced people in Scotland, and was the main recipient of all local authorities in the UK. From 2000 onwards, approximately 10 per cent of the UK's total asylum application numbers were dispersed to Glasgow, totalling an estimated 20,000 (Mulvey, 2015, p.363). As the only local authority participating in the Scheme, Glasgow saw the highest rates of demographic change in Scotland – a trend that has continued for the last decade. In part due to the populations brought by the Dispersal Scheme to Glasgow, the proportion of Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic groups in the city rose from 5% in 2001 to 12% in 2011 (an increase of 140%) (GCPH, 2014).

Figure 4: Total asylum seeking populations supported under Section 95 in Scotland, 2003-2016.
Source: Home Office (2017)

The implementation of the Dispersal Scheme in Glasgow occurred alongside movements to devolve powers of government to a Scottish parliament (see above). This meant the development of a distinct 'Scottish politics' occurred in parallel with management of and responses to the changes wrought in Glasgow by the Dispersal Scheme (Cairney, 2006). Early approaches to the Dispersal Scheme by the UK Government and the Scottish Executive (since 2012 known as the Scottish Government) were largely shaped by the new NASS infrastructure implemented by the IAA.

Administered by the Home Office under reserved powers, Dispersal in Glasgow was managed by the UK Government. This included the provision of accommodation, which was directly contracted to providers in Glasgow (Glasgow City Council and the YMCA) by NASS.

Local Authority	Total supported under Section 95	Syrian Resettlement Programme	Total
Glasgow	3311	34	3,345
Aberdeen	4	22	26
Aberdeenshire	0	19	19
North Ayrshire	0	14	14
South Lanarkshire	4	10	14
Inverclyde	0	12	12
Scottish Borders	0	10	10
Edinburgh	9	0	9
Argyll and Bute	0	8	8
Dundee	8	0	8
Renfrewshire	4	3	7
South Ayrshire	2	5	7
Stirling	1	6	7
East Renfrewshire	0	4	4
Perth and Kinross	3	0	3
Fife	1	1	2
East Ayrshire	1	0	1
Falkirk	1	0	1
West Lothian	1	0	1

Table 2: Total of asylum seekers and displaced people by Local Authority in Scotland 2016, Q.4.
Source: Refugee Council (2017)

Country of Nationality	Total supported under Section 95 in UK	Scotland
China	3,129	991
Iran	4,648	444
Iraq	3,761	317
Nigeria	2,932	270
Pakistan	4,478	264
Eritrea	1,880	133
Libya	1,055	108
Albania	2,331	61
Gambia, The	344	56
Kuwait	660	54
Syria	826	52
Afghanistan	2,467	46
Sudan	1,063	43
Sri Lanka	1,543	38
India	596	33

Table 3: Top 15 populations seeking asylum in Scotland (excluding Syrian Resettlement Programme), Q.4 2016. Source: Home Office (2017)

However, the arrangements made by NASS for the Dispersal Scheme in Glasgow soon proved problematic on a number of counts (Sim and Bowes, 2007, Darling, 2013, Schuster, 2000, 2004, 2005).

- First, NASS-contracted accommodation sites were under-prepared, under-resourced and poorly situated. Seen as an opportunity by housing contractors to fill unpopular accommodation in the city (Hynes 2011, p.77), Dispersal accommodation was largely located in geographically isolated areas that experienced existing multiple deprivations. Accommodation was often of a low quality, with few local amenities and limited links to other parts of Glasgow. Meanwhile, early government proposals to accommodate arrivals on the basis of 'language clustering' (Piacentini, 2012, p.130) did not materialise and people were accommodated on an ad hoc basis. Newly-arrived Dispersed populations therefore faced challenging housing conditions in locations that prevented them either from accessing local support or developing support systems of their own.
- Second, these conditions were made worse by developing social conditions in the sites. Inadequate community engagement by local authorities and government meant that existing residents in Dispersal sites saw newcomers as 'competition' for sparsely distributed resources (Kelly, 2002, Walsh et al., 2016). Following sensationalist reporting from local media, which portrayed asylum seekers and refugees as 'benefit cheats' and 'freeloaders' (Coole, 2002), Dispersed populations

were targeted for racist abuse and violence even as initial (devolved) government responses insisted that Scotland 'did not have a racism problem' (Arshad, 2003, p.138).

- Third, local support systems were neither adequately prepared nor resourced for the scale and type of provision needed for the Scheme. Early limitations on interpreting and social and legal services meant that new arrivals were left isolated in a strange city, in complex and confusing NASS infrastructure (Piacentini, 2012). A series of incidents in the early 2000s prompted the Scottish administration to revise its initially 'complacent' (Arshad, 2003, p.138) approach to dispersed populations. In 2001 the murder of Firsat Dag, a Kurdish man seeking asylum, prompted community-led and national outcry (Piacentini, 2012, p.123) and prompted a series of anti-racism campaigns led by the Scottish Executive (Rosenberg, 2008, Wren, 2004, Arshad, 2003). Between 2005-6, the issue of child detention, raised by the Glasgow Girls campaign (Hill and Nic Craith, 2016), drew a largely sympathetic response from the Scottish public and prompted the Scottish Executive to challenge the UK Government on its detention policy.

In the context of these incidents, and within its devolved remit, the Scottish Executive began to develop a distinct Scotland-orientated approach to refugees, asylum seekers and integration that responded to the particular demographic, social and economic conditions in Scotland. This work began within a race relations framework. In 2002, the Scottish Executive launched its One Scotland: Many Cultures initiative, which sought to foreground anti-racist work in public institutions, (Piacentini, 2012, p.126). At the same time, the Race Relations Act (Scotland) Order (UK Government 2002b) legislated for these concerns, prompting the Scottish Executive to develop its Race Equality Scheme (Scottish Executive, 2006), which, in some contrast to the more assimilationist policy of the New Labour UK Government (see above), stated a commitment to supporting a dynamic of mutual participation and engagement between majority and minority populations in Scotland (Scottish Executive, 2006; Section 5.3.5). The 2007 election of a minority Scottish National Party Government prefigured further divergence from UK Government policy on refugees, asylum seekers and integration.

Figure 5: leadership of local, devolved and reserved administrations, 1999-present

By 2008, the (now) Scottish Government's Race Equality Statement 2008-11 (Scottish Government, 2008) presented an integration infrastructure; however, whilst the Statement advocated for a 'two-way' process (Kirkwood et al., 2015, p.144), its language returned the burden of integration primarily to refugee groups (Hill, 2017). More recent policy has attempted to address some of the problems of the 2008 Statement. The 2014 relaunch of the One Scotland (Scottish Government, 2017b) campaign presented a vision of a community-orientated multicultural society that sought to advance civic frameworks of belonging. In 2014, the Scottish Government also launched the three-year New Scots 2014 – 2017 initiative, which based on the Ager and Strang model of rights-based integration (Ager and Strang, 2008), made recommendations progressive, mutual 'integration' strategies for asylum seekers and refugees (Scottish Government, 2017a).

Figure 6: 'Indicators of Integration'. Source: Ager and Strang (2004)

The 2014 New Scots initiative restated the Scottish Government's commitment to defining integration as 'from day one' of arrival in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2017a), a definition which, in contrast to prevailing UK Government policy, includes asylum seekers in any Scottish Government-supported integration provisions. The recently-launched second iteration of the New Scots initiative takes this commitment further, defining integration 'as a long-term, two-way process, involving positive change in both individuals and host communities, which leads to cohesive, diverse communities' (Scottish Government, 2018). The 2018 Strategy places responsibility for integration on both displaced and settled populations in Scotland, and commits to further support of existing multi-agency networks. In Scotland, 'integration' is therefore currently seen as a long-term programme that encompasses a person's progression from asylum seeker to refugee and beyond, with an end goal of (at the least) civic citizenship. These policies might be seen in the context of SNP politics, which have been ostensibly supportive of Scottish citizenship built on civic rather than ethnic belonging (Hussain and Miller, 2006, Meer, 2015). They might also be seen as a policy response to the threat of population decline in Scotland, which has so far been forestalled by increased immigration since the 2000s. As a result, and whilst asylum seekers in Scotland remain subject to reserved legislation that restricts their access to employment and welfare, there are a number of devolved areas in which they are able to access Scotland-specific integration provisions (see below).

In contemporary Glasgow, processes of integration consequently remain fairly complex. Asylum seekers continue to be subject to NASS infrastructure under the UK Government's reserved powers. As the UK Government increasingly turns to private contractors to fulfil its reserved duties, asylum seekers are also increasingly coming into contact with privatised systems (see below).

However, asylum seekers also fall under the devolved responsibilities of the Scottish Government, many of which are administrated and provided by local authorities and some by NGOs. Meanwhile, in the absence of an overt integration strategy from the UK Government, the integration programmes to which asylum seekers and refugees have access in Scotland are conceived by the Scottish Government and administrated by a number of third sector agencies in Glasgow.

2.1 Integration, Networks and Governance in Glasgow

Of the cities which have participated in the Dispersal Scheme, Glasgow is frequently cited as having made most progress in developing an environment of welcome and support (Piacentini, 2012).

Glasgow's success in establishing a comprehensive support network for asylum seekers and refugees has been largely enabled by the multi-agency network that has developed since the early 2000s. Rooted in responses to the disarray associated with the early years of the Dispersal Scheme, support and integration initiatives in Glasgow have developed both in partnership with and independently of devolved and reserved government.

Early instances of community mobilisation, such as the Glasgow Girls campaign, have also been complimented by the support of grassroots organisations, RCOs, Scottish NGOs, UK-wide NGOs, local authorities and Scottish Government policy (see Figure 8 below). Within Glasgow, the Scottish Government has established Integration Networks to aid and coordinate integration activities within specific areas of the city (including: Maryhill Integration Network, Govan and Craigton IN and so on).

It has also established an infrastructure of representation and advocacy, with named partners including: the Scottish Refugee Council, Saheliya, AMINA, CRER and BEMIS (Scottish Government, 2008). The coordination of these many different stakeholders alongside multilevel government requires constant maintenance; however, long-term, local work across agencies and stakeholders has facilitated co-operation and collaboration on an unprecedented scale (Darling, 2016a). Baberhoen and Muench suggest that one of the strengths of Glasgow's multi-agency network is its emphasis on the local, which has enabled it to cultivate the (impression of) a 'caring' discourse of a local belonging which it has set against a discourse of a centralised, uncaring UK bureaucracy (Baberhoen and Muench, 2016).

Figure 7: Selected integration stakeholders in Glasgow

Multi-agency networking in Glasgow has enabled stakeholders in Scotland to respond to some of the issues experienced by asylum seekers and refugees that remain unaddressed by the UK Government. For instance, the Holistic Integration Service (HIS) is a partnership between Scottish Refugee Council, British Red Cross, Bridges Programmes, Glasgow Clyde College and Workers Educational Association Scotland (Strang et al., 2015, p.13) that seeks to provide support in the 'move on' period (see above). HIS offers up to twelve-months support for people who have recently gained refugee status (Strang et al., 2015) and seeks to help them avoid common problems encountered in this period, such as accommodation issues, problems accessing welfare support and issues gaining employment. Other programmes mobilise multi-agency resources to provide education and advocacy services for asylum seekers (see Table 4 for a breakdown of services and stakeholders).

Initiative	Purpose?	Sponsor	Partners	Affiliation
Holistic Integration Service	To streamline the 'move on' period by improving communication between refugee services and the DWP, to support refugees to find employment	Scottish Refugee Council with BIG Lottery Scotland funding	Scottish Refugee Council (coordinator, advice and advocacy)	SG Integration partner Legal advice = devolved Employment advice = devolved
			British Red Cross	National (UK) organisation Health = devolved
			ESOL	Nationally funded ESOL = devolved ESOL implementation = voluntary/3 rd sector
			Bridges Programme	Employability support = devolved and reserved
			Glasgow Clyde College and Worker's Educational Association	Local (Glasgow) Education = devolved
DWP Resettlement Work	To give quick access to employment and social security to Syrian refugees arriving under the resettlement programme. Information sharing between DWP and HO	DWP (national government)	DWP (coordinator)	National (UK)
			Home Office	National (UK)
			Scottish Refugee Council	3 rd Sector, devolved
Refugee Peer Education for Health and Wellbeing	A programme that supports asylum seekers to run health and wellbeing courses for new asylum seekers	Scottish Refugee Council	Scottish Refugee Council (coordinator)	3 rd Sector, devolved
			NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde	Devolved
			North East Sector Improvement Team	Devolved
Asylum support and advice	An initiative to provide information to asylum seekers on their rights and entitlements in Scotland. To advise and support Home Office contractors (Orchard and Shipman, Migrant Help)	New Scots Asylum Dispersal Thematic group (SG)	New College Lanarkshire	Education, devolved
			Police Scotland	Devolved
			Crown Office Procurator Fiscal	Devolved
			Legal Services Agency	3 rd Sector, devolved/reserved
Asylum Journey Mapping	To map the legal and support journey for someone seeking asylum in Scotland	New Scots Asylum Dispersal Thematic group (SG)	Scottish Refugee Council	3 rd Sector, devolved
			Migrant Help	External contractor (Home Office funded, National level)
			Community agencies and organisations	Local (Glasgow), 3 rd Sector

Table 4: A selection of integration initiatives and networks of governance.

Source: Scottish Government (2017a)

Integration support networks in Glasgow are now therefore well-established and comprehensive. However, some gaps in provision remain, including:

- The extent to which grassroots and community groups are included in national level programmes of integration (see Netto, 2008)
- The loss of expertise, local knowledge and connections caused by a turn towards privatisation (Darling 2016a, 2016b, 2013, Rosenberg 2008, pp.90-1)
- The duplication of work and initiatives caused by similarities in organisations' remits.

This in turn may cause existing integration initiatives to become ineffective. Rosenberg quotes a stakeholder in Glasgow Community planning: 'there is an industry here where people can go from project to project to project and never really get integrated, just stay in that kind of unique sector and not feel part of the mainstream' (Rosenberg, 2008, p.88).

3 INTEGRATION IN GLASGOW

3.1 Regeneration, Accommodation and Urban Exclusion

Following the Immigration and Asylum Act 1999, under the Dispersal Scheme, Glasgow City Council agreed a contract with the Home Office to accommodate up to 2000 asylum seekers a year (McAllister, 2015, p.244). Asylum seekers were subsequently housed in areas in Glasgow North West, Glasgow South and Glasgow North East, predominately in housing schemes and high rises situated in areas of multiple deprivations (Barclay et al., 2003). The effects of Glasgow's Dispersal accommodation upon asylum seekers have been widely documented, and has highlighted how Dispersal sites created and exacerbated spatial, social and cultural isolation for many new arrivals. Dispersal sites were frequently located in difficult to access areas of the city, which were far away from support networks, faith centres or amenities. In addition, the quality of Dispersal accommodation has repeatedly been called into question. In a study using its Joint Client Database, the Scottish Refugee Council (Glen and Lindsay, 2014) highlighted specific issues encountered by asylum-seekers, including:

- Anti-social behaviour and harassment (which related to hostility faced by clients either from housemates or within their neighbourhood).
- Standards within the accommodation: including the physical quality of the accommodation and suitability of the type of accommodation.
- Hostility and anti-social behaviour from accommodation provider employees
- The recently published 2018 New Scots Strategy notes that within these issues, LGBTQ asylum seekers faced disproportionate discrimination (Scottish Government, 2018).

The The governance of Dispersal accommodation is complex. Until 2012, the Home Office (UK Government) contracted directly with Glasgow City Council (local Scottish government) to provide accommodation to asylum applicants, accommodation which was jointly managed by GCC and two third sector organisations. In 2012, the Home Office ended the accommodation contracts with local authorities and introduced a new delivery model for the provision of accommodation and related transport services to asylum applicants: the Commercial and Operational Managers Procuring Asylum Support Services (COMPASS). Contracts for the provision of asylum seeker accommodation were thus transferred from a mixture of consortia of local authorities, social housing associations and private providers to management by private contractors. Until 2017, the private company, Serco, had contractual responsibility for the Scotland and Northern Ireland region within COMPASS, which it subcontracted to a company called Orchard and Shipman. Following allegations against Orchard and Shipman in the press in 2017, this contract is currently out to tender, and the Scottish Government has expressed an interest in submitting a bid.

Whilst the governance of Dispersal accommodation is subject to UK Government decisions, it also falls under the Scottish Government's legislative competence over the standards of social, housing association, and private rented housing in Scotland, which it has clarified in the Scottish Social Housing Charter. To date, jurisdiction over Dispersal accommodation remains contentious, and the current Scottish Government has expressed frustration over the dynamic (Paterson, 2016). The areas of multiple deprivations in which Dispersal accommodation is located are also situated within a broader precedent of social marginalisation and displacement in Glasgow. Many of the Dispersal sites and their housing stock were the result of successive Glasgow City Council housing policies, which had pursued an agenda of demolition, rebuilding and depopulation since the 1900s (Walsh et al., 2016). The creation in the 1960s of 'modern' housing schemes and high rises on the outskirts of Glasgow were intended to solve the issues of inner-city over-crowding and slum conditions. However, in the decades since, the schemes have declined and been 'abandoned as zones of violence, antisocial behaviour and crime' The areas of multiple deprivations in which Dispersal accommodation is located are also situated within a broader precedent of social marginalisation and displacement in Glasgow. Many of the Dispersal sites and their housing stock were the result of successive Glasgow City Council housing policies, which had pursued an agenda of demolition, rebuilding and depopulation since the 1900s (Walsh et al., 2016). The creation in the 1960s of 'modern' housing schemes schemes and high rises on the outskirts of Glasgow were intended to solve the issues of inner-city over-crowding and slum conditions. However, in the decades since, the schemes have declined and been 'abandoned as zones of violence, antisocial behaviour and crime' (McAllister, 2015, p.244). These sites have subsequently been subject to programmes of social and economic 'renewal' and 'regeneration' since the latter half of the twentieth century. These programmes include:

- Glasgow Eastern Area Renewal Project (GEAR)
- Glasgow City Council's Transformational Regeneration Areas (TRAs)
- 2014 Commonwealth Games Regeneration programme
- The Gorbals Regeneration Projects
- Central Govan Action Plan (CGAP)

Regeneration programmes in Glasgow have had mixed successes. Though some initiatives have achieved community-approved results, many others have exacerbated conditions of exclusion and marginalisation for residents. Asylum seekers in Glasgow are highly likely to live in areas that are the subject of regeneration programmes.⁸ The top nine Glasgow areas in which asylum seekers are most populous are all regeneration sites and areas of multiple deprivations. However, despite this overlap, asylum seekers remain notably absent from local and national regeneration policies. This absence bears further investigation.

Once an asylum seeker has gained leave to remain, they are obliged to leave Dispersal accommodation within 28 days. However, the route to permanent accommodation is not easy. In Glasgow, individuals have usually either applied to Registered Social Landlords themselves or presented themselves as homeless to Glasgow City Council when their asylum support ended. Once assessed, refugees are eligible for social housing; however, the shift in status from asylum seeker to refugee, while positive, also brings stress and worry of being evicted from their accommodation and facing imminent homelessness.

8. Information cross-referenced from Scottish Government (2016a) and UK Government (2016)

3.2 Education and Developing Linguistic Competences

Education and English-language acquisition are seen as key facilitators of the integration of displaced people by both the UK and the Scottish Governments. In this context, education is closely linked to English-language acquisition (OECD, 2016). The UK Government identifies education and language-learning as facilitators of social inclusion, civic participation and economic contribution (APPGR, 2017). English-acquisition is seen to help adult refugees navigate processes of integration and civic citizenship, form social networks with other populations in the UK, participate in public life, and gain employment (Court, 2017). It has also been associated with physical and mental health (Bakker et al., 2017). The education of children and young adults is also seen as a key facilitator of their 'integration', which enables them to acquire knowledge and skills for future employment, form social networks, and develop citizenship skills (Pastoor, 2017). More recent UK Government approaches have shifted from seeing education and English-language-skills as facilitators of integration to markers of integration. English-language acquisition has increasingly been used to measure and identify the extent to which a population has 'integrated' (or is seen to have integrated) into mainstream society. In recent years, English-language abilities have also become subject to securitised discourses that have linked a lack of English-language proficiency within some minority populations with a failure to 'integrate', isolationism, social conservatism and fundamentalism.⁹ However, despite a UK Government focus of English-language acquisition in integration processes, it has been criticised for under-resourcing English-language support (APPGR, 2017). Since 2007, the UK Government has excluded asylum seekers from free access to ESOL courses (Mulvey, 2015, p. 454) and although the UK Government provides free English language classes to all those with refugee status under the English for Speakers of Other Languages (ESOL) Programme, there are significant restrictions on this provision. A 2017 investigation into ESOL provision in London by the Independent found that refugees were waiting up to three years to access ESOL classes (McIntyre, 2017). Accessing schooling can also be a struggle and RCOs claim that thousands of children seeking asylum in the rUK are being denied access to education.¹⁰

In Scotland, the situation is different. Under the Scotland Act 1998, education is devolved to the Scottish Government, which has enabled the Scottish Government to develop education and language strategy separately to rUK. As a result, Scottish education policies have worked alongside Scottish integration approaches to provide access to both refugees and asylum seekers to ESOL and education. The Scottish Government's Standards in Scotland's Schools Etc Act (2000) establishes universal access to compulsory education in Scotland for all children and young people, including those of refugee or asylum seeking backgrounds (Scottish Government, 2017a, p. 53). The Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004 emphasises the need for planned support to meet the needs of individual children and young people who experience barriers to learning. The Race Relations (Amendment) Act 2000 places a general duty on public authorities to eliminate unlawful racial discrimination, to promote equality of opportunity and to promote good relations between people of different racial groups. Local authorities are encouraged to adopt their own strategies for aiding children in schools for whom English is not a first language.

9. These discourses have also been racialised and gendered, and frequently target Muslim populations (Rashid 2016). See, for instance, (ex) Prime Minister David Cameron's comments about the failure of 'Muslim women' to learn English (Mason and Sherwood 2016).

10. Children in initial accommodation in England and Wales do not have a legal right to attend school and are not allowed to go on a waiting list to get a school place. Local councils claim they do not have a legal responsibility to provide education for them and those schools that are 'academies' are free of local government control and can't be forced by the council to take new arrivals.

Glasgow City Council has an English as an Additional Language (EAL) service that provides support to these children who attend educational establishments in Glasgow. EAL teachers in the city work in nursery, primary, secondary and additional support for learning schools. The EAL Service is available to all children and young people whether they have recently arrived in Glasgow from another country and are new to learning English or simply those who have always lived in Glasgow but use a language other than English at home. EAL teachers work alongside other school staff to help children access the curriculum and achieve their potential.

Since 2007, the Scottish Government has also established its own ESOL strategy, which was recently updated as the *Welcoming our learners: Scotland's English for Speaker of Other Languages (ESOL) Strategy 2015-2020* (Scottish Government, 2015b). The provision of education and English-language classes for asylum seekers and refugees has been achieved through collaborative work between Scottish Government agencies, local and higher education authorities and third sector parties. For instance, for those over the age of 16, the Scottish Funding Council 'waives fees for asylum seekers attending college and studying a full or part-time ESOL course or other part-time advanced or non-advanced course' (Scottish Government, 2017a, p. 54). A number of universities in Scotland have also developed scholarship schemes for people seeking asylum in Scotland. ESOL provision in Scotland similarly involves collaboration between the Scottish Government and further education colleges, which are governed and funded by the Scottish Government's Community Planning Partnerships (Scottish Government, 2017a, p. 54). ESOL provision was also funded and supported by the Holistic Integration Service, which was administrated by the Scottish Refugee Council and delivered by Glasgow's Integration Networks and some NGOs (Strang et al., 2015). Beneficiaries accessed ESOL classes at Workers Educational Association Scotland and Glasgow Clyde College and HIS partners supported refugees in their dealings with the DWP by teaching relevant vocabulary. ESOL tutors also have an important role in explaining the sanctions system in relation to benefits and supporting JSA claimants with advice on completing the necessary paperwork. The benefits system often works against further engagement with ESOL classes and other forms of education because full time students are not eligible for JSA nor Housing Benefit.

Scottish Government approaches to the education and language-support of displaced people are shaped by Scotland-specific integration policies. The inclusion of asylum seekers in ESOL and education provision is consistent with the Scottish Government's 'from day one' integration strategy (Scottish Government, 2018). Under this approach, English-language and education acquisition are understood as stages that facilitate integration within a rights and citizenship framework (Ager and Strang, 2008) – an emphasis that is in some contrast to rUK approaches, which emphasise education and English-language acquisition as part of the 'hospitality' exchange. Furthermore, the New Scots emphasis on integration as a two-way process has increasingly prompted the Scottish Government to explore alternative modes of language-learning and acquisition. For instance, the *Sharing Lives Sharing Languages* programme (Hirsu and Bryson, 2017) foregrounds a participative approach to language learning and 'aims to build connections between refugees and those whose first language is not English, and the host community' (Scottish Government, 2017a, p. 55).¹¹ Language learning is clearly a key component in terms of accessing the labour market and these two areas of integration clearly overlap.

11. These initiatives might also be seen in the context of Scotland's linguistic landscape. Scotland has officially been designated a multilingual country since 2005 (Phipps 2017). Though English therefore remains a dominant language in Scotland, it does not retain a complete monopoly on public life, and there are an increasing number of initiatives to promote minority languages in Scotland, albeit in a so far limited capacity.

3.3 Integration into the Labour Market and Skills Training

One of the key distinctions between asylum seekers and refugees in the UK is the right to work. While anyone given humanitarian protection status as a refugee is permitted to work, asylum seekers cannot lawfully do so while they are waiting for their case to be decided.¹² It is unsurprising therefore that some have pointed to an inherent contradiction between UK integration strategies that focus on employment and the restrictive government policies that negatively affect access to the labour market (Bloch, 2008). Indeed, such restrictions placed on asylum seekers by policy acted at a UK level has an impact which has to be subsequently dealt with by a combination of the Scottish government and local authorities such as Glasgow City Council (Mulvey, 2015).

One of the reasons why a distinctly Scottish approach to refugees and asylum seekers has been pursued is the demographic reality of a falling and ageing population combined with a continuing out-migration of younger and skilled people. In this context the Scottish Government (formerly the Scottish Executive) 'highlighted a need to encourage more people to choose to live and work in Scotland and recognises that refugees (and potentially asylum seekers) have much to contribute to Scotland's economic and social development' (Charlaff, 2004). Programmes were subsequently launched to integrate refugees into the teaching and medical professions. The Refugees Into Teaching in Scotland (RITeS) project which ran between 2004 and 2011 allowed hundreds of experienced teachers among the refugee population to get back in the classroom. RITeS offered shadow placements, access to university retraining, upgrading and English courses, teaching opportunities in Scottish schools and guided registration for the General Teaching Council for Scotland (GTCS). It also helped with the job search, interview techniques and work placements.¹³

Starting from the year 2000, the NHS in Scotland has also benefitted from UK wide projects for Refugee Doctors (Jackson et al., 2004, Stewart, 2007, Piętko-Nykaza, 2015).¹⁴ This scheme was relaunched by the Scottish Government in 2016 as the New Refugee Doctors Project in collaboration with the British Medical Association (BMA) and NHS in Scotland. It was designed to 'help to prevent de-skilling, offer the opportunity to observe the NHS in action and opportunities to experience the reality of working as a doctor in Scotland; and overcome potential cultural and linguistic barriers while working towards passing their clinical and language exams' (Scottish Government, 2016). The project received further funding in 2017 and distinguishes itself from other refugee doctor programmes in the UK by offering placement and clinical attachments around understanding the structure, culture and ethics of NHS Scotland as well as giving doctors access to postgraduate study and dedicated support for learning English, post-registration and job hunting.¹⁵

12. This restriction on working for asylum seekers has been in place since 2002. They can only apply for permission to work if they have waited for over 12 months for an initial decision on their claim although they are only allowed to do jobs on the "shortage occupations list".

13. Moving into teaching in Scotland was not straight forward with only 41 of the 301 teachers registered with the project having achieved GTCS registration as of May 2010 (Smyth and Kum 2010).

14. In her analysis of the integration of these doctors in Scotland in 2003-2005, Stewart (2005) notes that cities like Glasgow have few problems in recruiting staff whereas it is the more rural and remote areas that would benefit from the skills of these refugees

15. See the video produced by NHS Education for Scotland <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B6JbiqrFEO8>

As Scotland's largest city and the home for a majority of Scotland's refugees and asylum seekers, Glasgow has developed a series of multi-agency networks as a way to facilitate integration and the joint working across the public, private and voluntary sectors, including agencies such as the Scottish Refugee Council (Wren, 2007). Prior to October 2015, few local authorities outside of Glasgow had experience of refugees or resettlement. Therefore, Glasgow has been a substantial focus for the work of government initiatives such as the 'New Scots' refugee integration strategy (2014-2017) that was developed by the Scottish Government, COSLA and the Scottish Refugee Council which addressed six key thematic areas including 'employability and welfare rights' (Scottish Government, 2017). The city has been at the fore in developing solutions to help with the transition into employment. One of the most successful initiatives has been the Bridges Programmes, a specialist agency supporting the social, educational and economic integration of refugees, asylum seekers and migrants. It was founded in 2002 as a means to aid integration and develop skills for the work place and was originally piloted in the NHS and the construction industry. It now works directly with a range of employers and partners to help its clients into work if they are eligible or offer work shadowing and work experience placements for those who are not. The Bridges Programmes has been involved with a range of projects and has pioneered specialized training such as the Women's Empowerment Course (Hewitt et al., 2010).

The Bridges Programme has become the key partner for a range of initiatives such as the Refugee Integration Service (RIS) operated by the Scottish Refugee Council. It operates a 'skills audit' which assists individuals to recognise which skills and experiences are of value on the UK labour market (Martin, 2016). Bridges was also instrumental in 'New Scots' and delivered the employability element of the Holistic Integration Service (HIS) that ran from 2013-2016 with each person referred receiving an initial employment, education and skills assessment and then a developed Employment Action Plan. The clients referred to Bridges Programmes 'benefitted from the opportunities to explore career choices and support to enhance their CV (through training, education and work experience) to achieve their aspirations' (Strang et al., 2015).

3.4 Gender Dynamics of Reception and Integration

Gender dynamics affect all aspects and stages of seeking asylum, (not) gaining leave to remain and 'integration'. Constructions of gender by (1) incoming populations, (2) immigration authorities and integration initiatives and (3) established 'host' populations have impact upon people of all genders; however, the gendered dynamics of UK immigration and integration often disproportionately negatively affect women (Cheung and Phillimore, 2017). These dynamics are reflected across all levels of provision for displaced people. There is no current precedent in international law for a person's right to claim asylum on account of gendered persecution (Crawley, 2001). Furthermore, though international law is 'gender-neutral in theory', there is a long-established precedent of cases being seen according to gender binaries (male/female), and preference given to cases concerning 'male dominated, 'public' activities' over cases concerning matters normatively associated with the female and consequently (in this paradigm) with women (i.e. the 'domestic') (Crawley, 2001, p.17). As a result, the issues that may cause women to seek asylum – violence that is gender-based, and both domestic and political – are often ill-accounted for, or seen as secondary to 'public' persecution (predominantly) faced by men. In the UK, men made up 75% of main applicants for asylum in 2016 (Blinder, 2016). However, though men made up the majority of 'main applicants', 60 to 70% of dependents associated with these applications are women and girls (Scottish Government, 2017a, p.26), who often have specific needs in categories of health, education and accommodation, but whose entitlements are often obscured by an institutional focus on the 'main applicant' (Scottish Government, 2017a, p.26). Meanwhile, though (reserved) UK government provisions for refugees and integration remain ostensibly 'gender neutral', Government policies that have increasingly restricted the rights of refugee dependents¹⁶ has mostly impacted women, and has meant, for example, that women who are dependents do not have the right access to state-funded emergency refuges in cases of domestic violence (Phillips, 2006, pp.444-5).

Uneven gendered dynamics can be found throughout all categories associated with integration processes in the UK, and Franz suggests that 'variation in integration outcomes are more likely to be determined by gender than other variables' (Franz, 2003). These dynamics often intersect with other social dynamics – including all those identified by the GLIMER Project (accommodation, education, employment) and other social categories (race, ethnicity, class, nationality) – and cannot be viewed in isolation. With an emphasis on the gendered aspects of GLIMER categories, the following issues arise:

Housing and social inclusion

- Cheung and Phillimore (2017) find that NASS accommodation had a significant lasting negative effect on self-reported health for both genders.
- However, they also find that NASS accommodation had an adverse effect on asylum seeking women's ability to access local services and healthcare (Cheung and Phillimore, 2017).
- This is supported by other research. Poor and unhealthy housing conditions for asylum seekers have been linked to increased health risks for asylum seeking women. Open Democracy documents the unsanitary and unsafe accommodation in which pregnant asylum-seeking women are housed.¹⁷

16. Once a person is granted refugee status, they are allowed to bring dependents to the UK. However, to successfully gain entry, applicants must prove that they have no 'recourse to public funds' (Phillips 2006, 444-5).

17. Refugee and asylum seeking women make up 12% of all maternal deaths, and 0.3% of the population in the UK (Grayson 2017)

Education, English-language provision and employment

- Women asylum seekers and refugees experience additional barriers to English-language acquisition (Brahmbhatt et al., 2007). There were significant gender differences in language fluency and literacy with men reporting higher scores in both (Cheung and Phillimore, 2017, p.219).
- Asylum seeking and refugee women are more likely than men to live with dependent children (39% v. 17%) (Cheung and Phillimore, 2017, p.220). Akua-Sakyiwah highlights that a lack of access to childcare often creates barriers to women's access to ESOL and education (Akua-Sakyiwah, 2012).
- A lack of access to (or provision of) childcare for education and ESOL classes also often creates additional barriers to employment and welfare. Balancing childcare, education, ESOL classes and Job Centre attendance is often difficult or unfeasible, and non-attendance at Job Centre interviews can incur benefit sanctions (Akua-Sakyiwah, 2012). A lack of childcare provision can therefore have serious, long-term effects not only on women's access to ESOL classes and education, but subsequently on their employment prospects and/or access to welfare.
- Women refugees have significantly worse labour market outcomes than men (Wren, 2007), with 23 per cent more men in work than women (Cheung and Phillimore, 2017, p.219).
- Refugee women who receive benefits are likely to be disproportionately affected by cuts in welfare provision caused by austerity measures (Bassel and Emejulu, 2017).

Women seeking asylum and refugee women in Scotland experience many of the issues highlighted above (Strang et al., 2015). Mulvey notes that in Scotland, 'women in the asylum process in particular indicate very low WEMWBS scores, lower than the lowest economic quintile of the overall Scottish population' (Mulvey, 2015, p.371; quotes Given, 2008). There are some initiatives in Scotland that specifically target issues affecting asylum seeking and refugee women, including:

- The Scottish Government's Strategy on Violence Against Women (Scottish Government, 2015a), under which asylum seeking and refugee women are given provision (within devolved powers)
- The Scottish Government's National Action Plan on Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) (Scottish Government, 2017c), an initiative developed over the last decade with women's community groups, the Scottish Refugee Council, NGOs and the Scottish Government.
- The Scottish Government is 'also about to take control over aspects of social security that were previously reserved to Westminster, including maternity grants' (Murray, 2016).
- A number of local charities and community groups in Glasgow contain specific provision for women's groups.

Appendix A: Abbreviations and Acronyms

AMINA MWRC – Amina Muslim Women’s Resource Centre
APPGR – All Party Parliamentary Group on Refugees
BEMIS – Black Ethnic Minority Infrastructure in Scotland
BMA – British Medical Association
CEAS – Common European Asylum System
CEMVO – Council of Ethnic Minority Voluntary Sector Organisations
CGAP – Central Govan Action Plan
COMPASS – Commercial and Operational Managers Procuring Asylum Support Services
COSLA – Convention of Scottish Local Authorities
CRER – Coalition for Racial Equality and Rights
CUKC – Citizenship of the United Kingdom and Colonies
DWP – Department for Work and Pensions (UK Government)
ESOL – English for Speakers of Other Languages
FGM – Female Genital Mutilation
GEAR – Glasgow Eastern Area Renewal Project
GCC – Glasgow City Council
GRAMNet – Glasgow Refugee, Asylum and Migration Network
GTCS – General Teaching Council for Scotland
HIS – Holistic Integration Service
IAA – Immigration and Asylum Act (1999)
ILR – Indefinite Leave to Remain
IN – Integration Network
NASS – National Asylum Support Service
NGO – Non-Government Organisation
NHS – National Health Service
RCO – Refugee Community Organisation
RIES – Refugee Integration and Employment Service
RITeS – Refugees into Teaching in Scotland
RSL – Registered Social Landlord
rUK – Rest of UK (excluding Scotland)
SUNRISE – Strategic Upgrade of National Refugee Integration
TRA – Transformational Regeneration Area
UNHCR – United Nations Human Commission for Refugees
VPRS – Syrian Vulnerable Persons Relocation Scheme
WEMWBS – Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale

Appendix B: Selected Relevant Legislation and Policy

Year	Legislation / Policy Initiatives	Body
1948	UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights	United Nations
1948	British Nationality Act	UK Government
1951	UN Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees	United Nations
1962	Commonwealth Immigrants Act	UK Government
1965	Race Relations Act	UK Government
1968	Commonwealth Immigration Act	UK Government
1971	Immigration Act	UK Government
1981	Nationality Act	UK Government
1993	Asylum and Immigration Appeals Act	UK Government
1996	Asylum and Immigration Act	UK Government
1998	Scotland Act	UK Government
1999	Immigration and Asylum Act	UK Government
2000	Race Relations Act	UK Government
2000	Race Relations (Amendment) Act, Scotland Order	UK Government
2002	Nationality, Immigration and Asylum Act	UK Government
2002	Race Equality Scheme	Scottish Executive
2004	Asylum and Immigration (Treatment of Claimants etc) Act	UK Government
2006	Immigration, Asylum and Nationality Act	UK Government
2007	UK Borders Acts	UK Government
2008	Race Equality Statement	Scottish Government
2009	Borders, Citizenship and Immigration Act	UK Government
2010	Equality Act	UK Government
2011	Prevent Programme	UK Government
2015	Community Empowerment (Scotland) Act	Scottish Government
2016	Scotland Act	UK Government
2016	Race Equality Framework	Scottish Government
2016	Immigration Act	UK Government

Appendix C: UK Asylum and Refugee Pathways

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Work Package 2: Cyprus and Nicosia

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1 KEY EVENTS AND DEMOGRAPHIC DEVELOPMENTS IN MIGRATION

The literature evaluating the development of migration policies in Cyprus indicate a dramatic transformation over the past 30 years; Cyprus has evolved from a country of emigration to one of immigration: In terms of emigration, the island experienced two waves in its recent history. The first, in the early 20th century, involved a large-scale emigration¹ of Cypriots, predominantly for employment and economic purposes, and the second occurred between 1960 and 1975, principally as a² consequence of the rise in ethnic tensions and the subsequent invasion of the island by Turkey.

More recently, in the 1990s, labour shortages and other external factors resulted in a policy shift with regard to the system of governance relating to asylum and integration. Prior to engaging in this aspect however, we present a brief overview of Cyprus' migration history and approach undertaken up to this shift, in order to provide a rationale for current policy.

Conquerors have historically been attracted to the geographical position of the island, as it's located at the crossroads of the European, Asian and African continents. Cyprus provided safe harbour to many refugees in the early 20th century while it was a British colony - Armenians and Greeks from Asia Minor, Jews on their way to Palestine and Lebanese fleeing from war.³ British camps⁴ in Cyprus, which provided protection to Jewish refugees after the Second World War, raised concern among the local population, who feared the potential economic burden on the island by this new influx of refugees. These concerns were amplified by the uncertainty about the residence status of these refugees and the impact their stay would have on the national aspirations of the Greek-Cypriot community which sought to unify with Greece (Enosis).⁵ A recent analysis of local media articles from the 1940s and records of social commentary at the time indicate that organisations across the political spectrum were resistant to the arrival of the Jewish refugees, requesting "a ban on Jews or other foreigners entering Cyprus".⁶

The island gained its independence from the British in 1960, but the Republic which was established was quickly enmeshed in a period of ethnic tension between the Greek-Cypriot and Turkish-Cypriot communities, leading to the 1974 invasion and occupation of 37% of the island by Turkey. The gross domestic product (GDP) consequently suffered a severe drop during the period of 1973-5, accompanied by a distinct rise in unemployment and poverty.⁷ From that turbulent period, what remains in Cyprus is a physical and ethnic partition between the two communities, with the Greek-Cypriot community residing south of the UN buffer zone (the so-called 'green line'), while the Turkish-Cypriot community resides to the north of it. This report focuses on the area south of the green line, the internationally recognised Republic of Cyprus.

1. According to the definition used by the Cyprus Statistical Service, emigration includes individuals who have resided in Cyprus for at least a year who subsequently leave the country to settle elsewhere.

2. Panayiotis Gregoriou, Zenon Kontolemis and Maria Matsi: Immigration in Cyprus: An analysis of the determinants. Cyprus Economic Policy Review, Vol 4, No, 1, pp 63 – 88 (2010).

3. Migrants, Social Space and Visibility, The Cyprus Review, vol 20(2), pp 189-193.

4. These have been described as being akin to transitional camps for displaced persons that were founded and operated opportunistically to facilitate British policy in the Middle East: Alexios Alecou and Josefina Mavrou: Refugees in Cyprus: Local Acceptance in the Past and Present (2017)

5. This interpretation is presented in Ibid 4

6. Selioti V, British Refugee Camps in Cyprus (1946 – 1949). Thessaloniki: Epikentro. (2016). It cites a variety of articles in the newspaper 'Eleftheria' and its coverage of the issue during the period covering 1946-8.

7. Press Information Office 1997: The Almanac of Cyprus 1996, PIO Cyprus.

Since 1974, there have been waves of migration to the north of the island by ethnic Turks; this has been perceived as a “methodical plan by Turkey to alter population balances with obvious political motives”⁸ and it is critical to view the developments to Cyprus’ migration policy in light of this fact. The ‘Cyprus issue’, which continues to dominate political discourse and permeate policy in every affected field, has had a galvanising effect on the Greek-Cypriot community in terms of their continuing efforts to preserve a sense of ‘national identity’. As Vassiliadou⁹ asserts, the issue of ethnic identity in Cyprus is highly complex and assumptions which relate to ‘Cypriot identity’ tend to rely heavily on patriarchy, class and political affiliation. While a range of mainstream ethnic identities have been constructed and propagated,¹⁰ they are all complicit in the marginalisation and erasure of the ‘other’, which includes women, as well as subgroups that are largely oppressed or discriminated against, such as migrants. Therefore, the development of immigration policy and strategy in Cyprus has at its core the preservation of the Greek Cypriot community’s ‘identity’. Understanding this perception and desire to hold onto the national identity can also explain the state’s reluctance and continuing lack of proactiveness to propose or effectively implement policies promoting integration.

Since 1974, a population of approximately 200,000 internally displaced Greek-Cypriots provided the economy with cheap labour which, combined with the government’s assistance and the political environment of the time, created positive conditions, making the economic revival of the island possible.¹¹ During the 1980s and 1990s, Cyprus experienced dramatic economic growth, often called the “economic miracle”,¹² which resulted in an increased demand for labour. Up until 1990 however, immigration policy was highly restrictive. The economic surge brought about the need to overhaul the approach towards immigration policy and an evaluation of the needs of the labour market and the economy. In contrast with other Western European countries—which had greater experience with migration flows, as well as a more developed legislative and policy framework adept at meeting the needs of both migrants and the labour market—Cyprus lacked the appropriate legal, administrative or operational infrastructure to tackle the issue.¹³

The most recent population census undertaken in the Republic of Cyprus in 2011, tallies the population at 840,407 (with 659,115 Greek-Cypriots, 3,656 Maronites, 1,831 Armenians, 208 Latins,¹⁴ 1,128 Turkish-Cypriots, and 170,383, around 20%, foreign citizens).¹⁵ Since 1990, there has been a dramatic increase in immigration. In 1990, according to the Cyprus Statistical Service, there were 545 migrant workers who were documented third country nationals (TCNs); a figure that rose to an

8. Margarita Zervidou, National Report: The case of Cyprus, in: *Integration of Female Migrant Domestic Workers: strategies for employment and civic participation* (2008) Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies.

9. Myria Vassiliadou, *Questioning Nationalism: The Patriarchal and National Struggles of Cypriot Women within a European Context*, *The European Journal of Women’s Studies* (2002), Vol. 9(4): 459–482

10. The range of identities outlined by Vassiliadou (Ibid 9) are: the right-leaning political groups, advocating a patriarchal Greek identity and excluding a regional, Cypriot identity, the predominantly working-class left, who emphasize their identity as Cypriots, and downplay the Greek aspect. A smaller group, the Neo-Cypriots, present Cypriotism as the ‘real’ identity of Greek Cypriots in opposition to ‘Greek-ness’.

11. Anthias F. and Ayres R. *Ethnicity and Class in Cyprus*, *Race and Class*, XXV, (1983), pp 59–76.

12. Demetris Christodoulou. *Inside the Economic Miracle. The Labours of an Embattled Economic*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota. (1992)

13. Cochliou D. and Spaneas S. *Asylum system in Cyprus: a field for social work practice*, *European Journal of Social Work*, 12(4), pp 535 – 540.

14. Armenians, Maronites and Latins are officially recognised as religious minorities in the Republic of Cyprus, and all three communities are represented in the House of Parliament, without, however, having a vote.

15. Non-Cypriot nationals.

estimated 68,000 by 2011.¹⁶ In fact, as Teerling & King asserted, “Cyprus has experienced, proportionate to its population, the largest-scale immigration in recent years. Of the EU27, Cyprus had the highest rate of net immigration during the mid-late 2000s”.¹⁷ This said, despite the major migration crisis in the Mediterranean and the island’s proximity to the Middle East, the number of asylum seekers arriving in Cyprus remains relatively low in comparison to Greece and Italy. According to the Statistical Service, it has been estimated that in 2015, there were less than 3,000 asylum seekers arriving in Cyprus.¹⁸ The Council of Europe Commissioner for Human Rights attributed these low figures to the “island’s geographical isolation from the rest of Europe, [being] outside of the Schengen area, difficulties in leaving the country and restrictive asylum policies, especially regarding family reunification.”¹⁹

When it comes to residence permits granted to foreign nationals and migrants, the number seems disproportionate to the general population. For example, the number of female migrant domestic workers in Cyprus: The Civil Registry and Migration department²⁰ granted 15,610 permits to domestic workers in just 2015 – which constituted 35% of the total number of permits that had been granted since the start of the scheme. At the same time, the total number of domestic workers in Cyprus amount to more than 30,000 and it is estimated that the island hosts an additional 30,000 undocumented domestic workers. Female migrant domestic workers statistically form the biggest group of foreign residents in Cyprus and, as such, warrant particular consideration with respect to their access to services, education and the labour market, as well as their human rights.

Justifications for the surge in immigration are multi-fold. As mentioned above, on the one hand, Cyprus’s economic growth translated in a corresponding increased demand in labour. The initial justification for opening its doors to migrant labour in 1989 was that there was a temporary need to “cover the developmental needs arising from the shortage of labour”.²¹ Political developments around the world also had an impact on migration to Cyprus in the early 1990s. Namely, the collapse of the Soviet Union, the migration of a large number of Pontiacs from the Caucus region who had been granted Greek citizenship, the Gulf war and successive crises in the Middle East region, unrest in Israel and Palestine, and the fall of Yugoslavia.²² The same factors were behind the migration trend of Eastern European women arriving in Cyprus to work as ‘artistes’ in high risk establishments, often victims of trafficking for the purposes of sexual exploitation.

According to the Civil Registry and Migration department, the main factors behind the increased migration flow into Cyprus since 2004 have been “a) the need of individuals for circumstances that

16. Statistical Service of the Republic of Cyprus, Latest Figures: Population and Social conditions, available at: http://www.mof.gov.cy/mof/cystat/statistics.nsf/populationcondition_22main_en/populationcondition_22main_en?OpenForm&sub=2&sel=2 (accessed on 12 December 2017).

17. Teerling, J and King, R. Cyprus as a Multi-diasporic space, Working Paper No 67, Sussex Centre for Migration Research, University of Sussex (2011).

18. This is mainly due to the fact that Cyprus is an island, i.e. it has no easily traversable land borders with other European countries. It is also not very close by sea to the next closest European country, making it difficult for asylum seekers to journey on to their preferred host countries, usually in western or northern Europe.

19. Report by Commissioner for Human Rights, Council of Europe, following his visit to Cyprus from 7 – 11 December 2015: [https://rm.coe.int/ref/CommDH\(2016\)16](https://rm.coe.int/ref/CommDH(2016)16) (accessed 19 December 2017).

20. Statistics can be found at: <http://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/crmd/crmd.nsf/All/083980C0BA1B224AC2257EA4003861BA?OpenDocument> (accessed on 15 December 2017). (accessed on 15 December 2017).

21. Trimikliniotis and Demetriou, Labour Integration of Migrant Workers in Cyprus: A critical appraisal, Chapter in Mojca Pajnik and Giovanna Campani (2011), Precarious Migrant Labour Across Europe, MIROVNI INSTITUT, Ljubljana, pp 73 – 96 (2011).

22. Ibid 18

would provide them a better quality of life, b) sound democratic conditions that prevail in Cyprus, c) the accession to the European Union on 01/05/2004 and the benefits stemming from this accession, such as mobility once a legal status is acquired".²³ Moreover, despite the small size of the island, over the past decade, research²⁴ has shown an increased rate of Cypriots graduating from tertiary education, which has left a gap in the market for low skilled or manual labourers. Such positions have become increasingly filled by migrants.

23. Information provided by the Civil Registry and Migration Department to the Permanent Mission of the Republic of Cyprus to the Office of the UN at Geneva. July 3 2014 at: <http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/Migration/GA69thSession/Cyprus.pdf> (accessed on 12 December 2017).

24. Andri Kyrizi, Overeducation in Cyprus, University of Leicester, Department of Economics: <http://www.lse.ac.uk/europeanInstitute/research/hellenicObservatory/CMS%20pdf/Events/2011-5th%20PhD%20Symposium/Kyrizi.pdf> (accessed 16 December 2017).

1.1 Key Events and Demographic Developments in Migration

Literature focusing on the integration of migrants and asylum seekers in Cyprus remains sparse. The limited information tends to focus on asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection. Where a distinction is made, specific reference is provided on the particular needs and situation of the latter group.

From its inception, integration policy has been based on the premise that immigration to Cyprus serves the temporary purpose of covering labour shortages in specific sectors which are unpopular with Cypriots.²⁵ Integration in itself not being a priority, policy development in this field has remained limited. This has consequently resulted in criticism of the policy; there has been a “theoretical blindness of the gender aspects of the Europeanization of immigrant integration” which is said to also perpetuate “to a great extent the traditional gender blindness of theories of citizenship and rights”.²⁶ The ‘feminization of immigration’²⁷ has essentially changed “the structures of gender inequality”, in areas where “gender exclusion intersects with migrant status, race, class, sexuality etc, both in relation to the precariousness of migrants, as well as in relation to the patriarchal outlook of the state and state institutions”.²⁸ The European Commission asserts that Cyprus integration policy, which has been under-developed in general and especially so from a gender perspective, does not look at the “intersection of migrant status with structures of gender inequality in the receiving society”.²⁹ Doing so would ensure a more holistic approach to integration, taking into consideration the overlapping aspects and obstacles for all migrants and particularly women, being able to integrate in society.

According to the assessment by the 2015 Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX),³⁰ Cyprus has been ranked second to last among 37 countries in terms of achieving integration for migrants, and its policies have been concluded as discouraging long-term integration. MIPEX’s evaluation states that Cyprus has relatively unfavourable policies on mobility in the labour market, limiting access to migrants. Furthermore, very little targeted support has been found which would allow TCNs to access training, health or political participation. Despite the fact that Cyprus has put in place an EU-backed National Programme for the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF),³¹ the policies have been criticised by MIPEX as not being effective in promoting integration of migrants as they are restrictive and the limited support provided serves to discourage migrants and local communities from investing further in integration. Local NGOs³² have stressed that the majority of beneficiaries under this fund are public authorities, municipalities and consulting companies, and so doubt has been raised as to the effectiveness of this measure with respect to improving the integration of migrants. Moreover, the priorities set within the framework of the AMIF have not been based upon any consultation with groups representing migrant women; the priorities, therefore, are gender blind, thereby hampering their ability to adequately cater to the very groups in need of positive integration measures.

25. Ibid 18

26. Zelia Georgiou, Questioning the location of gender in integration discourses and policies, in *Young Migrant Women in Secondary Education*, Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies, 2011: http://www.medinstgenderstudies.org/wp-content/uploads/Integration_of_young_migrant_women_2011.pdf (accessed 19 December 2017).

27. Feminization of Migration is the phenomenon where the majorities of migrants travelling alone or as head of the families are women.

28. Ibid

29. Commission of the European Communities (2003) Communication on immigration, integration and employment. COM (2003) 336 final, Brussels, 3.6.2003.

30. Migrant Integration Policy Index 2015: <http://www.mipex.eu/cyprus> (accessed on 14 December 2017).

31. http://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/eufunds2015.nsf/page12_en/page12_en?OpenDocument (accessed 14 December 2017)

32. KISA: 75 million into a bottomless pit. <https://kisa.org.cy/75-million-into-a-bottomless-pit/> (accessed 18 December 2017)

The National Action Plan (NAP) for Integration of Immigrants Legally Residing in Cyprus 2010-2012³³ was adopted in 2010 by the Ministry of the Interior, as a result of the recommendation and support of the European Commission. Whilst this was an encouraging development, the NAP was drafted without consulting civil society or migrant organisations. Due to the lack of an inclusive approach in the drafting process, there is little to no focus on undocumented migrants and female migrants who are the most vulnerable groups and whose needs and circumstances warrant particular attention. The result of such an approach is the institutional marginalisation of these groups and a continuation of their inability to fully and actively participate across all levels of society.

Whilst the government had articulated that there were plans to draft a subsequent plan and strategy, this commitment remains unfulfilled. Currently, no NAP is in force and it is unknown whether there is a genuine commitment on the part of the government to adopt a comprehensive and inclusive policy. Successful integration is not solely determined on the existence and implementation of a comprehensive national policy, but also requires “the wider socio-economic relations within society as a whole”.³⁴ Cyprus has been described as having “poor governance and a fragmented civil society ... [which] impede progress towards successful integration irrespective of the effectiveness of a dedicated integration policy as such”.³⁵

The aforementioned NAP consisted of 8 priority pillars: i) information – service – transparency; ii) employment, training, trade unions; iii) education and language learning; iv) health; v) housing – improvement of quality of life, social protection and interaction; vi) culture, civics, basic elements of political and social reality; vii) participation; viii) assessment – annual and total. The lack of a substantive effort to define the integration process has indicated that “the Plan did not proceed on the basis of any substantive needs assessment of the ‘host community’, non-Cypriot communities of identity or interest or the needs of specific state institutions”.³⁶ Some success was recorded by ECRI,³⁷ according to information provided by the national authorities, namely the provision of Greek language programmes and the organisation of multicultural festivals. However, there doubt was expressed as to whether these sorts of disjointed actions led to any tangible long-term effects in promoting integration.³⁸ Moreover, the NAP was not subject to ongoing assessment by the authorities, nor was there an evaluation as to whether targets had been reached, a failing that was certainly compounded by the relatively small budget that was allocated to assessment efforts.³⁹

The NAP has been further criticised for failure to genuinely tackle social exclusion and promote integration of migrants in a variety of areas and across society. Specifically, despite general adherence to the European Union’s legislative framework regarding immigration and asylum, there is an absence of any gender mainstreaming in the migration and integration policies produced. This inadequacy of the framework is detrimental to migrant women in particular, who have been characterised as being invisible in both political and social discourse, as well as in society.⁴⁰ A variety

34. Officer and Taki, The needs of refugees and the integration process in Cyprus, UNHCR (2013): http://www.unhcr.org.cy/fileadmin/user_upload/Images/Protection/The_Needs_of_Refugees_-_26_June_.pdf (accessed 19 December 2017)

35. Ibid

36. Ibid 30

37. ECRI 2016: <https://www.coe.int/t/dghl/monitoring/ecri/Country-by-country/Cyprus/CYP-CbC-V-2016-018-ENG.pdf>

38. Ibid 30

39. Ibid 30

40. Views expressed in Integration of female migrant domestic workers: Strategies for Employment and Civic Participation pp 9, Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies (2008): <http://www.medinstgenderstudies.org/wp-content/uploads/integration-of-female-migrant-domestic-workers.pdf>

of problems experienced by female migrant workers have to their marginalisation and exclusion from the dominant culture and society, and as such warrant more strategic focus.⁴¹

Lastly, with respect to beneficiaries of international protection, at the end of 2014, Cyprus was hosting 3,412 refugees and persons with subsidiary protection status. As reported by UNHCR, whilst the NAP included some actions to address their needs, no integration measures were taken in favour of these persons. ECRI⁴² notes that they face many challenges, amongst others a lack of knowledge of the local language and culture, employment issues, lack of awareness that refugees are allowed by law to work after six months of having submitted their asylum application, and the non-availability of vocational training programmes. Furthermore, there are no measures in place to assist recognised beneficiaries of international protection to obtain social welfare or find accommodation and employment. This results in many remaining in reception centres in conditions which have been deemed not conducive to integration. The Council of Europe Commissioner for Human Rights, during his visit to the island in 2015,⁴³ condemned the 2014 law which restricted the right of refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection to family reunification. Local NGOs reported to the Commissioner that the very high rate of subsidiary protection reflected the “national authorities’ will to send the message that there is no long-term prospective in Cyprus for beneficiaries of international protection”.⁴⁴

41. Ibid 30

42 Ibid 33

43 Ibid 16

44 Ibid 16

2. CYPRUS IMMIGRATION AND ASYLUM

2.1 Regeneration and Urban Exclusion

The literature around the regeneration and urban exclusion of migrants is quite under-developed. Cyprus has a conservative political culture where power is predominantly held centrally, with local governments enjoying limited political autonomy.⁴⁵ Municipalities have the right to promote activities and events in a range of areas which depend on both the political will and the financial capability of the municipality in question. Since 2012, the municipality of Limassol, the second largest city in Cyprus after Nicosia, has participated in projects backed by the European Integration Fund, implementing a variety of 'social actions', such as Street Work,⁴⁶ which are specifically geared towards TCNs.

Limassol witnessed a rapid increase in its population since the 1974 Turkish invasion; apartment blocks were hastily built wherever space was available in order to accommodate the estimated 43,000 internally displaced persons from the North.⁴⁷ The need to provide immediate, as opposed to sustainable, housing for the sudden influx of displaced persons led to what has been characterised as "anarchistic urban development" in Limassol.⁴⁸ Today, these social housing estates are increasingly inhabited by migrants; this was enabled by a change in governmental policy over the years, which granted ownership titles to the original inhabitants, allowing them to rent their apartments out at affordable prices.⁴⁹

Nicosia, the capital of Cyprus and the largest city of the island, includes the old city and its immediate environs. The restrictions in movement between the Republic of Cyprus and the Turkish-occupied part of the island were partially lifted in April 2003. This resulted in several thousand Turkish-Cypriots crossing over to work south of the green line, where low skilled jobs were more readily available and salaries were higher. This greater freedom of movement has reportedly also resulted in "an unspecified number of undocumented migrants from Asia, northern Africa and the Middle East to enter the government-controlled area".⁵⁰ Migrant populations are spread throughout Nicosia, but are "particularly visible in the old centre of town owing to the concentration of poorly-kept buildings rented out for accommodation at relatively cheap prices".⁵¹ Despite the apparent ghettoisation of these areas, the actual number of migrants in Nicosia is not known. There are specific areas in the centre of the city, such as the Municipal Park, which attract migrants, especially on Sundays when migrant labourers such as domestic workers are usually given the day off.⁵² It has been argued that, as a result of negative public views on migration, there is a "sense of alienation from areas associated with

45. Legal base for local government is the Municipal Law of 1985 (N.111/85), found at: http://www.ucm.org.cy/Document-The_Municipalities_Law_in_English,966,35,English (accessed on 12 December 2017).

46. The initiative is funded by the Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance and takes place in a multi-ethnic part of the city. Several days a week a social worker is present in the neighbourhood to provide assistance and support where required. The programme targets 13-35 year olds, largely of Bulgarian, Romanian and Roma origin

47. Barderi, Freeman and Guidikova, City of Limassol, Intercultural Profile, Intercultural Cities (2011 updated in 2013)

48. Ibid 16

49. Olga Demetriou, British Council Living Together Programme, Migrant Cities Research: Nicosia South, November 2008. (PRIO, Cyprus)

50. Ibid 16

51. Ibid 45

52. Ibid 45

high migration levels, such as the old city within the walls".⁵³ According to a UNOPS⁵⁴ study, those who owned businesses but did not live in the area, exhibited much stronger intolerance towards migrants than the resident population. The municipality of Nicosia was criticised by local residents⁵⁵ in 2014 for having removed benches in public spaces in an attempt to appease business owners and encourage the gentrification of the old town. This removal not only impacts the youth and residents of the local area, but also serves to marginalise migrants who would use this area for leisure and entertainment.

A further important cause for concern⁵⁶ is the lack of basic infrastructure which affects the migrant population who are the primary users. An example is public transport. In Nicosia, the bus is the only available form of public transport; it has been reported to be unpunctual and unreliable, with a network that fails to adequately cover the city. This has pushed many migrants to ride bicycles instead, but as there are no cycle lanes in the city and local traffic is heavily made up of cars and drivers not adept at sharing the roads with cyclists, this has resulted in many road traffic accidents with migrants being injured. It is evident that the authorities have not taken the needs of migrants into consideration when developing urban infrastructure. This puts female migrants in an especially vulnerable position, as they already encounter great challenges in reconciling their daily responsibilities to their families and their employer and are further impeded by the lack of an efficient, effective transport infrastructure.

Effective urban planning is beneficial to migrant integration, particularly with respect to providing equal access to affordable and decent housing, as well as improving disadvantaged neighbourhoods. However, it is necessary for the authorities to undertake an assessment of the needs of the migrant community and model an urban development plan which would include measures to accommodate those needs.

Some ascertain that foreign permanent residents in Limassol "form mixed communities and there is no ghetto phenomenon".⁵⁷ Efforts⁵⁸ have been undertaken by the Limassol municipality in recent years to gentrify and revitalise the seafront promenade, pedestrian paths and cycle lanes, the old market square and the municipal gardens in an attempt to provide areas to facilitate greater interaction between the many communities residing in Limassol.

Despite these efforts however, a different picture emerges from the 2016 ECRI report on Cyprus⁵⁹ with respect to the Roma community. Cyprus submitted its Policy Measures for the Social Inclusion of Roma to the European Commission, under the EU Framework for National Roma integration strategies up to 2020,⁶⁰ where measures were outlined regarding the promotion of greater access to housing for the particular community in two cities (Limassol and Paphos). Despite claims that the policy was aimed at eliminating discrimination, ECRI notes that no measures have taken place nor have been planned in order to attain this goal. The two initiatives that were in fact implemented were

55. An independent residents group entitled 'Awake within the walls' issued a press release requesting the municipality to reinstate the public benches: <http://www.35-33.com/press-release-for-abuse-of-public-space-by-residents-of-old-nicosia/> (accessed on 13 December 2017) and a coverage of a public town hall meeting on the issue can be found at: <http://cyprus-mail.com/2014/04/06/the-battle-of-the-benches/> (accessed 13 December 2017).

56. Ibid 45

57. Ibid 16

58. Limassol municipal website: https://www.limassolmunicipal.com.cy/index_en.html (accessed on 12 December 2017).

59. Ibid 33

60. http://ec.europa.eu/justice/discrimination/files/roma_cyprus_strategy_en.pdf (accessed on 12 December 2017)

61. European Union and Roma Country Factsheet for Cyprus:

http://ec.europa.eu/justice/discrimination/files/roma_country_factsheets_2013/cyprus_en.pdf (accessed on 13 December 2017)

prefabricated housing projects, located in remote areas of the cities. The European Commission warned⁶¹ that this would result in Roma segregation and exclusion, and the ECRI has stated its disapproval of the settlements, stating that “the authorities have invested in improving or constructing further housing units specifically for Roma in these two specially designated areas away from contact with other members of society, thus promoting a policy and practice of de facto segregation”.⁶² Additionally, due to the lack of a targeted national strategy for the inclusion of the Roma population, as noted by ECRI, the Roma community “continue to be ignored and avoided in society”,⁶³ and have been rendered “invisible” in Cyprus.

The general perception of the local community towards migrants, as described throughout the literature review, appears to be overwhelmingly negative. The global economic crisis also affected the debates around immigration and employment in Cyprus and as unemployment rose in 2011, extreme right-wing groups⁶⁴ focused their rhetoric on connecting unemployment to the presence of migrant workers; the discourse has been demonstrably racist, at times even culminating in violence against migrants.⁶⁵

Preconceptions and negative stereotypes persist among the general population, and it has been argued that “these perceptions and stereotypes are to a large extent based on forging interconnections between race, gender and class”.⁶⁶ It has been claimed that “there appears to be a lack of awareness on what ‘racism’, ‘discrimination’ and ‘stereotyping’ really mean and what practices they may consist of, beyond the basic level”.⁶⁷ The literature summarises the public opinion that “migrants are poor, eternally in search of work and willing to undertake menial tasks or even engage in illicit or criminal activities to earn cash”.⁶⁸ It is further argued by the same authors that “at best migrants are seen as victims, at worst as unscrupulous”. It has been put forward that there is a “victimisation of the local population in a discourse of competition of ‘need’” whereby Greek-Cypriots, as victims of the 1974 Turkish invasion and subsequent economic hardship, have to compete with migrants for the limited available resources.⁶⁹

The stereotypes manifest themselves in particular ways in the area of domestic work and the sex industry: darker-skinned, smaller-built Asian women are thought to be better suited to housework, while tall, blonde, fair-skinned Eastern European women are considered to be more sexually desirable.⁷⁰ Despite the fact that discrimination based on colour is not the only form of racism, it has been suggested that “darker people are more likely (italicised in the original text) to be the target of racism”.⁷¹ Research undertaken indicates that “immigrant women in Cyprus experience a greater frequency of sexist and racist behaviour, belittlement by social circles or social exclusion”.⁷² ‘Filipina’ is a generalised term used for all female domestic workers, irrespective of nationality, while a more racist term commonly used to refer to domestic workers is ‘mavrou’ (little black woman). Certain ethnic

62. Ibid 33, pp21

63. Ibid 33, pp21

64. ELAM (National Popular Front). ELAM now a political party with a seat in Parliament.

65. Chowdhury and Kassimeris, Racist Violence in Cyprus, ENAR publication: https://kisa.org.cy/wp-content/uploads/2016/09/Racist-Violence-Cyprus_KISA.pdf (accessed 19 December 2017).

66. Agathangelou Anna, *The Global Political Economy of Sex: Desire, Violence and Insecurity in Mediterranean States*, London: Routledge (2004).

67. Ibid 45

68. Ibid 45

69. Ibid 45

70. Ibid 61

71. Trimikliniotis and Pantelides, *The European Dilemma: Institutional Patterns and the politics of ‘racial’ discrimination*,

72. Charalambidou-Solomi, Maouri and Economidou-Stavrou, *Female immigrants in Cyprus – profile, obstacles, needs, aspirations* (2010).

categories of workers are stereotyped as more suited to some professions more than others, demonstrating that migrants are facing perpetual, multi-layered discrimination by the general population. With respect to the Russian community however, who predominantly reside in Limassol, it has been generally claimed that “Russians are perceived more positively than most of the other migrant communities”.⁷³ This is primarily due the public perception of them being financially self-sufficient, Christian Orthodox and the historical and political links between Cyprus and Russia. Nevertheless, Russian women, and Eastern European women in general, who are not wealthy and often victims of trafficking in the sex industry are not perceived positively by the public.⁷⁴

With respect to asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection, amendments made in 2013 to the Refugee Reception Conditions Regulations created a general system of payment in kind, to replace direct financial aid or welfare support to asylum seekers. The effect of this is that newly-arrived asylum seekers and those who had so far been living in private housing and in receipt of welfare support are now required to live in the only reception centre in the country. Their free access to public transportation is insufficient, as the reception centre is located in an isolated rural area which is 45km from Nicosia, 30km from Larnaca and 40km from Limassol. The policy has been criticised as being detrimental for asylum seekers, in terms of access to the job market and public services or direct interaction with the local population, pushing them further to the fringes of society. This is especially disadvantageous to female asylum seekers who are their family’s primary caregivers; they are forced to undergo arduous travel arrangements in order to access basic necessities.

In Cyprus, the ‘refugee’ is widely used and understood as a specific term of reference for the internally displaced Greek Cypriots due to the events of 1974; “it is therefore difficult for public perceptions to accommodate the idea of ‘refugees’ as non-Cypriot”.⁷⁵ This persistent frame of reference could also be influencing the lack of adequate consideration afforded to those refugees currently residing in the reception centres.

73. Ibid 16

74. Social Welfare Services referred 169 potential victims to the police; of these, NGOs identified 52 potential victims and the government identified 117 potential victims. US Department of State 2017 report:

<https://www.state.gov/j/tip/rls/tiprpt/countries/2017/271175.htm> (accessed 19 December 2017)

75. Ibid 45

2.2 Education and Developing Linguistic Competences

The literature regarding education and the development of linguistic competence for the purposes of promoting greater integration into the educational system, vocational training and labour market is relatively limited. From the evidence that is available, it is apparent that the issue of racial, ethnic, religious and gender discrimination in education warrants further research. It has been argued that in order to understand exclusion and empowerment,⁷⁶ we must also investigate the gender structures, relations and norms in the school environment.

We now focus on policy, strategy and measures undertaken to successfully integrate non Cypriots in general, and refugees and asylum seekers in particular, in education and their development of linguistic competence. This must be “determined by a dedicated integration policy but also by the wider socioeconomic relations within society as a whole. So, for example, poor governance and a fragmented civil society which might characterise conditions within Cyprus more generally impede progress towards successful integration irrespective of the effectiveness of a dedicated integration policy as such”.⁷⁷

Refugees are entitled to a three-year residence permit, subject to an extension of three more years. The following rights are granted:

- The right to fair treatment regardless of gender, race, and religion, membership to a particular social group or political opinion or country of nationality.
- The right to the same treatment as nationals regarding among others the right to primary education, the right to full access of the minors to all levels of education, the right to education other than primary and particularly as regards to the access to education, the recognition of foreign education school certificates, diplomas and degrees, the exemption from tuition fee payment and the right to scholarships, the right to protection of literary rights, the right to participate in adult educational programmes that relate to issues of employment, professional training and practical performance at work places and the right to participate in social integration programmes.

According to a 2017 study⁷⁸ conducted by UNHCR Cyprus, it was highlighted that “there is no official procedure to assess the educational and cognitive level of the children upon enrolment” nor any consultation with respect to which class would be most appropriate for each child. This study confirms the findings of the Ombudsperson⁷⁹ which asserted that the state had yet to develop firm policies, free of racist or xenophobic influences, in order to ensure compliance with international legal standards and to ensure that every child enjoys their right to education. UNHCR underscores a

76. Zelia Gregoriou and Georgina Christou, *The dubious gift/debt of integration: Patriarchal regimes, ethnicity and sexuality in the school lives of migrant girls in Cyprus in: Young Migrant Women in Secondary Education: Promoting integration and mutual understanding through dialogue and exchange.* University of Nicosia Press 2011.

77. Trimikliniotis, *Mapping discriminatory landscapes in Cyprus: ethnic discrimination in a divided education system,* *The Cyprus Review,* Vol 15, Fall 2004.

78. Viewpoint expressed in: Trimikliniotis, Demetriou and Papamichael, *The embodiment of tolerance in discourses and practices addressing cultural diversity in schools: The case of Cyprus,* *Accept Pluralism Research Project,* European University Institute (2012).

79. *Ibid* 73

variety of recommendations with regards to the schooling of asylum-seeking children and refugees. Recommendations⁸⁰ include, inter alia: training programmes for school administrators and educators on refugee education policy, the development of a national educational policy for the effective integration of asylum-seeking and refugee children, and a comprehensive assessment and evaluation of the needs and capacities of the education system and the children. Lastly, in light of the fact that migrant children's perceptions have also been found to be "influenced and defined by the racial and patriarchal discourses of the host society to which they adjust", this aspect should be incorporated when drafting policies on integration and intercultural education.⁸¹

Further and in relation to asylum seekers, no specific measures have been undertaken with regards to their rights to education and their linguistic competence. However, when it comes to the asylum seekers who are minors, the refugee law⁸² provides for access to primary and secondary education on the same conditions as Cypriot citizens, immediately after applying for asylum to be implemented no later than three months from the date of submission. The Cyprus Refugee Council notes that "in practice, the vast majority of children access public education, However as there is no systematic monitoring of children's registration at school, there have been cases of children remaining out of the education system for more than 3 months, mainly for reasons related to difficulty of families accessing certain schools, lack of information / timely arrangements, limited schools' capacity at a given period to accommodate additional students etc. There is also a lack of official data on dropout rates regarding asylum-seeking children".

With regards to linguistic competence specifically, there are a few programmes that are accessible for refugees and asylum seekers. During the course of the desk research we found two main integration procedures, which assist TCNs in learning the local languages. These are provided by local municipalities, NGOs and through the public educational system but it should be noted that they are not specifically tailored to asylum seekers and refugees.

The language programmes for adult learning courses for migrants that are currently implemented regionally by public institutions, local municipalities and NGOs are the following:⁸³

80. Castles, Rogers, Vasta and Vertoce, Report on Migration and Social Integration of Migrant – Report on the Assessment of research reports carried out under the European Commission Targeted Socio-Economic Research (TSER) Programme, Centre for Migration and Policy Research, University of Oxford, Brussels (2003).

81. Ibid 71

82. <http://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/cyprus/access-education-0>

83. Information as received by Dr Stefanos Spaneas and Mr. Agamemnonas Zachariades, Centre of Social Cohesion, Development and Care of the University of Nicosia, through the project *RACCOMBAT: Preventing and Combatting Racism and Xenophobia through Social Orientation of Non-Nationals*.

PROVIDER	PROJECT TITLE	DESCRIPTION
Cardet (NGO)	BLEND-IN – Language, Cultural and Social Orientation for Young Refugees. ⁸⁴	BLEND-IN aims to prepare and empower young migrants & refugees seeking a better life in an EU host/ receiving country. In order to achieve this, the project partners will develop: A cultural, social and language integration toolkit in the form of a mobile application, orienting the young newcomer refugees and migrants into the hosting societies' cultural and social realities and norms;
Intercultural Centre (Municipality of Nicosia)	Integration programmes for TCNs – co-funded by AMIF	Multipurpose Centre which offers Greek & English language and digital literacy courses for migrants living in Nicosia. The Intercultural Centre provides a welcoming training area where members develop both their linguistic and e-skills to support their adaptation and integration into Cypriot society. For more information, see the Intercultural Centre's website .
Municipality of Agios Dometios	Integration programmes for TCNs – co-funded by AMIF	Offers Greek and English lessons but not year-round. In addition, it organises open discussions and reflective sessions on civic education issues on a monthly basis.
Municipality of Limassol	Integration programmes for TCNs – co-funded by AMIF	The municipality offers, English language, digital literacy, as well as first aid courses for migrants living in Limassol. In addition, it implements psycho-social interventions in primary schools which have a large proportion of migrant students.
Municipality of Aglatzia	Integration programmes for TCNs – co-funded by AMIF	The municipality offers English language and digital literacy lessons to TCNs.
Municipality of Ayios Athanasios	Open School Centre ⁸⁵	Open to all citizens, minors and adults. The Centre offers a wide range of courses enabling people to learn and develop new skills and abilities. Examples of courses on offer are: English, Modern Greek and basic skills in Information Technology. The Centre also offers a variety of cultural and art related courses, such as arts & crafts, theatre and dance as well as sports activities, which include tennis and volleyball.
Municipality of Geroskipou	Integration programmes for TCNs – co-funded by AMIF	The municipality offers English language, digital literacy lessons, first aid courses as well as international cooking courses for migrants living in Paphos/Geroskipou.
Municipality of Paphos	Integration programmes for TCNs – co-funded by AMIF	After school support for migrant primary school students; the programme runs on Saturday mornings between 9-12

84. For more information: <https://www.cardet.org/projects/current/763-blend-in-language-cultural-and-social-orientation-for-young-refugees>

85. For more information: <http://www.agiosathanasios.org.cy/%CE%91%CE%BD%CE%BF%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%84%CF%8C-%CE%A3%CF%87%CE%BF%CE%BB%CE%B5%CE%AF%CE%BF>

The University of Cyprus School of Modern Greek	Intensive Semester Courses. ⁸⁶	Free beginner's Greek classes in Nicosia from September to May
The KES College Cardet Innovade Municipality of Agios Dometios The Municipality of Deryneia The Municipality of Agios Athanasios The Municipality of Pafos	iLearnGreek ⁸⁷	Greek language courses to TCN over the age of 18, in order to support their integration into Cypriot society. The courses are offered in Nicosia, Limassol, Paphos, Kofinou and Deryneia and are at the beginner and intermediate levels. The following individuals may apply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refugees • Subsidiary Protection Beneficiaries • Asylum seekers • TCN with a student's or worker's or visitor's or Cypriot spouse's residence permit
The Ministry of Education and Culture	Adult education classes (Epimorfotika) ⁸⁸	These are held in the afternoons and evenings in various subjects, including language courses, such as Greek for beginners. These are offered all over the island at the local community level, open to all and at a low cost of EUR45-55 per year.
Ministry of Education	State Institutes of Further Education (SIFE) ⁸⁹	The fees are normally EUR250-400 per year, but for Guarantee Minimum Income (GMI) beneficiaries the cost is only EUR 10 per year.

What remains to be examined is whether asylum seekers and refugees have full access to the above, the rate of participation, the age and gender of participants, evaluation of the classes as well as their impact. To understand this, the research team in Cyprus will further examine these factors during the research phase.

86. For more information: www.ucy.ac.cy/mogr/en/courses

87. For more information: <http://www.ilearngreek.eu/en/>

88. For more information: <http://www.moec.gov.cy/epimorfotika/en/index.html>

89. For more information: http://www.moec.gov.cy/en/state_institutes.html

2.2 Education and Developing Linguistic Competences

In developing a model for migrants, Cypriot regulation took the framework of what was used to regulate migrant women in the sex industry (i.e. 'artiste' visas),⁹⁰ and developed it to cover other sectors of the labour market which revolved around unskilled, manual or otherwise low-wage work. As these regulations were extended to further sectors of occupation, trade unions began to view migrants as a potential 'threat' to the rights of Cypriot workers.⁹¹ Consequentially, a migration model was developed offering time-limited work permits, and only when no Cypriot nationals are willing or available to take the job.

As a consequence, we witness TNCs being overwhelmingly employed in sectors of the economy where there are labour shortages. Whilst steps have been taken by the government over the years in order to harmonise domestic legislation with those mandated by the European Union, more effort is required to remove the obstacles faced by migrant workers, especially female migrant workers,⁹² to have access and be integrated in the labour market, on a long-term basis.

Studies have suggested that "it is generally admitted ... that there is exploitation of foreign labour in Cyprus and especially on subjects such as pay, labour/industrial relations, and working conditions".⁹³ This has been attributed to "inadequate information, the general feeling of social exclusion, and marginalisation due to the inability and unwillingness of Cypriots to accept cultural diversity".⁹⁴ A framework has been developed where "low wage migrant workers can be utilised, rather than high skill, professional workers".⁹⁵ According to research on the distribution of work permits among migrant workers,⁹⁶ it has been found that there is a prevalence of permits being granted for low wage – low skill sectors, such as tourism, construction, agriculture and manufacturing, as well as domestic work.⁹⁷ Studies have highlighted cases where employers register migrant workers as farm workers but use them for a variety of other tasks unrelated to their job description and pay them less than what those jobs normally bring in as wages.⁹⁸ Meanwhile, professional migrant workers in offshore companies are perceived to enjoy favourable treatment free of discrimination, as a result of a targeted governmental policy to attract such companies to Cyprus.⁹⁹ This further erases the plight of migrant workers in low pay – low skill jobs.

90. Although reference is made to women in the sex industry on work permits, the position of MIGS is that prostitution is not a professional occupation and cannot therefore be subject to labour regulation.

91. Doros Polykarpou: <https://kisa.org.cy/wp-content/uploads/2013/03/Migrants-and-the-Right-to-Equal-Treatment-in-Cyprus.pdf> (accessed 16 December 2017).

92. When it comes to domestic workers, MIGS notes that there is a lack of any control mechanisms employed by the Labour Department to ensure that the terms of employment are complied with, or for inspecting the conditions under which these women live was ascribed to the particularity of their "workplace" which comes under the "private sphere" and is protected by law. It can be claimed that this constitutes deferential treatment, as the Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance does exercise respective control in the case of all other employees—migrants or Cypriots—through the Department of Labour Inspection. As a matter of fact, one of the Department's responsibilities is to inspect the premises or workplace of a Cypriot employer applying for the employment of a TCN, before hiring approval is granted by the Labour Department, a procedure which is not followed in the case of migrant domestic workers. This suggests the possibility that these women are not considered to be part of the labour market, something consistent with the fact that the Ministry of Labour is not responsible for the preparation of their employment contracts in the first place.

93. Presentation of preliminary results of a research, 2006: European Mobility Year in an Enlarged Europe, on behalf of the Labour Department of the Ministry of Labour, 2/10/2006, Lefkosia.

94. Ibid 18

95. Ibid 66

96. Research undertaken and expressed in: Ibid 66

97. Domestic work in Cyprus is not recognised as a labor sector.

98. Case studies presented in Ibid 18

99. Ibid 66

It is pertinent to note that public perception towards higher skilled migrants, who enjoy a correspondingly high social status and level of wealth, is significantly more positive than the attitude towards migrants working in lower skilled professions. If we then take into account that “women are over-represented in low-skilled jobs, and there are indications that they fill a significant number of jobs in the clandestine economy”,¹⁰⁰ the public’s perception has an even more detrimental impact on the likelihood of migrant women being treated equally. Local idioms often reflect such racially discriminatory perceptions - ‘I work like a black (person)’ is a common expression, carrying patently racist connotations. As reported by migrants themselves,¹⁰¹ this abusive term is often hurled at them outside their working environment. Similarly, as more and more Asian women have taken up domestic work in Cypriot households, a common phrase used among Greek Cypriots is ‘What do you think I am? Your Asian/Filipino woman?’. This perception places women who form the majority¹⁰² of migrant workers in a more vulnerable position in society with respect to their experience of discrimination and also hinders their inclusion and integration.

The immigration policy which regulates the employment of TCNs has been described as controlling “migrant workers on a short-term, temporary, employer-tied and restricted-to-specific-sectors basis”.¹⁰³ TCNs have “little, if any opportunity for training and betterment and no opportunity whatsoever to progress or advance in the employment ladder in terms of promotion or career move, as their stay is dependent on the particular job and employer”.¹⁰⁴

This aptly reflects the situation particularly with respect to female migrant domestic workers in Cyprus who “experience many barriers and disincentives often in the form of exclusion from the labour market, major social, legal and political institutions as well as exclusion within communities and neighbourhoods”.¹⁰⁵ Statistics indicate that the labour market in Cyprus is strongly gender segregated. According to Eurostat,¹⁰⁶ out of 21,060 immigrants in 2008, 55% (11,598) were female, while in 2015, out of 15,183, the proportion rose to 57% (8,688).

Further, female migrant domestic workers are mainly recruited from countries in South-East Asia (Sri Lanka and the Philippines) and constitute the largest group of TCNs employed in Cyprus. According to gender segregated data relating to long-term immigrants by country of origin and purpose of arrival, it is evident that the vast majority of immigrants are from Sri Lanka and the Philippines and are female.¹⁰⁷ The Civil Registry and Migration Department recorded a total of 57,672 work permits in 2015, out of which 18,549 (32%) were granted to domestic workers.¹⁰⁸

100. Ibid 18

101. The Cyprus Weekly, 7 – 13 October 1997

102. Regarding the gender distribution of migrants, Eurostat underlined that across the EU Member States in 2015, there were slightly more men than women, however, by contrast, Cyprus had the highest share of female immigrants (57%): http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Migration_and_migrant_population_statistics

103. Trimikliniotis and Fulas-Souroulla, Mapping of policies affecting female migrants and policy analysis: the Cyprus case, Working Paper No. 11 – WP1, December 2006.

104. Charakis K, (ed) (2005), Anti-social behaviour of Cypriot Youth – Racist Tendencies (Αντικοινωνική Συμπεριφορά των Νέων της Κύπρου – Ρατσιστικές Τάσεις), Athens, Sakoulas.

105. Castles, Rogers, Vasta and Vertovec, Report on Migration and Social Integration of Migrant – Report on the Assessment of research reports carried out under the European Commission Targeted Socio-Economic Research (TSER) Programme, Centre for Migration and Policy Research, University of Oxford, Brussels (2003).

106. http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=migr_imm2ctz&lang=en (accessed 19 December 2017).

107. Ibid 8, pp. 36-37

108. Immigration statistics for 2015: <http://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/crmd/crmd.nsf/All/083980C0BA1B224AC2257EA4003861BA?OpenDocument> (accessed 19 December 2017)

Research¹⁰⁹ has been undertaken to determine the reasons behind the increased demand for in-house female migrant domestic workers in Cyprus. Justifications include the fact that there is a growing number of women entering the labour market who require domestic workers to undertake what was previously their own unpaid domestic chores, a lack of comprehensive state welfare for the elderly, children and disabled persons, and the need to elevate one's own social status by projecting the economic capacity to employ such a worker. Some of these justifications point towards a perpetuation of gender stereotypes and inequality.

The legislation pertaining to the employment of domestic workers has not been gender mainstreamed nor have the specific needs of migrant women been taken into consideration.¹¹⁰ Despite the fact that the employment contract¹¹¹ specifically tailored to domestic workers will involve predominantly women, the employee throughout the document is referred to using male pronouns.¹¹² Furthermore, whereas the Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance is tasked with drafting and preparing employment contracts for migrant workers, the Civil Registry and Migration department is the authority which drafts employment contracts for domestic workers and 'artistes' specifically; this poses questions and concerns as to the level of protection and redress afforded to these 2 categories of workers.

Employment contracts for domestic workers include a restrictive clause linking the employee's labour and residence permit to one specific employer for a maximum of six years. A change in employer is now permitted but limited to two changes over the six year period and a change in sector is possible only with the approval of the Ministry of Interior. The close link which exists between the specific, named employer and the residence permit has been criticised by ECRI, who have ascertained that it may result in migrant workers having to endure "serious situations of exploitation and abuse in order to avoid deportation".¹¹³ Moreover, as domestic workers reside in the employer's abode, this has been said¹¹⁴ to give rise to "the development of an atypical relationship" which often takes on the form of an "ownership relationship". The fact that the domestic worker lives and works in a very 'insulated' environment severely limits and restricts her integration in the wider community; proactive measures which will encourage or facilitate her integration are therefore required. The concern is that the aforementioned atypical relationship may give rise to any of a number of discriminatory practices on the part of the employer which, compounded by the lack of accessibility or awareness of available forms of redress or assistance, may further marginalise the migrant domestic workers.

As domestic workers are eligible to work for a maximum of six years, they cannot fulfil the seven-year continuous legal residence requirement which is needed to qualify for Cypriot citizenship. The application procedure itself has been described as lengthy, "costly (500 euros application fees), and discretionary; they can be refused on account of 'lack of good character'".¹¹⁵ ECRI, however, has noted that some improvements have been made, resulting in an increase in the number of persons

109. Ibid 8

110. Christodoulou and Zobnina, Investigating Trafficking in women for labour exploitation in domestic work: The Case of Cyprus, in Combatting Trafficking in women for labour exploitation in domestic work, University of Nicosia, Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies, 2015.

111. The conditions for employing a domestic worker can be found on the Civil Registry and Migration department website: <http://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/crmd/crmd.nsf/All/5314ED0D3F68CA9EC2257D2C003A4DC2?OpenDocument> (accessed 15 December 2017).

112. Contract of Employment:

[http://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/crmd/crmd.nsf/All/5314ED0D3F68CA9EC2257D2C003A4DC2/\\$file/DOMESTIC%20WORKER%20ContractOfEmploymentEN.pdf](http://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/crmd/crmd.nsf/All/5314ED0D3F68CA9EC2257D2C003A4DC2/$file/DOMESTIC%20WORKER%20ContractOfEmploymentEN.pdf) (accessed 19 December 2017)

113. https://www.coe.int/t/dghl/monitoring/ecri/activities/annual_reports/Annual%20report%202011.pdf

114. Ibid 8

115. Ibid 33

acquiring citizenship: in 2013, 328 persons were naturalised compared to 1,010 in 2014.¹¹⁶ It is clear that the government considers female domestic migrant workers as temporary workers and as such, this approach perpetuates their invisibility and vulnerable position as they are not considered 'worthy' subjects of any long-term integration immigration policy.

Another category of vulnerable migrants who warrant attention and who also fall outside the realm of integration policies are women in prostitution / the sex industry. The available literature demonstrates an awareness of their vulnerable and precarious status in which they can easily be, and often are, victimised, as well as of their dependence on their employer in order to maintain their residence permit. The government's approach towards women in this industry has been widely criticised and has resulted in the perpetuation of working conditions which exploit, violate and humiliate female migrant workers.¹¹⁷ As documented in various research reports,¹¹⁸ trafficking for sexual exploitation has been an insurmountable problem for many years in Cyprus. The extent of the problem is best illustrated by the 2010 landmark ruling of the European Court of Human Rights, *Rantsev v Cyprus and Russia*,¹¹⁹ which concerned Oxana Rantseva, a young Russian woman, strongly believed to have been trafficked for the purposes of sexual exploitation, who fell to her death from the balcony of her employer's private apartment in an attempt to escape. The verdict stated that Cyprus had exhibited a "failure to provide for an appropriate legal and administrative framework to combat trafficking and to properly investigate how and where the victim was recruited".

With respect to beneficiaries of international protection, according to a 2013 UNHCR report,¹²⁰ labour market mobility for asylum seekers in Cyprus is the most unfavourable within the EU. Asylum seekers access is restricted to a small number of professions, mostly in agriculture, fishery, manufacturing, waste management and wholesale trade-repairs. They face particular challenges in obtaining recognition of their educational and professional qualifications. There are also no measures to assist asylum seekers who have been recognised as beneficiaries of international protection to obtain social welfare or find accommodation and employment. As a result, many remain in the reception centre in conditions which have been deemed by ECRI as "not at all conducive to integration". The general climate within Cypriot society with regards to refugees, and migrants in general, demonstrates a lack of understanding and sends signals that they are unwelcome. This attitude has dissuaded many employers from investing or targeting them as potential employees.

This reality is incongruous with the relevant legislation focusing on refugees. Under the Cyprus refugee law, a person who is recognised as a refugee should receive equal treatment to the citizens of the Republic with regards to wage-earning employment. In other words, refugees have the same rights as Cypriot citizens to employment; there are no regulatory restrictions on access across sectors of employment and there is no need for the Labour Department to approve and stamp a contract of employment between an employer and a recognized refugee.¹²¹ When it comes to beneficiaries of subsidiary protection, as in the case of recognised refugees, they have immediate access to employment upon the date they are granted the above status. In particular, there are no restrictions

116. The figures for 2014 include the naturalisation of EU as well as third country nationals.

117. Ibid 66

118. Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies, Mapping the Realities of Trafficking in women for the purpose of sexual exploitation in Cyprus, 2007, <http://www.medinstgenderstudies.org/wp/?p=322>

119. https://ec.europa.eu/anti-trafficking/legislation-and-case-law-case-law/rantsev-v-cyprus-and-russia-application-no-2596504_en (accessed 19 December 2017)

120. Ibid 30

121. Information Sheet: Employment of Asylum Seekers, the Department of Labour, Ministry of Labour, Welfare and Social Insurance. Available at http://www.mlsi.gov.cy/mlsi/dl/dl.nsf/page5j_en/page5j_en?OpenDocument

regarding their employment in particular occupations or sectors of the labour market. Further, it is not necessary for the Labour Department to approve and stamp a contract of employment between an employer and a person with subsidiary protection status. The only restriction from a legislative point of view, has to do with their legal status while their applications are being processed by the system; asylum seekers are not entitled to work during the first six months from the date of submission of their asylum application. After the initial six months, asylum seekers are allowed to be employed in the following categories:¹²²

S/N	Industry fields	Occupation
1	Agriculture	~Agriculture Laborers
	Animal Husbandry	~Animal Husbandry Laborers
	Fishery	~Fishery Laborers
2	Manufacture	~Forage Production Laborers
3	Waste Management	~Drainage and Waste Processing Laborers
		~Garbage and Trash Collection & Processing Laborers
		~Recycling Laborers
		~Offal Processing Laborers
4	Wholesale Trade-Repairs	~Gas Station and Car Wash Laborers
		~Freight Handlers of Wholesale Trade
5	Other Fields	~Building and Outdoors Cleaners
		~Distributors of Advertising and Informative Material
		~Food Delivery

Additionally, all applicants and recipients of material reception conditions, who are physically and psychologically able to take up employment, are required to register as unemployed after the initial six month period and show that they are actively seeking employment. A labour card is issued to asylum seekers and their unemployment status is confirmed either on a monthly or bi-monthly basis.

There is no formal limitation to their working hours. The standard remuneration for farming and agricultural jobs is set for 80 working hours per fortnight, spread over 6 working days a week.

In practice, asylum seekers still face significant obstacles in accessing the labour market. According to a report by the Commissioner for Administration regarding access of asylum seekers to employment, available data from July 2015 indicated that only 10, all men, out of 89 registered asylum seekers took up work.¹²³ The major obstacles as described by the Cyprus Refugee Council are summarised as follows :¹²⁴

122. IBID

123. Ombudsman, Report on access of female asylum seekers to employment and social welfare, 1799/2016, 11 November 2016, available in Greek at: <http://bit.ly/2kmGMDG>.

124. Information as received by the Cyprus Refugee Council

- **Low wages and lack of supplementary material assistance:** This is particularly problematic for asylum seekers with families. Remuneration from employment in agriculture and animal farming falls far short of meeting the basic needs of a family. Labour conditions, such as mandatory accommodation at the place of work, often lead to splitting up the family. These jobs are often offered to single parents with young children without taking into consideration the care or support of the children or the possibility of providing supplementary assistance.
- **Distance and lack of convenient transportation:** Given the nature of employment that asylum seekers are permitted to take up, workplaces are often situated in remote rural regions and working hours may start as early as 4 or 5am. Asylum seekers have reported difficulties in commuting to these workplaces using low-cost transportation (e.g. public buses). Remuneration does not cover travel expenses.
- **Language barriers:** Lack of communication skills in Greek and English often impede the efficient communication between officials of Labour Offices as well as potential employers. Many asylum seekers are unable to understand their prospective employers' needs or views during meetings and/ or the employers' requirements on their job referral forms.
- **Low demand:** There is a lack of interest from employers in the agricultural and farming sectors in employing asylum seekers. In fact, many employers in these sectors often prefer to employ TCNs who arrive in the country with an employment permit and are authorised to work for a period up to four years. In order to receive a license for the employment of TCNs, an employer is required to register at the Labour Office in addition to actively seeking for employees locally, nationally or within the EU.¹²⁵ As asylum seekers are referred to them by the Labour Office, the employers may try to avoid recruiting them, hoping that if they do not hire an asylum seeker, they will be able to invite/hire other workers on a working visa. They often frame the labour in such a way that the asylum seekers refuse to take on the work.
- **Lack of gender and cultural sensitivity in the recruitment procedure:** Female asylum seekers often face difficulties accessing employment for reasons related to cultural barriers.¹²⁶ For example, many women have never worked before and especially when it comes to the conditions in the sectors of agriculture and animal farming (remoteness, staying overnight, male dominated work spaces) there is a need for gradual and facilitated transition to employment. Women from Muslim backgrounds wearing visible symbols of their religious identity e.g. hijab / niqab report to have faced difficulties accessing the labour market, as in some cases, they were considered as unable to maintain employment due to their attire, according to the experience of Cyprus Refugee Council.

125. Circular on the Strategy for the Employment of Third Country Nationals (Στρατηγική για την Απασχόληση Αλλοδαπών), May 2008

126. Ombudsman, Report on access of female asylum seekers to employment and social welfare, 1799/2016, 11 November 2016, available in Greek at: <http://bit.ly/2kmGMDG>

When it comes to vocational training that will enable asylum seekers and refugees to access different sectors of employment, according to the information provided by the Cyprus Refugee Council there is no vocational education programs targeted specifically to refugees. Vocational Education and Training (VET) programmes are implemented by a variety of public and private institutions and enterprises.¹²⁷ Adult refugees are allowed to participate in the state-regulated vocational education system, provided that they fulfil the language and entry criteria. Examples of commonly-sought technical, upper secondary and post-secondary, non-tertiary, state-regulated vocational training programmes, leading to formal qualifications, are the following:¹²⁸

1. *Programmes consisting of afternoon and evening classes taking place in technical schools.* One or three-year programmes are provided by technical schools, which are administered by the Department of Secondary Technical and Vocational Education of the Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC). A variety of technical courses are offered (e.g. plumbing, electrical installations, engineering, computers, car mechanics, cooking and graphic design). Completion of the one-year programme leads to a certificate of attendance. The successful completion of a three-year programme leads to the acquisition of a leaving certificate equivalent to that awarded to graduates of upper secondary general or technical and vocational education, as far as the technical component is concerned (EQF, Level 4). Fees apply for these courses, ranging from 154 to 257 euro, per year.

2. *Post-secondary institutes offering vocational education and training.* These have been in operation since 2012 and offer technical specialisation (EQF level 5). They operate within existing technical schools within the remit of MoEC. The courses last two years and include workplace learning in enterprises and industrial units. A variety of technical programmes are offered such as management of natural gas, industrial and residential installations, gas handling pipes, welding and industrial structures, bakery and confectionery, computer and communication networks, electrical and industrial refrigeration installations, installation and maintenance of photovoltaic systems and wind turbines, industrial and residential automation etc. Attendance is free of charge. Applicants should be younger than 35 and hold a school leaving certificate as well their grade transcripts.

Attendance by asylum seekers and refugees is extremely limited due to language restrictions, lack of information and guidance, lack of necessary documents and/or funds. Other forms of training targeted to unemployed adults, which do not provide formal qualifications, but offer professional development and bringing specific skills up to date, are training programmes provided or subsidised by Human Resource and Development Authority (HRDA). These are offered mainly through the Public Employment Services and are offered mostly in Greek which makes access difficult for refugees and asylum seekers.

127. For an exhaustive list: https://cumulus.cedefop.europa.eu/files/vetelib/2016/2016_CR_CY.pdf

128. The information as provided in writing provided by the Cyprus Refugee Council, Mano Mathioudakis, Integration Officer of Cyprus Refugee Council, author Mano Mathioudakis, Integration Officer of Cyprus Refugee Council

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